

Report 3. Impact evaluation of FP6 (last call) and FP7 SSH research projects

Project acronym: **IMPACT-EV**

Project title: **Evaluating the impact and outcomes of European SSH research**

Grant Agreement number: 613202

Coordinator: Universitat de Barcelona

Funding Scheme: Collaborative Project

Due date of deliverable: Month 15

Actual submission date: Month 19

Start date of the project: 01/01/2014

Project duration: 48 months

Work package: 3

Task(s): 2

Deliverable: D3.2

Dissemination level: Public

Lead beneficiary for this deliverable: Data Archiving and Networked Services – DANS-KNAW. Andrea Scharnhorst

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Table of contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Sample and sources of data	4
2.1. Sample	4
2.2. Data collection	5
2.3. Data analysis	8
2.4. Limitations	9
3. Scientific impact.....	11
3.1. Overview.....	11
3.2. Success Stories	14
4. Political impact.....	17
4.1. Overview.....	17
4.2. Success stories.....	18
5. Social impact.....	25
5.1. Overview.....	25
5.2. Success stories.....	27
6. Impact on strengthening ERA	30
6.1. Overview.....	30
6.2. Success stories.....	34
7. Conclusions.....	37
References	40
Annex 1: List of Acronyms.....	41
Annex 2: List of projects	43
Annex 3: Questionnaire	69
Annex 4: Bibliometric analysis	99
Annex 5: Webometric Analysis.....	202
Annex 6: Fact sheets of successful projects (social impact)	207
Annex 7: Baseline statistics of projects (FP6 and FP7).....	247

1. Introduction

In this report, we present an impact assessment of a total of 439 SSH projects funded under FP6 (last call) and FP7 SSH in four domains: scientific, political, social and the promotion of the European Research Area. Scientific impact refers to the publications, citation patterns, and dissemination among scientific networks, as well as further research development. Political impact means the transfer of research outcomes and political recommendations into EU and national policies, and the use of research outcomes by civil society led or other entities in their political agendas.¹ Social impact occurs when there is evidence of social improvements in relation to the goals defined by legitimated political representatives which are the EU2020 targets, the objectives of the Lisbon strategy, or now the Juncker's Agenda for Jobs, Growth, Fairness and Democratic Change, as the result of implementing research results.² IMPACT-EV is particularly interested in exploring the social impact that the research projects have obtained in relation to the EU2020 targets (such as increased employment, reducing school dropout or reducing poverty rates) or the objectives of the Lisbon strategy. Finally, impact on strengthening ERA includes aspects such as mobility, training young researchers, interdisciplinarity, and international collaboration, among other related items.³ Thus, this report has been conducted during the first 15 months of the project. In what follow, we present general considerations and specific examples of the impacts of SSH in several fields, as well as a selection of those projects with the highest identified impact in each dimension.

¹ Economic and Social Research Council, United Kingdom. (2013). What is impact? Available at: <http://www.esrc.ac.uk/funding-and-guidance/impact-toolkit/what-how-and-why/what-is-research-impact.aspx>

² Flecha, R. (2014). *Cómo lograr impacto en los proyectos del Reto 6 [How to achieve impact in Challenge 6 projects?]*. H2020 Informative Day for Challenge 6. January, 22nd, 23rd, and 24th in Madrid, Barcelona and Bilbao.

³ European Commission. (2012). *A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth*. COM (2012) 392 final, Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/era/pdf/ere-communication/era-communication_en.pdf

2. Sample and sources of data

In order to accomplish the objective of drawing a map of the impacts of the EC-funded SSH research projects we have used a mixed methodology, combining quantitative with qualitative methods of data collection. We present here the sample, the data collection techniques and sources, and the data analysis main strategy.

2.1. Sample

In total, the sample of this report IMPACT-EV has consisted on 513 projects, covering both FP6 (last call) and FP7 programmes.

FP – Call	Funding scheme	N
FP6: last call of Priority 7 projects (Citizens and governance in a knowledge-based society) ⁴ FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4, FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5.	Integrative Projects	12
	Specific Target Research Projects (STREP)	48
	Network of Excellence	2
FP6: last call of Priority 8 projects (Scientific Support to Policies) ⁵ . FP6-2005-SSP-5A; FP6-2005-SSP-5B-INFLUENZA.	Specific Target Research Projects (STREP)	32
FP7: SSH projects of the Cooperation Programme ⁶ . FP7-SSH-2007-1; FP7-Adhoc-2007-13; FP7-ERANET-2008-RTD; FP7-SSH-2009-A; FP7-SSH-2009-B; FP7-SSH-2010-1; FP7-SSH-2010-2; FP7-SSH-2010-3; FP7-SSG-2010-4; FP7-SSH-2011-1; FP7-SSH-2011-2; SSH-2011-3; FP7-ERANET-2011-RTD; FP7-SSH-2012-1; FP7-SSH-2012-2; FP7-ERANET-2012-RTD; FP7-SSH-2013-1; FP7-SSH-2013-2.	CP-FP (Collaborative projects small or medium-scale)	170
	CP-IP (Collaborative projects large scale)	28
	CP-FP-SICA (small and medium)	14
	CP-IP-SICA (large scale)	1
	CP-SICA (small, medium and large)	2
	CSA-CA	9
	CSA-ERA-PLUS	2

⁴ All IPs, STREPs and NoEs funded within the last call were selected in the sample. Projects funded under FP6-2004-CITIZENS-6 were exclusively SSA so they were not included.

⁵ We selected STREPs Projects from Area 2 “Providing Health, Security and Opportunity to the People of Europe” and Area 3 “Underpinning the Economic Potential & Cohesion of a Larger and More Integrated EU” as more aligned to SSH issues. Projects within Area 1 “Sustainable Management of Europe's Natural Resources” were not included in the sample.

⁶ All Calls and projects of SSH of the Cooperation Programme.

	CSA-SA	24
	BSG-CSO (Benefit Specific Groups-Civil Society Organizations)	2
HERA (Humanities in the European⁷ HERA JRP I-Humanities as a Source of Creativity and Innovation	Projects funded under HERA	19
NORFACE⁸ FP7-ERANET-2008-RTD	Projects funded under NORFACE	24
ERC Ideas⁹	Starting Grants	53
	Advanced Grants	29
Non SSH projects which include SSH research in an embedded form. Health FP7-HEALTH-2007-A; FP7-HEALTH-2007-B; FP7-HEALTH-2009-single-stage ¹⁰	CP-FP (small or medium-scale focused projects)	35
Non SSH projects which include SSH research in an embedded form. Energy. FP7-ENERGY-2007-1-RT; FP7-ENERGY-2009-2; FP7-ENERGY-2009-3; FP7-ICT-2011-7 ¹¹	CP-Collaborative project (generic)	1
	CP-FP (Small or medium)	5
	CP-IP (large scale)	1
TOTAL		513

2.2. Data collection

The evaluation has been conducted based on mixed methods. The research team has gathered a variety and complementarity of the data, in order to conduct critical, evidence-based assessment of the projects' impacts. In this regard, the following sources of information have been used, combining both qualitative and quantitative data:

⁷ All the HERA I projects (2010-2013), under the *Humanities as a Source of Creativity and Innovation* and *Cultural Dynamics: Inheritance and Identity* themes, have been taken into account for selection. The HERA II projects were disregarded as they started in 2013 (18 projects).

⁸ All projects funded under NORFACE Research Programme: *Re-emergence of Religion as a Social Force in Europe?*, and NORFACE Plus *Migration in Europe - Social, Economic, Cultural and Policy Dynamics* initiatives were selected for the sample.

⁹ All projects finished by 31 December 2013 were selected.

¹⁰ Selection of projects related to public health policies and a SSH dimension embedded. This selection was provided by the officers on IMPACT-EV request.

¹¹ Selection of projects related to Energy, economics of energy and a SSH dimension embedded. This selection was provided by the officers on IMPACT-EV request.

1) E-CORDA data on participants in SSH FP7 Cooperation Programme.

2) Data available at the CORDIS web page and on projects webpages

For those projects not available in the E-CORDA database, we obtained data (i.e. EC contribution, participant institutions, etc) from the CORDIS web page and other related Webpages (in the case of HERA and NORFACE). We also used structured data from the OpenDataEU initiative about FP6 and FP7 SSH projects¹². We complemented this information with links to projects websites, and performed a webometric analysis based on this (see annex 5)

3) IMPACT-EV Online questionnaire (N=473). The online **questionnaire** was sent to all PI's of all projects excepting those FP7 projects funded by the last two calls corresponding to 2013 (FP7-SSH-2013-1 and FP7-SSH-2013-2). This is an instrument with multiple choice and open-ended questions focused on obtaining information and analysing the four types of impact from SSH research projects: Social, Political, Scientific impact and Strengthening ERA. The questionnaire was elaborated on the basis of a number of indicators defined based on a review of relevant scientific literature (explored in Report 1), already existing questionnaires for impact evaluation (e.g. *Payback*¹³ and *Pocarim*¹⁴), and the EU2020 targets and Lisbon 2010 structural indicators. The questionnaire focuses on relevant information about research impact that is not available in existing databases, organized in four sections (i.e. scientific, political, social and ERA impacts). The questionnaire was sent to all the partners asking to review it.

The questionnaire was **piloted** with eight main researchers. Four of the researchers responded partially the questionnaire. The final version of the online questionnaire was placed on the web service limesurvey (<http://www.limesurvey.org>) and an individual link was sent to all the projects selected in the final sample. In order to insure an acceptable questionnaire return rate, follow-up phone calls to all main researchers who were not replying were conducted. We have realised several phone calls rounds, mainly in July 2014, September – October 2014, January – February 2015.

4) SESAM database. The reports (Final and/or Periodic depending on availability) of 162 FP7 projects were facilitated by the Scientific Officers and have been analysed.¹⁵ From all the reports analysed, 119 contained the section on “societal

¹² <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp6projects> and <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp7projects>

¹³ Donovan, C. & Hanney, S. (2011). The ‘Payback Framework’ explained. *Research Evaluation*, 20(3), 181–183.

DOI: 10.3152/095820211X13118583635756.

¹⁴ POCARIM. Mapping the Population, Careers, Mobilities and Impacts of Advanced Research Degree Graduates in the Social Sciences and Humanities. (2012-2015). European Commission. Seventh Framework Programme.

¹⁵ We have excluded 23 reports corresponding to CSA-CA, CSA-SA and CSA-ERA-Plus – ERA-NET Plus projects, as they were not included in the sample of this report.

implications” which was exploited in relation to different issues of interest for this report (e.g. Interdisciplinarity, Gender Issues).

- 5) **Interviews with EC Scientific Officers.** CREA researchers conducted a total of 15 interviews to scientific officers of the Unit B6 Reflexive Societies of the DG Research & Innovation. All interviews were recorded and notes were used to identify projects with potential impacts.
- 6) **Interviews with main researchers** were conducted to obtain further information and clarification on the project impacts (through telephone and online-video calls). These researchers were selected based on: the questionnaires’ answers, scientific officers’ suggestions or after email exchanges. The interviews lasted 30 – 60 minutes in each case and notes were included in the analysis of data. The majority of these researchers have been very cooperative and they have contacted the consortium they have coordinated in order to gather further information about their impacts.

We have placed a relevant effort on reaching the main researchers of all projects, in order to promote their participation in the questionnaire, as well as to ask for complementary information, clarify aspects regarding impact or making agreements for interviews. A template was sent to the main researchers of the FP7 projects from which we had not yet received information, including those from the last calls, who did not received the questionnaire. Overall, the IMPACT-EV coordination team has made more than 1400 phone calls, as they are showed in the following summary table:

Table 1: Overview of contact strategies with PI’s and main researchers

	FP6 - 7	FP6 - 8	FP7	HER A	Norface	Health	Energy	ERC	Total	Calls average
Not contacted (1- 3 attempt)	17	18	51	9	15	24	6	40	180	360
Not contacted (more than 3 attempts)	8	3	57	5	5	2	0	13	93	372
Contacted_no further information (1 to 3 contacts)	16	9	34	1	4	6	1	21	92	184
Contacted_no further information (more than 3 contacts)	16	2	29	4		0		6	57	228
Contacted_further information (1 to 3 contacts)	5		29			2		2	38	76
Contacted_further information (more than 3 contacts)			27						27	108
Contacted_further information_interview			25			1			26	104
Total general	62	32	252	19	24	35	7	82	513	1432

- 7) **Complementary information of the individual projects** from web pages, public reports and scientific papers (desk research). In this regard, a cross-checking information process has been conducted to avoid biased results. We usually asked for additional external information from the main researchers to confirm the data obtained from their own sources, including if needed to ask for information provided by other stakeholder groups and, when possible, with information from independent third parties or official statistics. The contacted researchers provides us with a wealth of additional information such as reports, links to videos and media, interviews to policy makers with references to their researches and other reports. In several cases, the ImpactEV research team also searched for complementary sources. The main aim of the multi-source, multi-channel information gathering process was to identify robust evidence for the objective of ImpactEV, that is the evaluation of impact and outcomes of the SSH research in Europe.
- 8) **Bibliometric analysis** conducted (see Annex 4 for a more detailed account).
- 9) **Webometric analysis** conducted (see annex 5 for a more detailed account).
- 10) **Specific study of the scientific excellence and productivity of the research teams** of a sample of 134 projects from FP7 Cooperation. From each one of these projects, an exploration of the websites has been done in order to identify all the researchers of their teams. From this analysis, a total of 3540 researchers have been identified. For each of those researchers manually bibliographic records of their publications in sources indexed by the Thompson Reuter Web of Science, including citations have been downloaded for a particular bibliometric analysis.
- 11) The **FP7 OpenAIRE project**. Available at: <https://www.openaire.eu/> Desk research on individual projects and their outputs has been performed.
- 12) **Previous assessment, evaluation reports and other relevant documents**. We have taken into account previous assessments and evaluation reports regarding the Framework Programmes as well as specific issues (such as promotion of ERA from SSH, HERA action and others).

2.3. Data analysis

The analysis has been differently conducted for quantitative and qualitative data. The questionnaire data was transferred into SPSS. We have also conducted a quantitative analysis of other information such as employment data gathered in the specific sections of “societal implications” in the questionnaire or the above mentioned bibliometric data. Additionally, some baseline statistics were conducted analysing information such as the number of projects, main institutions involved, volume and duration of investments. Qualitative analysis was conducted on the available information from the research projects. Beyond the wide range of benefits and effects of the research projects, we have made an effort to identify specific impacts supported by evidences. The analysis has been focused on these actual impacts rather than on the aims, theme, disciplines and

contributions of the projects. The qualitative analysis has allowed us to identify projects which have done relevant contributions in every dimension. Quantitative and qualitative method have been integrated in writing up this report. In particular together they informed the development of the a system of scores for different impact dimensions, and related rankings of projects. This will be introduced in detail in the next sections.

The analytical categories that have guided our review have been the evaluation criteria set by the European Commission: the relevance of the research, or extent of the correspondence of the objectives to the needs within the EU has been analysed as regards the projects' correspondence with the Lisbon 2010, EU2020 objectives and Juncker's Agenda for Jobs, Growth, Fairness and Democratic Change, as they has been one of the main criteria for social impact assessment. We explicitly asked for the changes/effects occurred as a result of the project and for evidences that could ensure this attribution (effectiveness), and for the justification of the costs given the effects achieved (efficiency). Other dimensions have been also considered. For instance, the sustainability of the changes was taken into account in the analysis of the social impact, and much of the information gathered made references to the stakeholders' satisfaction and their perceptions. Objective and quantifiable data on the effects achieved and information primarily reported by sources external to the project was asked to be provided whenever possible in order to avoid social impact attributions based only on subjective perceptions. Finally, equity and specifically gender issues have been also considered both in social impact and in the impact on ERA.¹⁶

2.4. Limitations

In our assessment we have encountered some limitations that should be acknowledged here:

- Some of the reviewed projects are still ongoing. This limits the possibility to identify all projects' subsequent impacts, as they might not occur yet or limited information is available yet.
- Limited access to projects' reporting information. The CORDIS webpage of the European Commission contains reports of several of the projects. For the analysis of reports, we took into account those facilitated by the European Commission. These were 162 reports available of FP7, 119 of them were Final Reports or Periodic Reports that contain information regarding the "societal implications" of the projects. This limitation is even more marked as not for all projects we could obtain information on the same level of detail (?). In short, different information is available for different sets of projects. At the end, this makes it impossible provide comparable quantitative data for all the projects enclosed in our sample.¹⁷

¹⁶ European Commission. (2013). Public consultation on Commission Guidelines for Evaluation.

¹⁷ This lack of data integration and harmonization on the level of project information of EC funding is currently tackled by a new project RISIS – Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation Studies, www.risis.eu

- Availability of the projects' websites. As part of the data collection process we collected URL's to project websites and not all of them are available anymore. This limitation was more frequent for FP6 projects. Difficult access to main researchers. Diverse situations have made very difficult or impossible reaching out, being impossible to follow up the questionnaire or even sending the invitation to participate. Situations like: retirement, incorrect contact details, change of institutions, and other situations.
- Lack of tradition among the SSH scientific community to gather information and evidences about the impact of their projects. While data regarding their scientific impact has been usually collected, it is not that usual to gather information about the political and social impact achieved. This, as already mentioned, has been in many cases transformed in the course of the interviews and informal conversations we have held with researchers.
- Evidences cannot be collected for all projects along all dimensions. It was not possible to gather the same amount of evidence for all projects.

3. Scientific impact

3.1. Overview

Scientific impact has been widely developed and debated in all disciplines, in the specific case of the SSH, this debate has been always marked by the recognition of the specific features of these areas. In this report, we have explored different issues related to the scientific excellence and productivity of the SSH funded projects. This analysis reveals that the reviewed projects have a significant scientific impact, not only producing a considerable number of publications (mainly articles, and books) but also through their citations, conference presentations and leading to subsequent research opportunities.

Excellent researchers

It is a fact that SSH projects involve research consortiums of excellent researchers. Scientific productivity of these scholars is a clear indicator of this excellence. We analysed a sample of 134 FP7 projects. For those projects we identified 3540 participating researchers. We looked those researchers up in the Web of Knowledge – a database of Thomson Reuters. We found that in 98 of those projects (73% of them) at least one of the researchers has more than 10 JCR publications. The analysis also shows that the consortiums have on average 98 JCR articles. This finding demonstrates how FP7 was able to attract and promote excellent research teams across Europe. This data is worth being highlighted taking into account the lesser tradition of dissemination through scientific publications in SSH as compared with other fields of research.

s

The average of JCR publications per researcher is 3,71 taking into account that this figure includes a significant amount of young researchers with no publications. Excluding those with 1 or 0 publications, the average goes up to 8,5 per researcher. It is a proof of the high level of scientific publication of the researchers and the importance of the training of early career researchers.

Another proof of the excellence criteria is the presence of many top researchers in the projects awarded with different prizes and distinctions. At the international level, we find highly recognized researchers, such as the Nobel Prize in economy Jean Tirole, who has been involved in three projects. Other international awards are the annual distinction of the International Social Science Council (ISSC), the Schumpeter Prize Competition, or the recognition of being among the top 5% economists in the RePEc

(Research Papers in Economics) worldwide ranking¹⁸. At the European level, we find awards such as the one from the European Science Foundation on pioneering demographic research, and an Yrjo Jahnsson medal awarded by the European Economic Association. Finally, national prizes include for instance a National Natural Science Prize, an Honorary Fellow of the Royal Society of New Zealand, a Certificate of Merit for Pre-Eminent Contribution to Creative Legal Scholarship by American Society of International Law, or a Fellow of the British Academy.

Publications' patterns

According to the data collected in the IMPACT-EV questionnaire, scientific publications tend to be the most common procedure to disseminate new knowledge within the scientific community. By analyzing the researchers' responses to the question about their 10 most representative publications, most of the publications are peer reviewed journal articles (68%), followed by book chapters (11,4%) and books (9,8%). Publicly available Full reports (3,3%) are also present in various projects while non-peer-reviewed journal articles (2,4%), journal editorials (2,5%) newsletters (0,8%) are less common. Different to other scientific areas, the specific importance for SSH research of books is important to be highlighted here, as if it is ignored, it does not fully reflect the disciplinary tradition.

The data obtained from the project reports' section on "societal implications" (119 projects) available on SESAM shows that the 78% of projects have published articles in peer reviewed journals, leading to an average of 16 articles per project. Half of these projects (50,5%) have published between 1 and 10 articles, and the other half (49,5%) have published more than 10, in a range between 11 articles and 115 (GINI). The latter half has published a sum of 1.253 articles, which are the 85% of all the articles published. This can be partly explained by the time when these projects were conducted, as the number of year passed since the projects finished is slightly lower for those that have published more than 10 articles (3,37 years) than for those that published 10 or less (3,78 years). Indeed, more recent projects tend to have as average more publications: projects finished in 2013: 21,65 articles; finished in 2012: 12,44 articles; finished in 2011: 10,45 articles; finished in 2010: 9,79 articles. These data shows a positive trend in terms of scientific impact.

In terms of citation patterns, data from the IMPACT-EV questionnaire indicates that in the cases in which the Journal Citation Report (JCR) quartile is reported in the questionnaire, articles tend to be published in the first quartile. Thus, drawing from other impact factor sources, the number of citations in Scopus and Google Scholar reveals that the 39% of projects publications have been cited at least once.

Engagement in Open Access (OA), ORCID, OpenAIRE, and other platforms

¹⁸ <https://ideas.repec.org/top/top.person.all.html>

Most of the projects publish significant part of their scientific production in OA either the article per se or the journal. Based on the available information in the final reports, 43% of the published articles are open access. Furthermore, when we refer to articles published in Open Access journals, the percentage of articles lower down to 22%.

SSH researchers are also increasingly engaging in scientific platforms in order to make their research visible as well as their careers and scientific productivity. The FP7 project OpenAIRE aimed to support the EC and ERC Open Access policies' implementation. Its successor OpenAIRE Plus is to facilitate the cross-linking of research publications to associated data and funding schemes, contributing to the Open Linked Data initiatives. Drawing from our own desk research in OpenAIRE and CORDIS, we have identified that the 42,5% out of the 162 projects (SESAM) have uploaded publications in the OpenAIRE repository, and the average of publications per project (out of those who published in OpenAire) is of 6,62. The range goes from 1 article and up to 120 (Project: ACCEPT PLURALISM). Both finished and not finished projects are included in this count.

In our desk research in the ORCID database we retrieved information for all FP7 252 main researchers' participation (N=252). We have observed that 22% of the project coordinators (55 out of the FP7 SSH 252 projects) have already an ORCID ID. The importance given to SSH research is reflected in multiple initiatives. Just to mention one, ORCID appointed 2013 for the first time a researcher in its Board of Directors, and purposefully choose a researcher from SSH. We are very proud to be able to report that Marta Soler from the IMPACT-EV project is the elected representative. Her task is ensure/promote an increase in the participation of SSH researchers in cross-domain, information service platforms such as ORCID.

International Scientific Conference presentations

Based on the IMPACT-EV questionnaire, out of a maximum of 10 international conferences that could be reported by principal investigators, an average of 8,1 conference presentations per project are reported, including invited ones. The number of conference presentations range from 2 to 10. When distinguished between finished and unfinished projects, the average of conference presentations per finished project is of 10 and for the unfinished projects the average is of 7.6, which is expected to be raised by the end of the project. Participation in national conferences is not included.

Projects leading to subsequent research led by consortium members

The majority of the principal investigators who participated in the IMPACT-EV questionnaire report to have generated subsequent research as a result of the project. The average of new research generated is 1,2 new projects per project. Most of the new projects are international. So, we can state that concerning the further strengthening of the ERA, EC funding acts as *seed-money* and triggers new avalanches of research.

3.2. Success Stories

For a large part of the reviewed project scientific impact has already been proven. We present here a selection of projects that have demonstrated to have a high scientific impact. The selection has been based on the most frequent criteria used regarding scientific impact: publications, scientific dissemination (conferences and seminars) and subsequent research. As indicated in the table below, different weights have been allocated leading to an initial preliminary selection of projects.

Publication, dissemination (during the project duration), and subsequent research are used categories. The footnotes to the table detail the construction of the scores for each of them. In the category *Publication* we took classic output indicators into account, such as peer reviewed publications. For the other categories, we also included indicators for which information cannot easily be retrieved from one database, such as *invited lectures*, *organization of workshops*, or *number of follow-up projects*.

Success Stories with scientific impact

ACRONYM	Pillar ¹	Publications (weight 5) ²						Scientific dissemination (weight 3)						Subsequent research (weight 5)						Scientific Impact Value	Scientific Impact Score ⁹				
		Peer-reviewed journal article (weight 20)		Books/chapters (weight 10)		Others (weight 5)		Conferences Invited (weight 20)		Conferences Submitted & Accepted (weight 15)		Seminars Organization (weight 10)		Seminars Attendance (weight 5)		International (weight 20)		European (weight 15)				National (weight 10)		Local (weight 5)	
		N	Score ³	N	Score ⁴	N	Score ⁵	N	Score ⁶	N	Score ⁶	N	Score ⁶	N	Score ⁶	N	Score ⁷	N	Score ⁷	N	Score ⁷	N	Score ⁷		
AIDA	Democratic change	20	7	13	6	43	9	9	2	1	1	0	0	3	1	1	1	--	--	4	2	--	--	1605 ⁸	10
ASPA	Jobs	47	20	5	2	--	--	--	--	29	3	--	--	12	3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2280	10
ASPRO CEE 2007	Fairness	41	17	--	--	--	--	--	--	10	2	5	1	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1835	10
CHANGING BEHAVIOUR	Fairness	9	6	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	1	1	1	1	--	--	850	7
DERREG	Jobs	26	7	7	4	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	900	7
EFIGE	Growth	11	7	--	--	27	6	--	--	14	3	--	--	13	3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1030	8
ELDIA	Fairness	18	5	4	1	4	1	23	3	7	2	9	2	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	920	7
EU-GRASP	Democratic Change	5	2	16	5	102	10	3	1	8	2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	850	7
EUMARGINS	Jobs	11	6	2	2	1	1	--	--	5	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	--	--	820	7
FAMILIES AND SOCIETIES	Democratic Change	12	6	1	1	--	--	9	2	1	1	10	2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	875	7
FINNOV	Growth	9	5	1	2	1	1	--	--	7	2	7	2	3	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	730	6
GEITONIES	Democratic Change	9	3	3	1	--	--	3	1	7	2	6	2	4	1	3	1	--	--	1	1	--	--	725	6
GINI	Fairness	36	16	7	4	--	--	11	3	19	3	3	1	12	3	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	2265	10
GUSTO	Jobs	24	11	8	4	--	--	5	1	1	1	--	--	6	2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1435	9
ICATSEM	Growth	19	9	7	4	1	1	--	--	35	3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1260	9
INCLUD-ED	Jobs	73	20	4	2	--	--	1	1	18	3	--	--	8	2	--	--	--	--	3	1	--	--	2375	10
MELA	Fairness	4	1	37	10	--	--	--	--	60	3	10	2	3	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	810	7
MERCURY	Growth	11	5	13	5	--	--	8	2	21	3	6	2	4	1	--	--	3	1	--	--	--	--	1155	8
MULTILINKS	Democratic Change	20	8	--	--	--	--	--	--	38	3	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	935	7
POLHIA	Growth	23	14	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1475	9

¹ Based on Jean Claude Juncker agenda for Jobs, Growth, Fairness and Democratic change

² Each type of scientific impact has a different weight assigned.

³ A score is assigned according to: a) the number of articles published: for 1-5 articles=1; 6-10=2; 11-15=3; 16-20=4; 21-25=5; 26-30=6; 31-35=7; 36-40=8; 41-45=9; >45=10; b) the sum of all the individual impacts: each article has an individual score depending on the journal quartile of JCR (Q1=1; Q2=0,75; Q3=0,5; Q4=0,25, no JCR quartile =0) plus the cites achieved (for cites in WOS and Scopus, 1 to 5 cites= 0,25; 6 to 10= 0,5; 11 to 20 = 0,75; more than 20 = 1. For cites in Google scholar, 1 to 25 cites = 0,25; 26 to 50 = 0,5; 51 to 100 = 0,75; more than 100 = 1). Final score for Project articles is the sum of a) and b).

⁴ A score is assigned according to: a) the number of books or chapters published: for 1-5 books/chapters=1; 6-10=2; 11-15=3; 16-20=4; 21-25=5; 26-30=6; 31-35=7; 36-40=8; 41-45=9; >45=10; b) the sum of all the individual impacts: each book/chapter has an individual score depending on the publisher prestige based on whether they are indexed in the Book Citation Index - Web of Science (http://wokinfo.com/products_tools/multidisciplinary/bookcitationindex): 1 if it is included, 0 if it is not.

⁵ A score is assigned according to the number of other publications: for 1-5 other publications=1; 6-10=2; 11-15=3; 16-20=4; 21-25=5; 26-30=6; 31-35=7; 36-40=8; 41-45=9; >45=10.

⁶ A score is assigned according to the number of conferences (invited / submitted & accepted) / seminars (organized / attended): 1 to 5 = 1; 6 to 10 = 2; more than 10 = 3.

⁷ A score is assigned according to the number of subsequent projects developed: 1 to 3 = 1; 4 to 5 = 2; more than 5 = 3.

⁸ $5 \times 20 \times 7 + 5 \times 10 \times 6 + 5 \times 5 \times 9 + 3 \times 20 \times 2 + 3 \times 15 \times 1 + 3 \times 5 \times 1 + 5 \times 20 \times 1 + 5 \times 10 \times 2 = 1605$

⁹ 10 (>1500), 9 (1251-1500), 8 (1001-1250), 7 (801-1000), 6 (601-800), 5 (401-600), 4 (301-400), 3 (201-300), 2 (101-200), 1 (0-100)

4. Political impact

4.1. Overview

In this report, political impact is understood as any evidence showing how research findings are taken into account in the political sphere. It entails policy-makers elaborating new policies or reforms (policy impact) based on these findings. But research findings can also have political impact because social movements and non-governmental organizations draw on them to undertake actions as part of their vindications to foster social change.

Political impact as part of projects' objectives

The review of projects shows that SSH funded research is increasingly committed and successful in regards to the political impact. There are projects that have already inform policies in order to better face societal challenges, as it is reflected in the fact that most of the projects have it as one of their main objectives.

Based on our review of the 162 FP7 projects in SESAM, the analysed data show that the 95% of the projects' coordinators state that their **project were aimed at generating outputs** (expertise or scientific advice) **for the policy makers**; the 65% of the total, as a primary objective of the project, and the 30% as a secondary objective. Priority 8 of FP6 called "Scientific Support to Policies – SSP" was specifically dedicated to support policies about three main priority areas: the sustainable management of Europe's natural resources, the improvement of health, security and opportunities enjoyed by EU citizens, and the enhancement of the economic potential and cohesion of an enlarging Europe¹⁹. According to that, most projects had in their initial objectives the aim of influencing policy making.

Additionally, the major part of the projects have elaborated at least 1 **policy briefs and/or 1 policy recommendations** as a summary of a particular project's issue and aimed at government policymakers and others who have influence in formulating or advising policy.

Exchanges with political representatives

Beyond the elaboration of policy briefs and policy recommendations and the projects' objectives expected, many researchers have made relevant efforts to reach out policy makers and other relevant stakeholders. In this sense, it is relevant to mention what has been called "**Productive interactions**" as it is considered to be one of the indicators

¹⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/fp6/ssp/index_en.htm

used to assess research social and political impact. Productive interactions²⁰ are defined as exchanges between researchers and stake holders in which knowledge is produced and valued that is both scientifically robust and socially relevant. In the case of political impact, these interactions are those that take place with policy makers as well as with representatives from different institutions. Based on our qualitative desk research analysis, we found that having this kind of interactions is common among the research community, which potentially leads to political impact. Many projects have had **meetings with representatives from the European Commission and European Parliament, and/or with other European/International political representatives**, such as the Council of Europe, the European External Action Service (EEAS), the United Nations or the OECD, among others. Among many other examples, the researchers of the “*MERCURY*” Project discussed their findings with President of the European Commission José Manuel Barroso.²¹ Moreover, a relevant number of projects have organized or participated in forums with relevant policymakers.

Policies and programmes developed as a result of the projects

Despite the difficulties to establish a direct link between research projects and specific policies, our assessment has allowed us to identify several examples of **projects which results influenced policies developed by governmental and supranational institutions, and also** have been the base for the **development of strategic plans and/or programmes by organizations using the results of these projects**. Many local, regional, national or European and/or International organizations and Institutions have elaborated their plans and/or programmes taking into account the projects' outcomes.

4.2. Success stories

According to the state of the art on political impact and the analysis of the projects, the research team has identified projects achieving political impact based on a set of criteria and weights assigned to them.

1. **Policies:** transfer of research outcomes into policies adopted by governments and supranational institutions. Political impact is considered to occur if there are evidences of a relationship between the research project and policies.
In the case of Policies at the European level, they include Regulations, Directives, Decisions, Recommendations, Resolutions, Opinions and Conclusions adopted by the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union or the European Commission. Resolutions, declarations, treaties, protocols, global plans of actions, conventions, agreements, conferences and

²⁰ Spaapen, J. & van Drooge, L. (2011). Introducing “productive interactions” in social impact assessment *Research Evaluation*, 20(3), 211-218. (p.212)

²¹ MERCURY Report Summary. http://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/57691_en.html

summits, consultative opinions, etc. adopted or promoted by the United Nations, as well as agreements, guidelines, recommendations and declarations adopted by OECD are also included in this category.

2. **Programmes** implemented by civil society organizations (NGOs, companies, unions, trusts, professional bodies and other stakeholders) that have used the findings of the research. Political impact is considered if there are evidences of the relationship between the research project and the policy.
3. **Political forums** in which the findings of research have been presented and discussed with policy makers and/or other relevant stakeholders.

For each type of impact, the weight varies according to the scope of the impact and number of impacts. The following table show the weights assigned to each project. The application of these weights allows quantifying the political impact of a project. The projects identified as having a highest political impact are shown in the next table.

Success Stories with Political Impact

ACRONYM	Pillar ¹	Policies (weight 5) ^{2,3}								Programmes (weight 3) ⁴								Forums (weight 1) ⁵								Political Impact Value	Political Impact Score ¹⁰
		Int / European (weight 20) ^{6,7}		National (weight 15)		Regional (weight 10)		Local (weight 5)		Int / European (weight 20)		National (weight 15)		Regional (weight 10)		Local (weight 5)		Int / European (weight 20)		National (weight 15)		Regional (weight 10)		Local (weight 5)			
		N	Score ⁸	N	Score	N	S	N	Score	N	Score	N	Score	N	Score	N	Score	N	Score	N	Score	N	Score	N	Score		
ASSPRO CEE	Fairness	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4	2	--	--	3	1	--	--	50	5
CAP-IRE	Growth	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	9
COINVEST	Jobs	1	1	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	2	1	--	--	--	--	210	10
DISCIT	Democratic change	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	7	3	--	--	--	--	145	9
DOMAC	Fairness	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	10	3	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	9
ENACT	Democratic Change	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	3	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	7
EURO-JUSTIS	Fairness	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	2	1	7	3	--	--	--	--	150	9
FINNOV	Growth	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	95	8
IMPROVE	Democratic change	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4	2	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	4
INCLUD-ED	Jobs	1	1	--	--	1	1	--	--	1	1	--	--	1	1	--	--	5	2	2	1	--	--	--	--	295	10
MERCURY	Growth	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	4	2	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	8
MIRRIS	Growth	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	--	--	16	3	--	--	50	5
MONFISPOL	Growth	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	105	9
NOPOOR	Fairness	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5	2	--	--	2	1	3	1	55	6
PIDOP	Democratic Change	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	9
POLINARES	Democratic change	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	--	--	1	1	--	--	130	9
PRIV-WAR	Fairness	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2	1	3	1	--	--	--	--	135	9

SUSTAINCITY	Growth	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	95	8	
VICO	Jobs	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2	1	--	--	--	--	--	95	8	
WIOD	Jobs	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5	2	1	1	--	--	215	10

¹ Based on Jean Claude Juncker agenda for Jobs, Growth, Fairness and Democratic change

² Each type of impact has a different weigh assigned.

³ Policies adopted by governments and supranational institutions. Political impact is considered if there are evidences of the relationship between the research project and the policy.

⁴ Programmes implemented by civil society organizations (NGOs, companies, unions, trusts, professional bodies and other stakeholders) that have used the findings of the research. Political impact is considered if there are evidences of the relationship between the research project and the policy.

⁵ Political forums (with policy makers) in which the findings of the research have been presented.

⁶ Policies at the European level include Regulations, Directives, Decisions, Recommendations, Resolutions, Opinions, Conclusions and Recommendations adopted by the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union or the European Commission. Also are included in this category resolutions, declarations, treaties, protocols, global plans of actions, conventions, agreements, conferences and summits, consultative opinions, etc. adopted or promoted by the United Nations, as well as agreements, guidelines, recommendations and declarations adopted by OECD.

⁷ For each type of impact, the weight varies according to the scope of the impact.

⁸ Score is assigned according to intervals of the number of policies / programmes / forums: 1 to 3 = 1; 4 to 5 = 2; more than 5 = 3

⁹ $5 \times 20 \times 1 + 1 \times 20 \times 1 = 120$

¹⁰ 10 (>200), 9 (101-200), 8 (81-100), 7 (61-80), 6 (51-60), 5 (41-50), 4 (31-40), 3 (21-30), 2 (11-20), 1 (0-10)

The main impacts of these projects are briefly explained as follows.

- The results of CAP-IRE project have been used in evaluations that have been developed as a basis to the post 2013 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)²², clearly influencing on the development of this policy framework.
- The data and methods of the COINVEST project have been integrated in the Innovation Strategy “Getting a Head Start on Tomorrow” of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)²³ Besides, the COINVEST policy recommendations to the UK Government about investment in intangible assets have influenced the UK knowledge investment growing²⁴.
- The project DISCIT took part in the European Commission’s Work Forum on the implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in April, 2015.
- The interaction between some team members of the DOMAC project and stakeholders and policy makers from World Health Organization (WHO), have been crucial to achieve the outputs of the project and also to influence the final document of the Kampala Declaration²⁵.
- The ENACT project’s main researcher was invited onto the working group for the European Year Citizenship Alliance (EYCA) to draft a manifesto to be presented to the European Commission in 2013, enshrining the principles of an ‘active European citizenship.
- The results of EURO-JUSTIS project have been included by the UK Ministry of Justice and the National Audit Office (NAO) in their Briefing for the House of Commons Justice Committee.²⁶ The project results of EURO-JUSTIS have contributed also to the elaboration of a module (set of questions) to the fifth

²² European Commission. (2013). *The Common Agricultural Policy after 2013*. Accessed October 28, 2014. <http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/cap-post-2013/>

²³ OECD. (2010). *The OECD Innovation Strategy: Getting a Head Start on Tomorrow*. Accessed October 28, 2014.

<http://www.oecd.org/sti/theoecdinnovationstrategygettingaheadstartontomorrow.htm>

²⁴ UK Government. (2015). *UK knowledge investment continues to grow*. London: GOV.UK. Accessed March 20, 2015. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-knowledge-investment-continues-to-grow> ; Intellectual Property Office

²⁵ World Health Organization. WHO. (2008). *The Kampala declaration and agenda for global action*. Geneva: WHO Press. Accessed March 14, 2015.

<http://www.who.int/workforcealliance/Kampala%20Declaration%20and%20Agenda%20web%20file.%20FINAL.pdf?ua=1>; DOMAC Final Report. <http://www.domac.is/media/domac-skjol/DOMAC-18-Uganda.pdf>. Coalition for the International Criminal Court (ICC), (2010). *Report on the first REVIEW CONFERENCE ON THE ROME STATUTE 31 May-11 June 2010 Kampala, Uganda*. New York, ICC. Accessed January 18, 2015. http://www.iccnw.org/documents/RC_Report_finalweb.pdf

²⁶ UK Ministry of Justice. (2012). *Comparing International Criminal Justice Systems*. London: National Audit Office. Accessed January 22, 2015.

http://www.nao.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2012/03/NAO_Briefing_Comparing_International_Criminal_Justice.pdf

European Social Survey (ESS) which has been replicated by an EU/UNDP project²⁷.

- The results of FINNOV project have been taken into account to elaborate the UK *Innovation and Research Strategy for Growth*²⁸.
- INCLUD-ED results have served as the basis to different political developments at the EU level (European Commission, Council of the EU, European Parliament), state, regional and local level (i.e. Albacete, Rivas-vaciaMadrid). The project findings' and more specifically, the identified successful educational actions have also been transferred into eight countries of Latin-America by the NATURA institute, the social responsibility branch of the Brazil based company.
- A direct outgrowth of the MERCURY project was the Marie Curie initial training network on EU external action – EXACT.
- MONFISPOL developed DYNARE that is a software platform for handling a wide class of economic models, in particular dynamic stochastic general equilibrium (DSGE) and overlapping generations (OLG) models. Various public bodies (central banks, ministries of economy and finance, international organisations) and some private financial institutions use DYNARE for performing policy analysis exercises and as a support tool for forecasting exercises. It has strong political impact in banks²⁹.
- The PIDOP project influenced the Secretary General's action plan for combatting extremism and radicalisation leading to terrorism
- The POLINARES³⁰ project has served as the basis for the development of the Commission's impact assessment document for a Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council;³¹
- Some of the project recommendations of PRIV-WAR have been included in the European Resolution about the development of the common security and defence policy following the entry into force of the Lisbon Treaty³².

²⁷ Research Excellence Framework. (2014). *Impact Case Study (REF 3b)*. London: REF. accessed March 18, 2015. <http://results.ref.ac.uk/DownloadFile/ImpactCaseStudy/pdf?caseStudyId=17684>; C. Maier (EURO-JUSTIS Project EC Officer), personal communication, December 18, 2014.

²⁸ Department of Business Innovation and Skills of UK. (2011). *Innovation and Research Strategy for Growth*. Accessed March 14, 2015. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/innovation-and-research-strategy-for-growth>

²⁹ DYNARE. (2014). *Dynare Summer School 2011*. Fishers: PLone Foundation. Accessed March 18, 2015. <http://www.dynare.org/events/dynare-summer-school-2011>

³⁰ POLINARES, POLicy for NATural RESouces (CP-FP). <http://www.polinares.eu>

³¹ European Commission. (2014). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council setting up a Union system for supply chain due diligence self-certification of responsible importers of tin, tantalum and tungsten, their ores, and gold originating in conflict affected and high-risk areas SWD(2014) 53 final*. Brussels: European Commission. Accessed January 17, 2015. http://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/docs/2014/march/tradoc_152227.pdf.

- The SUSTAINCITY increased the interest in land use-transport mode modelling in Switzerland and demonstrated the substantial data management involved. In response, the federal government funded a much simpler model called FALC, which is used for modeling land use transport interactions.
- The VICO project results influenced a change in Finish policy towards venture capital. Instead of channelling governmental funds through government owned and management venture capital companies, the Finish government now does it through privately management venture companies, which was proved by the project to be more efficient.
- The WIOD project results were the base of a policy brief of the International Monetary Fund. Furthermore, the project influenced the EC Staff Working Document SWD(2012)299, which accompanied the communication from the Commission titled “A stronger European Industry for Growth and Economic Recovery Industrial Policy Communication Update COM(2012)582”.

Other evidence of the political impact achieved is the **presentation of the projects' results in political forums**. There is an intensive work from the projects in order to disseminate their results among policy-makers, stakeholders and/or among other professionals related with politic issues. In this sense, several activities are developed to enhance the contact with this type of audience. Among these political forums, the main ones are: **meetings with representatives from the European Commission and European Parliament, and/or with other European/International political representatives**, such as the Council of Europe, the European External Action Service (EEAS), the United Nations or the OECD (for instance, ASSPRO reported to have taken part in 4 International or European forums and IMPROVE in 5); **meetings with National Political Delegations, Agencies or Ministries; European or/and International Workshops and Seminars** organized in collaboration with political representatives (for instance, MIRRIS reported to have taken part in 16 regional forums of this kind); and **European /International Conferences** also organized in collaboration with political representatives and mainly addressed to stakeholders, policy makers and/or other professionals related with politic issues. One clear example of this kind of political impact is the NOPOOR project, which took part in 5 international forums. One of those forums was organized in Senegal and it was attended by high-ranking Senegalese politicians, including representatives of the Minister in charge of the General Delegation of Social Protection in Senegal, a number of international donor representatives and representatives of the World Bank, UNESCO, UNICEF, OXFAM, and ENDA/CACID.

³² European Parliament. (2011). *REPORT on the development of the common security and defence policy following the entry into force of the Lisbon Treaty (2010/2299(INI))*. Brussels: European Parliament. Accessed March 16, 2015. <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?pubRef=-//EP//NONSGML+REPORT+A7-2011-0166+0+DOC+PDF+V0//EN>

5. Social impact

5.1. Overview

Scientific community and funding agencies have been increasingly aware about the importance of evaluating and measuring the social impact of research. The recent nature of this increased interest is shown in debates about procedures, tools and indicators most suitable for social impact assessment.

The IMPACT-EV approach considers social impact of research when the published and disseminated research results, which have been transferred, lead to an improvement in relation to the goals agreed in our societies.³³ In the case of European research, the EU Lisbon 2010, EU2020 Strategy (i.e. employment, R+D investment, climate change/energy, poverty/social exclusion and education) and the recently launched EC Agenda for Jobs, Growth, Fairness and Democratic Change serve as a framework of those common social targets or objectives. A high number of projects have reported in the questionnaire to contribute to these diverse goals. Of course, it should be noted that because of a project is designed to tackle one of these areas, it cannot be inferred that it has achieved social impact.

Importantly, social impact should not be confused with disseminating results, that is when research findings are also made known, both to the scientific community, as well as to policy-makers, stakeholders and citizens in general (i.e. press, social media, networks, etc).³⁴ Thus, social impact is not the same than knowledge transfer: when the published and disseminated results are taken up by policymakers and/or social actors as the basis for their policies and/or actions regardless of whether they have made social improvements or not. Here taking into consideration these distinctions, we only consider social impact when sufficient evidences show that such social improvements (in reference to the political goals stated above) have taken place. These conceptual clarifications are important as research informing policy making does not necessarily involve a positive effect in the lives of the citizens and the societal challenges. That impact is more likely to occur when the research informing policies has already demonstrated evidences of improvements at a micro level. On the other hand, some researches may produce relevant social impacts with a further potential political impact.

³³ IMPACT-EV Consortium (2014). *State of the art in the scientific, policy and social impact of SSH research and its evaluation, Report 1*. FP7 2014-2017.

³⁴ Flecha, Ramon. "Buenas prácticas: Cómo lograr impacto en los proyectos del Reto 6." [Good practices: How achieve impact with the projects of the Challenge 6]. In H2020: Informative session about Challenge 6, ed. FECYT and European Commission. Bilbao: Universidad de Deusto (24 January 2014).

Due to the novelty of **social impact assessment, indicators and measurement are quite difficult** and, even among those researchers achieving this kind of impact, to have evidences and records of these impacts is very uncommon. With our follow up calls and interviews to researchers we have helped several projects to identify and specify some of the benefits that can be attributed to the results and the process of their projects. In this sense, it is relevant to highlight that when researchers are asked for the social impact of their research, they gain awareness on the importance of collecting such evidence, and we found that most of them are open to try to identify the social impacts they achieved and to get them evaluated. We found an overall collaborative climate. One evidence of this, is the fact that during to our telephone campain with main researchers, we encountered some cases in which the PI would take additional efforts. As we got to know main researchers, even thought their projects had been over, contacted again their partners to collect all information possible to justify their social impact. For many, this was the first time they thought about their work from this perspective. As a result of the collaboration with the IMPACT-EV team they are now seeking for new venues to explore whether their research has had social impact or not. The evaluation of the social impact of research seems to contribute to a change in researchers' mind, in terms of engaging them more explicitly with the aim of improvement of society. In this respect, one could say that the research strategy of IMPACT-EV acted as an intervention in the SSH field, and triggered more awareness for social and other impact already.

Another difficulty is to relate the benefits resulting from a specific project with direct contributions to these targets. Many impacts of the research projects can not directly be tagged as social impact (i.e. increasing employment in a specific group) and cannot be expressed in terms of the correspondent impact indicator (i.e. percentage of people who have found a job because of the research). However, they can be social achievements that are related to these EU2020 indicators, and can be expressed as Social Impact Indicators.

Moreover, social impact requires the longest time to be achieved than scientific or political one. Because a considerable amount of projects are still in process, it is more difficult to report impact from their ongoing or fairly recent research results; in addition social impact can have an implicit and indirect nature which makes it difficult to have a record of it. In this sense, we should acknowledge different researchers who had self-reported expected social impact linked to their project's further development. For example, the FP5 Project WORKALO³⁵ (2001-2004) got their results approved by the EU Parliament in 2005 and this led to strategic plans for the Roma at member state level (for instance the Catalan government Integrative Plan or the Spanish National Roma Council) which promoted employment in deprived Roma communities years later³⁶.

³⁵ WORKALÓ project. Funded under EU FP5-Human Potential, Fifth Framework Programme ([FP5/1998-2002] [FP7/2001-2004]) under reference HPSE-CT-2001-00101.

³⁶ ROM-UP Project, Newsletter VI. Available at: http://cloud2.snappages.com/c13113aadcc6acbc7b237bdac53d0398570c62aa/ROM-UP_Newsletter%206_EN%20PDF.pdf

The WORKALO results have also served to inform a Romani women employment initiative launched by the Roma association *Drom Kotar Mestipen*. This association has directed vocational training courses as school canteen monitors (eight editions) that have led to a success rate of 85%³⁷ among all those Roma women who have taken the course.³⁸ This initiative has been also replicated in different contexts (e.g. Albacete).

Taking into account these difficulties, in our review we have identified examples of projects which have succeeded in achieving social impact and show how SSH research funded under EC contribution can make real improvements in different contexts and levels.

5.2. Success stories

In what follows, a table summarizing success stories is enclosed. The ranking has been based on all the evidences that we have been able to gather through a wide range of data collection strategies (as detailed in the methodology section), mainly, website search, available reports, phone and Skype interviews with PIs, EC officers interviews, among many others. The criteria and weights assigned for the social impact of SSH projects are related to the evidences of social improvements in relation to EU2020 targets, the objectives of the Lisbon strategy or other social targets and the other criteria specified in the table. For each project, all the possible impacts achieved are accounted for. At the end, the final **Social Impact Score** of a given project will be the highest score among all its impacts. In Appendix 5, a more detailed account of the impacts achieved for each success story is provided.

Article published on the Virtual Museum of the Roma People website: <http://www.museuvirtualgitano.cat/ca/component/content/article/9-actualitat/90-cami-de-la-universitat.html>

³⁷ Sordé-Martí, T., Munté, A., Contreras, A., & Prieto-Flores, O. (2012). Immigrant and Native Romani Women in Spain: Building Alliances and Developing Shared Strategies *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 38(8), 1233-1249. doi: 10.1080/1369183X.2012.689179.

³⁸ Idem.

Success Stories with Social Impact

ACRONYM	Pillar ¹	Social Impact ²	Responds to at least one EU2020 target or Lisbon strategy objective		% of improvement achieved ³	Evidences of transferability ⁴	Sources of evidences ⁵	Sustainability ⁶	Score – impact ⁷	Social Impact Score ⁸
AIDA	Democratic Change	1	Yes	Education	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	4
ALAC's	Fairness	1	Other societal objectives	EU's Justice and Home Affairs Agenda 2020	Not available	Yes	Other sources	Yes	3	7
		2	Yes	Employment	Not available	Yes	Other sources	Yes	7	
ASPA	Jobs	1	Yes	Employment	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	4
CSEYHP	Fairness	1	Yes	Poverty	Not available	Yes	Other sources	No	5	5
DESAFIO	Growth	1	Yes	Poverty	Not available	Yes	Other sources	No	5	5
DIASPEACE	Democratic change	1	Yes	Poverty	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	4
EURESCL	Fairness	1	Yes	Poverty	Not available	No	Other sources	Yes	5	5
INCLUD-ED	Jobs	1	Yes	Education	98%	Yes	Scientific journals	Yes	10	10
		2	Yes	Employment	39%	Yes	Scientific journals	Yes	10	
LOCALISE	Jobs	1	Yes	Employment	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	4
MAXCAP	Democratic change	1	Other societal objectives	EU enlargement	Not available	No	Other sources	No	2	2
MEDPRO	Growth	1	Yes	R&D	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	4
MEMOLA	Growth	1	Yes	Employment	Not available	Yes	Other sources	No	5	5
		2	Yes	Employment	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	
MIGROM	Fairness	1	Yes	Employment	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	4
		2	Yes	Education, Poverty	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	
MYPLACE	Jobs	1	Yes	Poverty/social exclusion	Not available	No	Other sources	Yes	4	5
POINT	Growth	1	Yes	Climate change	Not available	Yes	Scientific journals	No	6	6
RESPECT	Democratic change	1	Other societal objectives	Increased cultural tolerance, respect and sensitivity with regards to minority groups	Not available	Yes	Other sources	No	1	2

SAMPLE	Democratic change	1	Yes	Poverty	Not available	No	Other sources	Yes	5	5
SUSTAINCITY	Growth	1	Yes	Climate change	Not available	Yes	Scientific journals	No	6	6
TAP	Jobs	1	Yes	Employment	Not available	Yes	Scientific journals	Not available	6	6
TENLAW	Fairness	1	Yes	Poverty	Not available	No	Other sources	No	4	4

¹ Based on Jean Claude Juncker agenda for Jobs, Growth, Fairness and Democratic change.

² Each social impact corresponds to a specific societal improvement.

³ Percentage of improvement achieved in relation to the starting situation. For instance, in the case of employment targets, it is the percentage of people who has showed certain improvement as the result of the actions developed based on the project's findings.

⁴ At least implemented in 2 different contexts (Yes/No).

⁵ Publication on scientific journals (with a recognized impact), other sources (from governmental or non-governmental official bodies).

⁶ Evidences of the impact after the end of the project life span (Yes/No).

⁷ The Score of each impact is assigned according to the criteria that it fulfils:

10: The impact meets all the criteria, and has more than 30% of improvement

9: The impact meets all the criteria, and has more than 20% of improvement

8: The impact meets all the criteria, and has more than 10% of improvement

7: The impact meets all the criteria, and has some % of improvement (not available the specific %)

6: The impact responds to EU2020/Lisbon strategy objectives, has achieved some % of improvement and meets at least 2 of the other criteria

5: The impact responds to EU2020/Lisbon strategy objectives, has achieved some % of improvement and meets at least 1 of the other criteria

4: The impact responds to EU2020/Lisbon strategy objectives and has achieved some % of improvement

3: The impact responds to other societal objectives, has achieved some % of improvement and meets at least 2 of the other criteria

2: The impact responds to other societal objectives, has achieved some % of improvement and meets at least 1 of the other criteria

1: The impact responds to other societal objectives and has achieved some % of improvement

⁸ The final Social Impact Score of a given project will be the highest score obtained.

6. Impact on strengthening ERA

6.1. Overview

In our review, we have identified different ways in which SSH research is contributing to strengthening ERA. The “2012 European Commission ERA Communication: a Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth”³⁹ establishes five ERA priorities, namely: 1) improving effectiveness of national research systems, 2) enhancing an optimal transnational co-operation and competition, 3) fostering an open labour market for researchers, 4) ensuring gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research 5) and optimizing the circulation, access to and transfer of scientific knowledge including via digital ERA. The report on the “Evaluation of the impact of the Framework Programme on the formation of the ERA in Social Sciences and the Humanities”⁴⁰ already showed how the FP6 has greatly contributed to strengthening ERA compared to previous programmes. It is also highlighted that larger instruments tend to be beneficial for structuring effects. Our analysis confirms the strong capacity of large projects to promote supranational and interdisciplinary teams able to tackle crucial societal challenges. In SSH funded projects under FP6 and FP7, the average of partners range from 9 (in the case of small and medium projects) to 20.

Funding scheme	Average number participants
FP6 Integrative Projects	18
FP6 STREPS – PRIORITY 7 AND 8	9
FP6 Network of Excellence	20
FP7 CP-FP	9
FP7 CP-IP	19
FP7 CP-FP-SICA	11
FP7 CP-IP-SICA	19
FP7 CP-SICA	11
FP7 BSG-CSO	15

Synergies promoting ERA

Beyond the cooperation within the consortium, research projects have developed strong synergies and collaborations with others. Actually, 46% of the projects that reported

³⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/euraxess/pdf/research_policies/era-communication_en.pdf

⁴⁰ European Commission (2010). Evaluation of the impact of the Framework Programme on the formation of the ERA in Social Sciences and the Humanities (SSH). Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/social-sciences/pdf/evaluation-fp-ssh_en.pdf

achieving impact on ERA have collaborated with other FP projects, with an average of 2.9 projects (collaborations) per project. The range of values goes from collaboration with 1 project to a maximum of 6 projects (i.e. INSPIRES project). Furthermore, 20.8% of the projects collaborated with non-FP projects, with an average of 2.5 projects (collaborations) per project. For instance, the MERCURY project collaborated with EU-GRASP, EU4SEAS and SCOOP; the EUMARGINS project collaborated with CSEYHP, EDUMIGROM, YIPPEE, YUONEX and INCLUD-ED; and the LOCALISE project collaborated with IMPROVE, INSPIRES, COPE, FLOWS and WILCO. Another example was the collaboration between INNODRIVE and COINVEST to promote the INTAN-Invest initiative, which consisted in a cross-country intangible investment data website useful to develop new resources of analysis of growth and to identify the importance of intangible capital for public policies. Again, the range of values goes from collaboration with 1 project to a maximum of 6 projects (i.e. FINESS project). The collected information via interviews and reports confirm these collaborations and point out the results of this common work.

A lower number of projects (9 of 30 reporting having impact on ERA) declare to have also collaborated with non-FP projects, with a range from 1 to 14 collaborations (for example, the SAWS project collaborated with the Alpheios, Ars Edendi and Comparative Oriental Manuscripts projects; and the MIRRIS project collaborated with the JRC Stairway to Excellence project), and some others to have had collaborations with other research organizations, in most cases from different countries or at European level and in particular cases with a high number of organizations (more than 20).

Regarding the collaboration with research organizations, 12.5% of these projects mentioned this type of collaboration. Some examples highlight, for instance, the HI-POD project which collaborated with a relevant research infrastructure: DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities). Other examples are the TAP project (HERA), which collaborated with the Ludwig Boltzmann Institute (LBI) for Archaeological Prospection and Virtual Archaeology (Austria), the Leverhulme-funded UK Landscapes of Governance team at UCL London and the Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historic Monuments of Scotland (RCAHM); the NOPOOR project (FP7 SSH), which collaborated with the UNESCO Most Programme; and the MIRRIS project (CSA), which collaborated with the COST Action BESTPRAC. In general, collaborations among research projects and organizations include a number of different initiatives: joint conferences, being part of the advisory board, co-writing a policy brief, cross-invitation at project seminars, workshops and conferences, joint meetings, presentations, dissemination of findings among networks, interviews with researchers, exchange and comparison of results.

There are also examples of projects collaborating and promoting European research infrastructures. For instance, the project SAWS (Sharing Ancient Wisdoms: Exploring the tradition of Greek and Arabic wisdom literatures) collaborated and kept constant communication with the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH). This collaboration is contributing to optimize the circulation, access to and transfer of scientific knowledge including via digital ERA. HI-POD (Historical patterns of development and underdevelopment: origins and persistence of the great divergence) collaborated with the Globalizing Europe Economic History Network (GLOBALEURONET), supported by the European science Foundation.

Dissemination at the European scale

The particular case of FP7 cooperation projects allowed reaching a **relevant EU scale dissemination of the results**. The analysis of project reports reveals that in most of the cases dissemination is done both in each of the participant countries and in a European scale through conferences, workshops, web tools among others. The Coordination and Support Actions have played a complementary role for disseminating internationally the outcomes of several projects.

Researchers Mobility

Based on the IMPACT-EV questionnaire responses, in relation to mobility of researchers, among the projects that reported impact on the ERA 33% specified they promoted mobility opportunities for the researchers in their teams. The answer varies significantly across projects, from 5% of the researchers having mobility opportunities to 100%. Besides, 37.5% of the projects reported that the participation in the project has led to career advancement for staff of their team. The MERCURY project main aim was to examine the European Union's contribution to multilateralism. One of the main outcomes of the project was the creation of the Marie Curie initial training network on EU External Action – EXACT, as a direct result of MERCURY. In relation to these date, it must be taken into account that some of the FP7 projects have not finished yet and still will have opportunities for enhancing ERA in the course and as a result of their research.

New employment opportunities

In relation to new employment opportunities generated by FP7 projects, we should highlight that, according to the workforce statistics gathered in the reports of a sample of 119 projects, 927 out of 6023 researchers were PhD students. That is to say those, around 15% of the total researchers in FP7 SSH Cooperation projects were junior researchers. Projecting to the total FP7 SSH projects (n=252), it would be an estimation of 1963 PhD students hired throughout the FP7.

Graph 1. Junior researchers involved in FP7 SSH Projects (%)

Source: Own elaboration with data from E-CORDA

Additionally to the official available data, we have asked to several scientific coordinators about the employment created in their own projects, profiles of the employed researchers and promotion of scientific careers beyond the project lifespan. From this qualitative data, some insights can be highlighted. First, most part of the junior researchers hired were aged between 25 and 35 years than under 25. Although the majority of researchers are PhD students, there are also master students, post-doc students and associate researchers, even undergraduate students took part in some projects. Second, many researchers recognized that these junior researchers were hired after the project completion and in around a half of them were promoted to better academic positions. Some of these jobs were related to new projects resulting from the previous ones.

Regarding to gender, scientific coordinators (57%), work packages leaders (61%) and experienced researcher (56%) are men, overrating the number of women in this position. The figures are turned around in the case of additional or other researchers that participate in the projects, as there are more women than men, as in the case of PhD students, who were 57% of women.

Graph 2. Gender distribution of the total researchers involved in FP7 SSH Projects per category (%)

Source: Own elaboration with data from E-CORDA

6.2. Success stories

In this section, we highlight the projects that we have been able to identify with more impact on strengthening the ERA according to mainly the answers in the questionnaire and further information provided by the researchers. Calculations have been made according to two main criteria: the quantity, extent and diversity of collaborations established as a follow up of the given project, and the employment and promotion of research careers. The weights assigned for the impact of SSH projects on strengthening the ERA are related to three criteria: a) Collaborations developed by the project; b) Employment generated by the project, and c) Researchers' career advancement.

Success Stories with Impact on strengthening ERA

ACRONY M	Pillar	Collaborations (weight 3) ¹										Employment (weight 3)				Career Advancement (weight 5)				ERA Impact Value	ERA Impact Score ⁷
		FP projects (weight 20)		Other Projects (weight 15)		Eu/Int Org (weight 15)		Nat Org (weight 10)		Eu Infr (weight 5)		Researchers employed (weight 10)		Junior researchers (weight 5)		% Mobility (Weight 5)		% Position promotion (weight 10) ⁴			
		Num	Score ²	Num	Score	Num	Score	N	Score	N	Score	N	Score ³	N	Score	%	Score ⁵	%	Score		
BLUE-ETS	Jobs	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	25	2	--	--	--	--	75 ⁶	6
CIT-PART	Democratic change	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	8	1	--	--	--	--	75	6
COINVEST	Jobs	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	3	1	--	--	--	--	75	6
e-FRAME	Democratic change	1	1	--	--	1	1	1	1	--	--	10	1	--	--	--	--	4,17	1	165	8
EUMARGINS	Jobs	5	2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	5	1	--	--	--	--	58	3	300	9
EURASIA-NET	Democratic change	2	1	1	1	3	1	--	--	--	--	13	2	10	1	10	3	--	--	300	9
FIDUCIA	Fairness	2	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	10	1	10	1	--	--	--	--	105	8
FINESS	Growth	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	15	2	13	2	--	--	--	--	90	7
FLOWS	Jobs	3	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	28	2	--	--	--	--	90	7
IMPROVE	Democratic change	5	2	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	165	8
INSPIRES	Jobs	7	2	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	10	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	195	8
LOCALISE	Jobs	5	2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	46	2	--	--	7	1	--	--	205	9

MeLa	Fairness	5	2	3	1	--	-	--	--	--	--	36	2	17	2	15	1	30	2	380	10
MERCURY	Fairness	53	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	60	5
MIRRIS	Growth	1	1	1	1	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	8
NOPOOR	Fairness	2	1	--	--	1	1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	105	8
POLHIA	Growth	5	2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	14	2	1	1	--	--	1,92	1	245	9
SAWS	Jobs	--	--	16	3	--	--	--	--	1	1	17	2	--	--	60	3	14,29	1	335	10
SYRTO	Growth	2	1	--	--	1	1	--	--	2	1	35	2	6	1	--	--	--	--	195	8
TAP	Growth	--	--	4	2	9	2	--	--	--	--	11	2	3	1	--	..	75	3	405	10

¹ Each type of impact has a different weigh assigned.

² This score is assigned according to intervals of the number of collaborations: 1 to 3 =1; 4 to 10= 2; more than 10 = 3.

³ This score is assigned according to intervals of the number of senior or junior researchers employed: 1 to 10 =1; 11 to 50 = 2; more than 50 =3.

⁴ Percentage of researchers promoted in relation to the size of the consortium.

⁵ This score is assigned according to intervals of the percentage of mobility among researchers and the percentage of position promotion: 1 to 25% = 1; 26 to 50% = 2; more than 50% = 3.

⁶ Example: $3 \times 15 \times 1 + 3 \times 5 \times 2 = 75$

⁷ This score is assigned according to intervals of the ERA Impact Value: 10 (>300), 9 (201-300), 8 (101-200), 7 (81-100), 6 (61-80) , 5 (41-60), 4 (31-40), 3 (21-30), 2 (11-20), 1 (0-10)

7. Conclusions

The present report contributes with new insights to the existing debate on the SSH legitimacy by showing in which ways SSH research leads to social improvements. Against what is often believed, IMPACT-EV project has identified European funded projects which results have been used to inform policies or actions that have in turn contributed to achieve the politically established societal goals (i.e. Lisbon strategy, EU2020 targets, Agenda for Jobs, Growth, Fairness and Democratic Change). Besides, plenty of particular examples of how the EC funded projects have had scientific, political and social impact, a ranked list of the projects in each of these types of impacts is provided here. To this endeavour, SIOR (the Social Impact Open Repository) makes visible in which ways research from all disciplines is also achieving social impact.

We have observed that FP7 projects are achieving significant scientific impact in different ways and they show a positive progress in this regard. For instance, the average of JCR publications per researcher is 3,71. This figure should be considered in the light that the calculations have included young researchers with no publications. However, there is still some space for improvement an ex-ante evaluation could be improved in order to better select the groups, as it is noticed in the publication records (articles in JCR journals) that there are groups without this scientific impact.

Among the reviewed projects, we observe that there is a significant achievement of political impact. There are projects which findings have served as the basis for policy-makers or civil society to develop actions, programs and interventions; thus, generating what has been defined as political impact. Policy briefs and policy recommendations are the most common way to connect scientific findings with political recommendations, however, an increasing diversification of strategies have been unfolded among FP7 project to pursue greater political impact. Based on our analysis, it can be concluded that there is still space for greater improvements. While examples of projects that have directly informed EU legislation and policy, as well as OECD, national, regional and local one have been reported here, there are others who are not achieving political impact. This might be due to the fact that these latter could achieve so later on, as they are still ongoing or have just been finished.

A growing concern about SSH research social impact has been recently raised, being a crucial and ongoing debate within the scientific community. Our analysis here captures this current debate, and in most part of the analysed projects, researchers widely recognize the importance of social impact, and even those who until now had never thought about this issue they are now starting to consider so. There are projects which has a significant social impact. However, there are many other projects which do not have social impact or which researchers do not know whether they have it or not. In some cases, the IMPACT-EV questionnaire has opened up the opportunity for these researchers to consider and rethink their own work from the social impact perspective, and with many of whom we have collaborated with in order to analyse their research social impact. Other main researchers, even in cases where the projects have already finished more than two years ago, are contacting with their consortium

in order to explore whether their project has generated social impact or not. In general, it is necessary to remark the positive response received by the scientific community when assessing SSH research social impact. Again, a difficulty also faced for evaluating the social impact is that it takes longer to occur, posing additional barriers for ex-post evaluation to fully capture it. This is the case of the present evaluation in which an important amount of projects are still ongoing or recently finished, and it might be too soon to identify social impact achieved.

Some FP7 SSH projects have also contributed to the achievement of the European Research Area (ERA). It is important to highlight that FP7 has made possible for all EU member states to participate. FP7 SSH projects have succeeded in involving excellent researchers in their consortiums. Not only in terms of the scientific productivity average but also because of the multiple awards (i.e. Nobel Prize). Participation is showed to be more even from the gender perspective. A slight increase in the female participation is reported in comparison to previous programmes. It is also important to note that sexual orientation starts to be considered, especially among those projects focused on interrelated areas. Additionally, the present report also sheds light to the impact of EC funded projects in creating employment in general, and more specifically among junior researchers. In terms of ages, most part of them are aged between 25 and 35. Evidences are also showed in which ways funded projects derivate to further research proposals that tend to generate employment opportunities for these priory hired researchers, involving an upgrading of these junior researchers careers.

Besides, identifying the different impacts, an important aspect to highlight is the transformation that is taking place within the scientific community. Particularly, in the process of data collection, we have identified many researchers whose projects have had or potentially might have social impact but they did not gather these types of information before. Their contact with the IMPACT-EV projects makes them realize about the relevance and the importance in doing so, and they have committed to start doing so. On the other hand, those researchers whose work has had very limited social impact, we have witnessed many examples of how they started to reconsider the way they approach and design their works.

The analysis of IMPACT-EV has shown that there is not one indicator or quantitative measure to cover impact of various kinds. Characteristics for our approach is an intense, time consuming, but also informative, engaging and to some extent even intervening personal contact to PI's and main researchers, study of documentation, and usual qualitative methods. The later can help to structure observations, but not replace them. This unique combination of different methods of project analysis (interviews, questionnaires, baseline statistics) give weight to the reported observations.

Finally, even though the ex-ante evaluation has been progressively enhanced, there are some steps that can be done in this regard. First, a clarification should be made in differentiating between scientific, political and social impact. A suggestion can be made in order to require all the project proposals to clearly state this distinction. Project proposals should nail down the types of impacts they expect to obtain and to

include in which way they will be measured, and assessed. Second, in the same way researchers are required to include their record in scientific publications and presentations, they could also be required to include their previous achievements in terms of pursuing political and social impact, as part of the description of their resume. This resonates to different initiatives which are already selected success stories among projects which have achieved significant social impact, for instance, the recent European Commission selection, or the expressed interest of ORCID in including this type of information into their database of researchers' production by linking with SIOR, the newly created Social Impact Open Repository (IMPACT-EV).

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Annex 1: List of Acronyms

BSG-CSO - Research for the Benefit of Specific Groups Civil Society Organisations

CfWI - Centre for Workforce Intelligence

CORDIS - Community Research and Development Information Service

CP - Collaborative projects

CP-FP (small and medium) - Small or medium-scale focused research projects

CP-FP-SICA (small and medium) - Small or medium-scale focused research projects for specific cooperation action dedicated to international cooperation

CP-IP (large) - Large-scale integrating project

CP-IP-SICA (large) - Collaborative Project (large scale integrating project) for Specific International Cooperation Actions

CSA - Coordination and Supporting Actions

CSA - CA - Coordination (or networking) actions

CSA - ERA-PLUS –

CSA - SA - Coordination and Support Actions

CSO - Civil Society Organizations

EAV - European Added Value

E-CORDA - External COMmon Research DAta Warehouse

EC - European Commission

ERC - European Research Council

ERA - European Research Area

ESS - European Social Survey

ETP - European Technology Platform

EU- European Union

EU-JRC - European Union Joint Research Centre

FP- Framework Programme

FP5- Fifth Framework Programme

FP6- Sixth Framework Programme

FP7- Seventh Framework Programme

H2020 - HORIZON 2020

HSE - Higher of Secondary Education

ICPCs - International Cooperation Partner Countries

IPR- Intellectual Property Rights

ISSC - International Social Science Council

JCR – Journal Citation Report

MS - Member State

NAO - National Audit Office

OA - Open Access

OECD - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

ORCID - Open Researcher and Contributor ID

PRC - Private Commercial

PUB - Public Body (excl. Research and Education)

R&D - Research and Development

REC - Research Organisation

SESAM - European Commission online reporting tool for Research and Technological projects

SMEs - Small and Medium Enterprises

STI - Science, Technology and Innovation

Annex 2: List of projects

FP6 Priority 7

Acronym	Title	Call	
ACRE	Accommodating Creative Knowledge: Competitiveness of European Metropolitan Regions Within the Enlarged Union	FP6-CITIZENS	IP
AIM-AP	Accurate Income Measurement for the Assessment of Public Policies	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
CAPRIGHT	Resources, rights and capabilities; in search of social foundations for Europe	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
CBCED	Challenges and Prospects of Cross Border Co-operation in the Context of EU Enlargement	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
CIVICWEB	YOUNG PEOPLE, THE INTERNET AND CIVIC PARTICIPATION	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
COMPARE	Toolbox for Improving the Comparability of Cross-National Survey Data with Applications to SHARE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
CRIME AND CULTURE	Crime as a Cultural Problem. The Relevance of Perceptions of Corruption to Crime Prevention. A Comparative Cultural Study in the EU-Accession States, the EU-Candidate States and in the EU-States D,	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
DYLAN	LANGUAGE DYNAMICS AND MANAGEMENT OF DIVERSITY	FP6-CITIZENS	IP
DYNREG	Dynamic regions in a knowledge-driven global economy: lessons and policy implications for the EU	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
EMILIE	A European Approach to Multicultural Citizenship Legal Political and Educational Challenges	FP6-CITIZENS	STREP
ENEPO	EU Eastern Neighborhood: Economic Potential and Future Development	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
EREP	Social Knowledge for e-Governance	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
ESS4	European Social Survey Round 4 - Improving Social Measurement in Europe.	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
EUDIMENSIONS	Local Dimensions of a Wider European Neighbourhood: Developing Political Community through Practices and Discourses of Cross-Border Co-operation	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
EUREQUAL	Social Inequality and Why It Matters for the Economic and Democratic Development of Europe and Its Citizens. Post-Communist Central and Eastern Europe in Comparative Perspective	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP

EUROCCUPATIONS	Developing a detailed 8-country occupations database for comparative socio-economic research in the European Union.	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
EUROETHOS	Exploring the Scope for a Shared European Pluralistic Ethos. A comparative investigation of religious and secular ethically-derived requests for exemption from the law in an enlarging Europe	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
EUROSPHERE	Diversity and The European Public Sphere: Towards a Citizens' Europe	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
EVIA	Evaluating Integrated Impact Assessments	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
FEMCIT	Gendered Citizenship in Multicultural Europe: The Impact of the Contemporary Women's Movements	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
GEM-CON-BIO	Governance and Ecosystems Management for the CONservation of BIODiversity	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
G-FORS	Governance for Sustainability	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
GO-EUROMED	The Political Economy of Governance in the Euro-Mediterranean Partnership	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
INCLUD-ED	Strategies for inclusion and social cohesion in Europe from education	FP6-CITIZENS	IP
INEQ	Inequality: Mechanisms, Effects and Policies	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
JOBMOB AND FAMLIVES	Job Mobilities and Family Lives in Europe Modern Mobile Living and its Relation to Quality of Life	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
JURISTRAS	The Strasbourg Court, democracy and the human rights of individuals and communities: patterns of litigation, state implementation and domestic reform	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
KNOWANDPOL	The role of knowledge in the construction and regulation of health and education policy in Europe : convergences and specificities among nations and sectors	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
LINEE	Languages In a Network of European Excellence	FP6-CITIZENS	NoE
LOCALMULTIDEM	Multicultural Democracy and Immigrants' Social Capital in Europe: Participation, Organisational Networks, and Public Policies at the Local Level	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
MAGGIE	Major Ageing and Gender Issues in Europe	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
MICROCON	A Micro-Level Analysis of Violent Conflict	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
MICRO-DYN	The competitiveness of firms, regions and industries in the knowledge-based economy: What room for job-rich growth in Europe?	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
MIRICO	Legal Political and Educational Challenges	FP6-CITIZENS	STREP
PICO	Academic entrepreneurship from knowledge creation to knowledge diffusion	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
PIQUE	Privatisation of Public Services and the Impact on Quality, Employment and Productivity	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
PROKNOW	Production of Knowledge Revisited. The Impact of Academic Spin-Offs on public research performance in Europe	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP

PROMINSTAT	Promoting comparative quantitative research in the field of migration and integration in Europe	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
QUALITY	Quality of life in a changing Europe	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
QUING	Quality in Gender Equality Policies	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
RECON	Reconstituting Democracy in Europe	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
RECWOWE	Reconciling Work and Welfare in Europe	FP6-CITIZENS	NoE
REDCO	Religion in Education. A contribution to Dialogue or a factor of Conflict in transforming societies of European Countries	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
RESIST	Researching Inequality through Science and Technology	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
REVACERN	Religions And Values: Central And Eastern European Research Network	FP6-CITIZENS	STREP
RICAFE2	Regional Comparative Advantage and Knowledge Based Entrepreneurship	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
SAL	Society and Lifestyles: Towards Enhancing Social Harmonization through Knowledge of Subcultural Communities	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
SEFONE	Searching for Neighbours: Dynamics of Physical and Mental Borders in the New Europa	FP6-CITIZENS	STREP
SHARELIFE	Employment and health at 50+: A life history approach to European welfare state interventions	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	IP
SHUR	Human Rights in Conflicts: The Role of Civil Society	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
SOCCOH	The Challenge of Socio-economic Cohesion In the Enlarged European Union	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
SPREW	Generational approach to the Social Patterns of Relation to Work	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
SS-ERC	Project on Social Sciences and European Research Capacities	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
SSH-FUTURES	SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES FOR EUROPE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
TRANSLEARN	Transnational Learning through Local Experimenting - The creation of Dynamic Complementarities between Economy and Society	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
TRESEGY	Toward a social construction of an European youth-ness: experience of inclusion and exclusion in the public sphere among second generation migrated teenagers	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
TTSRL	Transnational Terrorism, Security and the Rule of Law	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
U-KNOW	Understanding the Relationship between Knowledge and Competitiveness in the Enlarging European Union	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
UPP	Understanding Privatisation Policy: Political Economy and Welfare Effects	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
VEIL	Values, Equality and Differences in Liberal Democracies. Debates about Female Muslim Headscarves in Europe.	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP

WAVE	Welfare and Values in Europe: Transitions related to Religion, Minorities and Gender	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	STREP
WORKCARE	Social quality and the changing relationships between work, care and welfare in Europe	FP6-CITIZENS	STREP

FP6 Priority 8

Acronym	Title	Call	
ASSET	Assessing sensitiveness to transport	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
AUTHENTICO	Authentication methodologies for metal artefacts based on material composition and manufacturing techniques	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
CHAMP	Changing behaviour of health care professionals and the general public towards a more prudent use of anti-microbial agents	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
CHEF	Cultural heritage protection against Flood	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
CLANDESTINO	Irregular Migration: Counting the Uncountable. Data and Trends Across Europe	CIS8	STREP
COINS	Combat on-line illegal numismatic sales	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
CONSCIENCE	Concepts and Science for Coastal Erosion Management	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
CONSTGLASS	Conservation materials for stained glass windows - assessment of treatments, studies on reversibility, and performance of innovative restoration strategies and products	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
CRCC	Crime Repression Costs in Context	CIS8	STREP
DECOIN	Development and comparison of sustainability indicators	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
DEMOB.INC	Development of a European measure of best practice for people with long term mental illness in institutional care	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
EACH-FOR	Environmental Change And Forced Migration Scenarios	CIS8	STREP
EUROFLU	Molecular factors and mechanisms of transmission and pathogenicity of highly pathogenic Avian Influenza Virus	FP6-2005-SSP-5-B-INFLUENZA	STREP
EUROVAQ	European value of a quality adjusted life year	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
FLUINNATE	Innate immunity in influenza virus infection of mammalian airways	FP6-2005-SSP-5-B-INFLUENZA	STREP
FLUPOL	Host-Specific variants of the influenza virus replication machinery	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
FLUVAC	Dose sparing and increased immunogenicity of a pandemic influenza vaccine by CoVaccine HT	FP6-2005-SSP-5-B-INFLUENZA	STREP
FORWAST	Overall mapping of physical flows and stocks of resources to forecast waste quantities in Europe and identify life-cycle environmental stakes of waste prevention and recycling	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
FURAN-RA	Role of genetic and non-genetic mechanisms in furan risk		STREP

HAPPY AUDIT	Health alliance for prudent prescribing, yield and use of antimicrobial drugs in the treatment of respiratory tract infections	SP5A-CT-2007-044154	STREP
IDEA	Mediterranean and Eastern European Countries as new immigration destinations in the European Union	CIS8	STREP
INDI-LINK	Indicator-based evaluation of inter-linkages between different sustainable development objectives	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
INNO-HTA	HTA-methodology for innovative healthcare technologies	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
INTRANASAL H5VACCINE	Immunogenicity and protective efficacy of intranasal delNS1(H5N1) influenza vaccine	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
MODELS	Model development for the evaluation of Lisbon strategies	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
PANFLUVAC	Efficacious vaccine formulation system for prophylactic control of influenza pandemics	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
PRIMA-EF	Development of a European psychosocial Risk Management Framework	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
PRIONSCREEN	Development of a blood screening assay for diagnosis of prion diseases in humans	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
PROPAINT	Improved protection of paintings during exhibition, storage and transit	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
RASP	Rapid SPR for parallel detection of pathogens in blood	FP6-POLICIES	STREP
TOOLQIT	Tools for the assessment of level and quality of service across different transport market segments	FP6-2005-SSP-5-A	STREP
UWT	Undocumented Worker Transitions: Compiling evidence concerning the boundaries and processes of change in the status and work of undocumented workers in Europe	CIS8	STREP

FP7 SSH

Acronym	Title	Call	
ACCEPT PLURALISM	Tolerance, Pluralism and Social Cohesion. Responding to the challenges of the 21st century in Europe	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
AEGIS	Advancing knowledge-intensive entrepreneurship and innovation for growth and social well-being in Europe	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-IP
AGENTA	Ageing Europe: An application of National Transfer Accounts (NTA) for explaining and projecting trends in public finances	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
ALAC'S	Promotion of Participation and Citizenship in Europe through the "Advocacy and Legal Advice Centres (ALACs)" of Transparency International	FP7-SSH-2007-1	BSG-CSO
ALICE RAP	Addictions and lifestyles in contemporary Europe – Reframing addictions project	FP7-SSH-2010-1	CP-IP
AMELI	Advanced methodology for European laeken indicators	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
ANTICORRP	Anticorruption Policies Revisited. Global Trends and European Responses to the Challenge of Corruption	FP7-SSH-2011-1	CP-IP
ARABTRANS	Political and Social Transformations in the Arab World	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP-SICA
ASPA	Activating senior potential in ageing Europe	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
ASSPRO CEE 2007	Assessment of patient payment policies and projection of their efficiency, equity and quality effects. The case of Central and Eastern Europe	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
ATHEME	5.2.1 ATHEME- Advancing the European Multilingual Experience	FP7-SSH-2013-1	CP-IP
ATLANTIC FUTURE	Towards an Atlantic area? Mapping trends, perspectives and interregional dynamics between Europe, Africa and the Americas	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP-SICA
ATLAS	Armed conflicts, peacekeeping, transitional justice: law as solution	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
AUGUR	Challenges for Europe in the world of 2025	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
BEUCITIZEN	All Rights Reserved? Barriers towards EUropean CITIZENship.	FP7-SSH-2012-1	CP-IP
BLUE-ETS	BLUE-Enterprise and Trade Statistics	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
CAP-IRE	Assessing the multiple impacts of the Common Agricultural Policies (CAP) on rural economies	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
CHANCE2SUSTAIN	Urban Chances: City growth and the sustainability challenge; Comparing fast growing cities in growing economies	FP7-SSH-2009-B	CP-SICA
CARE	Curriculum Quality Analysis and Impact Review of European ECEC	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
CASCADE	Exploring the Security-Democracy Nexus in the Caucasus	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP-SICA
CHANCE2SUSTAIN	Urban Chances: City growth and the sustainability challenge; Comparing fast growing cities in growing economies	FP7-SSH-2009-B	CP-SICA
CHINA EU STANDARDS	China EU information Technology standards	8.2. Horizontal	CSA-CA -

	research partnership	measures to support international cooperation	Coordination (or networking) actions
CHINESEVIEWSOFEU	Disaggregating Chinese perceptions of the EU and the implications for the EU'S China policy	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
CITISPYCE	Combating inequalities through innovative social practices of, and for, young people in cities across Europe	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
CIT-PART	Impact of citizen participation on decision-making in a knowledge intensive policy field	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
CIVISTI	Citizen visions on science, technology and innovation	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
CLICO	Climate Change, Hydro-conflicts and Human Security	FP7-SSH-2009-B	CP-SICA
COCOPS	Coordinating for Cohesion in the Public Sector of the Future	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
COEURE	Cooperation for European Research in Economics	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CSA-CA - Coordination (or networking) actions
COINVEST	Competitiveness, innovation and intangible investment in Europe	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
CONSENSUS	Confronting social and environmental sustainability with economic pressure: balancing trade-offs by policy dismantling?	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
CONSENT	Consumer sentiment regarding privacy on user generated content services in the digital economy	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
COPE	Combating Poverty in Europe: Re-organising Active Inclusion through Participatory and Integrated Modes of Multilevel Governance	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
CORE	The role of Governance in the Resolution of Socioeconomic and Political Conflict in India and Europe	FP7-SSH-2010-3	CP-FP-SICA
COUNTER	Socio-economic and cultural impacts of the consumption of counterfeit goods	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
CREATING	Cooperative research on East African territorial Integration within globalisation	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CSA-SA - Support actions
CRESSI	Creating Economic Space for Social Innovation	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
CRE8TV.EU	Creativity for Innovation & Growth in Europe	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
CRIC	Identity and conflict. Cultural heritage and the re-construction of identities after conflict	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
CSEYHP	Combating social exclusion among young homeless populations: a comparative investigation of homeless paths and reinsertion programmes for young men and women of different ethnic and migrant statuses	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
DEMETER	Development of methods and tools for evaluation of research	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
DEMHOW	Demographic change and housing wealth	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP

DERREG	Developing Europe's rural regions in the era of globalization: an interpretative model for better anticipating and responding to challenges for regional development in an evolving international context	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
DESAFIO	DEMOCRATISATION OF WATER AND SANITATION GOVERNANCE BY MEANS OF SOCIO-TECHNICAL INNOVATION	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP-SICA
DIASPEACE	Diasporas for peace: patterns, trends and potential of long-distance diaspora involvement in conflict settings. case studies from the horn of Africa	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
DISCIT	Making Persons with Disabilities Full Citizens - New Knowledge for an Inclusive and Sustainable European Social Model	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
DIVERCITIES	Governing Urban Diversity: Creating Social Cohesion, Social Mobility and Economic Performance in Today's Hyper-diversified Cities	FP7-SSH-2012-1	CP-IP
DOMAC	Impact of international criminal procedures on domestic criminal procedures in mass atrocity cases	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
ECOPAS	European Consortium for Pacific Studies	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CSA-CA - Coordination (or networking) actions
EDC2020	European development co-operation to 2020	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EDUMIGROM	Ethnic differences in education and diverging prospects for urban youth in an enlarged Europe	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EERQI	European educational research quality indicators	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EFFACE	European Union Action to Fight Environmental Crime	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
EFIGE	European firms in a global economy: internal policies for external competitiveness	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-IP
EFP	European foresight platform – Supporting forward looking decision-making	FP7-SSH-2009-C	CSA-SA - Support actions
E-FRAME	European framework for measuring progress	FP7-SSH-2011-3	CSA-SA - Support actions
ELDIA	European Language Diversity for All: Reconceptualising, promoting and re-evaluating individual and societal multilingualism	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
ENACT	Enacting European citizenship	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
ENGOV	Environmental Governance in Latin America and the Caribbean: Developing Frameworks for Sustainable and Equitable Natural Resource Use	FP7-SSH-2010-3	CP-FP-SICA
ENRI-EAST	Interplay of European, national and regional identities: nations between states along the new eastern borders of the European Union	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EQUIP	EU-India Social Sciences and Humanities Platform	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CSA-SA - Support

			actions
ERANID	European Research Area Network on Illicit Drugs - Towards integrated European research in illicit drugs: cause and nature of drug problems; interventions and policies	FP7-ERANET-2012-RTD	CSA-SA - Support actions
EU4SEAS	The EU and sub-regional multilateralism in Europe's sea basins: neighbourhood, enlargement and multilateral cooperation	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EUBORDERREGIONS	European Regions, EU External Borders and the Immediate Neighbours. Analysing Regional Development Options through Policies and Practices of Cross-Border Co-operation	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
EUBORDERSCAPES	Bordering, Political Landscapes and Social Arenas: Potentials and Challenges of Evolving Border Concepts in a post-Cold War World	FP7-SSH-2011-1	CP-IP
EUCROSS	The Europeanisation of Everyday Life: Cross-Border Practices and Transnational Identities among EU and Third-Country Citizens	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
EU-GRASP	Changing multilateralism: The EU as a global-regional actor in security and peace	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EU-INNOVATE	Sustainable Lifestyles 2.0: End User Integration, Innovation and Entrepreneurship	FP7-SSH-2013-1	CP-IP
EULAKS	Connecting socio-economic research on the Dynamics of the knowledge society in the European Union and Latin American and Caribbean Countries	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CSA-CA - Coordination (or networking) actions
EUMAGINE	Imagining Europe from the outside. On the role of democracy and human rights perceptions in constructing migration aspirations and decision towards Europe	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
EUMARGINS	On the margins of the European community young adult immigrants in seven European countries	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EUNAMUS	European national museums: Identity politics, the uses of the past and the European citizen	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
EURA-NET	Transnational Migration in Transition: Transformative Characteristics of Temporary Mobility of People	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
EURASIA-NET	Europe-South Asia exchange on supranational (regional) policies and instruments for the promotion of human rights and management of minority issues	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CSA-SA - Support actions
EURESCL	Slave trade slavery abolitions and their legacies in European histories and identities	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EURISLAM	Finding a place for Islam in Europe: cultural interactions between Muslim immigrants and receiving societies	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EUROBROADMAP	European union & the world seen from abroad	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EURO-FESTIVAL	Art festivals and the European public culture	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP

EUROIDENTITIES	The evolution of European identity: using biographical methods to study the development of European identity	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EURO-JUSTIS	Scientific indicators of confidence in justice: tools for policy assessment	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
EUROPOLIS	EuroPolis: a deliberative polity-making project	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
FACIT	Faith-based organisations and exclusion in European cities	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
FAMILIESANDSOCIETIES	Changing families and sustainable societies: Policy contexts and diversity over the life course and across generations	FP7-SSH-2012-1	CP-IP
FAMILYPLATFORM	Social platform on research for families and family policies	FP7-SSH-2009-C	CSA-CA - Coordination (or networking) actions
FARHORIZON	Use of foresight to align research with longer term policy needs in Europe	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
FESSUD	Financialisation, economy, society and sustainable development.	FP7-SSH-2010-1	CP-IP
FIDUCIA	New European Crimes and Trust-based Policy	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
FINESS	Financial systems, efficiency and stimulation of sustainable growth	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
FINMAP	Financial Distortions and Macroeconomic Performance: Expectations, Constraints and Interaction of Agents	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
FINNOV	Finance, innovation and growth: Changing patterns and policy implications	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
FLAGSHIP	Forward Looking Analysis of Grand Societal Challenges and Innovative Policies	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
FLASH-IT	Facilitating access to socio-economic research through information and communications Technology	FP7-SSH-2011-3	CSA-SA - Support actions
FLAWS	Impact of local welfare systems on female labour force participation and social cohesion	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
FOODSECURE	Exploring the Future of Global Food and Nutrition Security	FP7-SSH-2011-1	CP-IP
FRAME	Fostering Human Rights Among European (external and internal) Policies	FP7-SSH-2012-1	CP-IP
FREE	Football Research in an Enlarged Europe: Identity dynamics, perception patterns and cultural change in Europe's most prominent form of popular culture	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
FRIDA	Fostering regional innovation and development through anchors and networks: a cross regional comparison in an evolving international context	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
GEITONIES	Generating interethnic tolerance and neighborhood integration in European urban spaces	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP

GEMIC	Gender, migration and intercultural interactions in the Mediterranean and South East Europe: an interdisciplinary perspective	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
GEMMA	Enhancing evidence based policy-making in gender and migration	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CSA-SA - Support actions
GENDERACE	The use of racial anti-discrimination laws: gender and citizenship in a multicultural context	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
GILDED	Governance, infrastructure, lifestyle dynamics and energy demand: european post-carbon communities	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
GINI	Growing Inequalities' Impacts	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
GLAMURS	Green Lifestyles, Alternative Models and Upscaling Regional Sustainability	FP7-SSH-2013-1	CP-IP
GLOBAL VALUE	Assessing the Impacts of Multinational Corporations on GLOBAL Development and VALUE Creation	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP-SICA
GLOBAL-IQ	Impacts Quantification of global changes	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
GLOBINN	The changing nature of internationalization of innovation in Europe: impact on firms and the implications for innovation policy in the EU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
GOETE	Governance of Educational Trajectories in Europe. Access, coping and relevance of education for young people in European knowledge societies in comparative perspective	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
GRASP	Growth and sustainability policies for Europe	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
GREEN	Global Re-ordering: Evolution through European Networks	FP7-SSH-2010-1	CP-IP
GRINCOH	Growth-Innovation-Competitiveness: Fostering Cohesion in Central and Eastern Europe	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
GUSTO	Meeting the challenges of economic uncertainty and sustainability through employment, industrial relations, social and environmental policies in European countries	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
HERA			CSA -ERA-PLUS
HI-POD	Historical patterns of development and underdevelopment: origins and persistence of the great divergence	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
IAREG	Intangible assets and regional economic growth	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
ICATSEM	Institutional changes and trajectories of socio-economic development models	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
IDEAS	Integrating and developing European Asian studies	FP7-SSH-2009-C	CSA-SA - Support actions

IKNOW	interconnecting knowledge for the early identification of issues, events and developments (e.g. wild cards and associated weak signals) shaping and shaking the future of STI in the ERA	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
IME	Identities and modernities in Europe: European and national identity construction programmes and politics, culture, history and religion	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
IMME	Mobility and inclusion in multilingual europe		CP-IP
IMPACT	Impact Measurement and Performance Analysis of CSR	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
IMPACT-EV	Evaluating the impact and outcomes of European SSH research	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
IMPROVE	Poverty Reduction in Europe: Social policy and innovation	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
INDICSER	Indicators for evaluating international performance in service sectors	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
INFOCON	Involving Transnational Communities - Civil Society Forum on Conflicts	FP7-SSH-2007-1	BSG-CSO
INFOCORE	(in)forming conflict prevention, response and resolution: the role of media in violent conflict	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
INFU	Innovation futures in europe: A foresight exercise on emerging patterns of innovation. visions, scenarios and implications for policy and practice	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
ENGINEUS	Impact of networks, globalisation, and their interaction with EU strategies	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-IP
INNODRIVE	Intangible capital and innovations: drivers of growth and location in the EU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
INNOS&T	Innovative S&T indicators combining patent data and surveys: Empirical models and policy analyses	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
INNOSERV	Social platform for innovative social services	FP7-SSH-2011-3	CSA-SA - Support actions
INSPIRES	Innovative Social and Employment Policies for Inclusive and Resilient Labour Markets in Europe	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
INTERCO-SSH	INTERNational COoperation in the SSH: Comparative Socio-Historical Perspectives and Future Possibilities	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
IRISS	Increasing Resilience in Surveillance Societies	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
ISSICEU	Intra-and Inter-Societal Sources of Instability in the Caucasus and EU Opportunities to Respond	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP-SICA

ITSSOIN	Social Innovation and Civic Engagement	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
JAD-PBP	Just and durable peace by piece	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
LEPAS	Long-run economic perspectives of an ageing society	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
LIPSE	Learning from Innovation in Public Sector Environments	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
LIVEWHAT	Living with Hard Times: How European Citizens Deal with Economic Crises and Their Social and Political Consequences	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
LLLIGHT'IN'EUROPE	Lifelong Learning, Innovation, Growth and Human capital Tracks in Europe	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
LOCALISE	Local Worlds of Social Cohesion. The Local Dimension of Integrated Social and Employment Policies	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
MACFINROBODS	Integrated Macro-Financial Modelling for Robust Policy Design	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
MAFE	Migration between Africa and Europe	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
MAPCOMPETE	Mapping European Competitiveness	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CSA-CA - Coordination (or networking) actions
MAXCAP	Maximizing the integration capacity of the European Union: Lessons and prospects for enlargement and beyond	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
MECODEM	Media, Conflict and Democratisation	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
MEDEA	Models and their effects on development paths: an ethnographic and comparative approach to knowledge transmission and livelihood strategies	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
MEDIA & CITIZENSHIP	Media and citizenship: transnational television cultures reshaping political identity in the European Union	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
MEDIAACT	Media Accountability and Transparency in Europe	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
MEDIADEM	European Media Policies Revisited: Valuing and Reclaiming Free and Independent Media in Contemporary Democratic Systems	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
MEDPRO	Prospective Analysis for the Mediterranean Region	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
MELA	European Museums and Libraries in/of the Age of Migrations	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
MEMOLA	MEDITerranean MOUNTAINOUS LANDscapes: an historical approach to cultural heritage based on traditional agrosystems	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP

MERCURY	Multilateralism and the EU in the contemporary global order	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
MIG@NET	Transnational Digital Networks, Migration and Gender	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
MIGROM	The immigration of Romanian Roma to Western Europe: Causes, effects, and future engagement strategies.	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
MILESECURE-2050	Multidimensional Impact of the Low-carbon European Strategy on Energy Security, and Socio-Economic Dimension up to 2050 perspective	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
MIRRIIS	Mobilizing institutional reforms for better R&I systems/institutions in Europe	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CSA-SA - Support actions
MNEMERGE	A Framework Model on MNE's impact on global development challenges in emerging markets	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP-SICA
MONFISPOL	Modeling and implementation of optimal fiscal and monetary policy algorithms in multi-country econometric models	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
MOPACT	MOBILISING THE POTENTIAL OF ACTIVE AGEING IN EUROPE	FP7-SSH-2012-1	CP-IP
MULTILINKS	How demographic changes shape intergenerational solidarity, well-being, and social integration: a multilinks framework	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
MULTIPART	Multi-stakeholder partnerships in post-conflict reconstruction: the role of the European Union	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
MYPLACE	Memory, Youth, Political Legacy And Civic Engagement	FP7-SSH-2010-1	CP-IP
MYWEB	Measuring Youth Well-Being	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CSA-SA - Support actions
NET4SOCIETY3	Trans-national co-operation among National Contact Points for Socio-economic Sciences and the Humanities (SSH NCPs)	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CSA-SA - Support actions
NET4SOCIETY	Trans-national co-operation among National Contact Points (NCP) for Socio-economic Sciences and Humanities	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CSA-SA - Support actions
NET4SOCIETY2	Trans-national cooperation among National Contact Points for Socioeconomic Sciences and the Humanities (SSH NCPs)	FP7-SSH-2010-4	CSA-SA - Support actions
NEUJOBS	Employment 2025: How will multiple transitions affect the European labour market	FP7-SSH-2010-1	CP-IP
NOPOOR	Enhancing Knowledge for Renewed Policies against Poverty	FP7-SSH-2011-1	CP-IP-SICA
NORFACE			CSA-ERA-PLUS
NORFACE-II	New opportunities for Research Funding Agency cooperation in Europe II		CSA-SA - Support actions

PACT	Pathways for carbon transitions	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
PASHMINA	PARadigm SHifts Modelling and INnovative Approaches	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
PEGGED	Politics, economics and global governance: the European dimensions	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-IP
PICK-ME	Policy Incentives for the Creation of Knowledge: Methods and Evidence	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
PIDOP	Processes influencing democratic ownership and participation	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
PLATON	Strengthening the role that Socio-economic Sciences and Humanities (SSH) have on the ERA development by reinforcing interactions between SSH and non-SSH research communities		CSA-CA - Coordination (or networking) actions
POCACITO	POst-CARbon CIties of TOMorrow – foresight for sustainable pathways towards liveable, affordable and prospering cities in a world context	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
POCARIM	Mapping the population, careers, mobilities and impacts of advanced research degree graduates in the social sciences and humanities	FP7-SSH-2011-3	CSA-SA - Support actions
POINT	Policy influence of indicators	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
POLHIA	Monetary, fiscal and structural policies with heterogeneous agents	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
POLINARES	POLicy for NATural RESources	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
POWER2YOUTH	‘Freedom, dignity and justice’: A comprehensive approach to the understanding of youth exclusion and the prospects for youth inclusion and overall change in the South and East Mediterranean	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP-SICA
PRIV-WAR	Regulating privatisation of war : the role of the EU in assuring the compliance with international humanitarian law and human rights	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
PROFACITY	Profane citizenship in Europe - testing democratic ownership in hybrid situations	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
PRONTO	Productivity, Non-Tariff Measures and Openness	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
RASTANEWS	Macro-Risk Assessment and Stabilization Policies with New Early Warning Signals	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
RELIGARE	Religious Diversity and Secular Models in Europe Innovative Approaches to Law and Policy	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
REMC	Religious education in a multicultural society: school and home in comparative context	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP

REMEDIE	Regenerative medicine in Europe: emerging needs and challenges in a global context	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
REPRO	Reproductive decision-making in a macro-micro perspective	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
RESCUE	Patterns of Resilience during Socioeconomic Crises among Households in Europe	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
RESLEU	Reducing Early School Leaving in the EU.	FP7-SSH-2012-1	CP-IP
RESPECT	Towards a Topography of Tolerance and Equal Respect. A comparative study of policies for the distribution of public spaces in culturally diverse societies	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
RICHES	Renewal, Innovation and Change: Heritage and European Society	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
RISQ	Representativity indicators for survey quality	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
RUFUS	Rural future networks	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
RURBANAFRICA	African Rural-City Connections	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP-SICA
SAHWA	Empowering the young generation: towards a new social contract in South and East Mediterranean countries (SAHWA)	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP-SICA
SAMPLE	Small area methods for poverty and living condition estimates	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SANDERA	The future impact of security and defence policies on the European research area	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SCIFI-GLOW	SCience, innovation, firms and markets in a globalized world	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SCOOP	Socio-economic sciences: communicating outcomes oriented to policy	FP7-SSH-2009-C	CSA-SA - Support actions
SEARCH	Sharing Knowledge Assets: InteRegionally Cohesive NeighBorhoods	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
SEATIDE	Integration in Southeast Asia: Trajectories of Inclusion, Dynamics of Exclusion	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP-SICA
SEFORIS	2.1.2 SEFORIS- Social Enterprise as Force for more Inclusive and Innovative Societies	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
SELUSI	Social entrepreneurs as "lead users" for service innovation	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SERVICEGAP	The impact of service sector innovation and internationalisation on growth and productivity	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
SERVPPIN	The contribution of public and private services to European growth and welfare, and the role of public-private innovation networks	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SESTI	Scanning for emerging science and technology issues	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SHRINK SMART	Governance of shrinkage within a European context	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research

			project
SI-DRIVE	Governance of shrinkage within a European context	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SIMPACT	Boosting the Impact of Social Innovation in Europe through Economic Underpinnings	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
SIMPATIC	Social IMPact Policy Analysis of Technological Innovation Challenges	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
SMARTSPEC	Smart Specialisation For Regional Innovation	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
SMILE	Synergies in multi-scale inter-linkages of eco-social systems	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project
SOCIAL POLIS	Synergies in multi-scale inter-linkages of eco-social systems	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SOCIETY	Social Innovation - Empowering the Young (SocIEtY) for the Common Good	FP7-SSH-2012-2	CP-FP
SOM	Support and opposition to migration. A cross national comparison of the politicization of migration	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SPHERE	Space, place and the historical and contemporary articulations of regional, national and European identities through work and community in areas undergoing economic restructuring and regeneration	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
SPINTAN	Smart Public Intangibles	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
SPREAD	Social platform on sustainable lifestyles	FP7-SSH-2010-4	CSA-SA - Support actions
STYLE	Strategic Transitions for Youth Labour in Europe	FP7-SSH-2013-1	CP-IP
SUSTAINCITY	Micro-simulation for the prospective of sustainable cities in Europe	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
SYRTO	SYstemic Risk TOMography: Signals, Measurements, Transmission Channels, and Policy Intervention	FP7-SSH-2012-2	
T-AP	Trans-Atlantic Platform for the Social Sciences and Humanities	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CSA-SA - Support actions
TEMPER	Temporary versus permanent migration	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
TENLAW	Tenancy Law and Housing Policy in Multi-level Europe	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
TEPSIE	The theoretical, empirical and policy foundations for building social innovation in Europe	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP

THIRD SECTOR IMPACT	The Contribution of the Third Sector to Europe's Socio-economic Development	FP7-SSH-2013-2	CP-FP
TOLERACE	The semantics of tolerance and (anti-)racism in Europe: public bodies and civil society on a comparative perspective	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
TRANSIT	Transformative Social Innovation Theory project	FP7-SSH-2013-1	CP-IP
TRANS-NET	Transnationalisation, migration and transformation: Multi-level analysis of migrant transnationalism (TRANS-NET)	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
TRANSWORLD	Redefining the transatlantic relationship and its role in shaping global governance	FP7-SSH-2011-2	CP-FP
URBACHINA	Sustainable Urbanisation in China : Historical and Comparative Perspectives, Mega-trends towards 2050	FP7-SSH-2010-3	CP-FP-SICA
VERA	Forward visions on the European Research Area	FP7-SSH-2011-3	CSA-SA - Support actions
VICO	Financing entrepreneurial ventures in Europe: impact on innovation, employment growth, and competitiveness	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
WALQING	Work and Life Quality in New and Growing Jobs	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
WCS-WORCARE SYNERGIES	Dissemination of Synthesized Framework Programme Research Findings results on work-care, family policy, female empowerment, flexicurity, social quality and cohesion for efficient stakeholder and policy use		CSA-SA - Support actions
WILCO	Welfare Innovations at the Local level In favour of Cohesion	FP7-SSH-2010-2	CP-FP
WIOD	World Input-Output Database: Construction and Applications	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-IP
WORKABLE	Making capabilities work	FP7-SSH-2009-A	CP-FP
WWFOREUROPE	Welfare, Wealth and Work for Europe	FP7-SSH-2011-1	CP-IP
YIPPEE	Young people from a public care background: pathways to education in Europe	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP
YOUNEX	Youth, unemployment, and exclusion in Europe: a multidimensional approach to understanding the conditions and prospects for social and political integration of young unemployed	FP7-SSH-2007-1	CP-FP

HERA I

Acronym	Title	Call	
CIM	Creativity and Innovation in a World of Movement (CIM)		
CinBA	Creativity and Craft Production in Middle and Late		

	Bronze Age Europe (CinBA)		
CMRP	Cultural Memory and the Resources of the Past, 400 - 1000 AD (CMRP)		
CULTIVATE	Copyrighting Creativity: Creative Values, Cultural Heritage Institutions and Systems of Intellectual Property (CULTIVATE)		
ELMCIP	ELMCIP: Electronic Literature as a Model of Creativity and Innovation in Practice		
HERAVALUE	Measuring the Societal Impacts of Universities' Research into Arts and the Humanities (HERAVALUE)		
IDII4MES	Investigating Discourses of Inheritance and Identity in Four Multilingual European Settings (IDII4MES)		
MAW	Memory at War: Cultural Dynamics in Poland, Russia and Ukraine (MAW)		
OOR	Of Authorship and Originality: Reclaiming Copyright in Support of Creative Collaboration in the Digital Environment (OOR)		
PhotoCLEC	Photographs, Colonial Legacy and Museums in Contemporary European Culture (PhotoCLEC)		
POPID	Popular Music Heritage, Cultural Memory and Cultural Identity: stories and their Significance for Music Audiences and Music Industries in Europe (POPID)		
ROMIDENT	The Role of Language in the Transnational Formation of Romani Identity (ROMIDENT)		
Rhythm Changes	Rhythm Changes: Jazz Cultures and European Identities (Rhythm Changes)		
SAWS	Sharing Ancient Wisdoms: Exploring the Tradition of Greek and Arabic Wisdom Literatures (SAWS)		
SCIBE	Scarcity and Creativity in the Built Environment (SCIBE)		
TAP	The Assembly Project - Meeting Places in Northern Europe AD 400-1500 (TAP)		
TEF	Technology, Exchange and Flow: Artistic Media Practices & Commercial Application (TEF)		
	Fashioning the Early Modern: Innovation and Creativity in Europe, 1500-1800 (Fashioning the Early Modern)		
	The Dynamics of the Medieval Manuscript: Text Collections from a European Perspective (DynamicsoftheMedievalManuscript)		

NORFACE

Acronym	Title	Call	
CHOICES	Understanding Migrants' Choices		
CILS4EU	Children of Immigrants. A Longitudinal Study in Four European Countries		
IMEM	Integrated Modeling of European Migration		
LineUp	500 Families: Migration Histories of Turks in Europe		
MI3	Migration: Integration, Impact and Interaction		
MIDI-REDIE	Migrant Diversity and Regional Disparity in Europe		
NODES	Nordic welfare states and the dynamics and effects of ethnic residential segregation		
SCIP	Causes and Consequences of Early Socio-Cultural Integration Processes Among New Immigrants in Europe		
SIMCUR	Social Integration of Migrant Children: Uncovering		

	Family and School Factors Promoting Resilience		
TCRAF-Eu	Transnational child-raising arrangements between Africa and Europe		
TEMPO	Temporary Migration, integration and the role of Policies		
THEMIS	Theorizing the Evolution of European Migration Systems		
	Transnational Southern Pentecostal Churches, Networks and Believers in Three Northern Countries: a Potential and Potent Social Force		
	The Architecture of Contemporary Religious Transmission		
	Gender, National and Religious Diversity in Force at European Pilgrimage Sites		
	What are the Impacts of Religious Diversity? Regions in three European Countries Compared		
	Islam as a Social Force in Europe: Islamic fashion and the Politics of Presence		
	Ethnic Identity and Religious Mobilisation of the European Second Generation: Comparing Muslim Youth in Multicultural Cities		
	“Recognizing Christianity” • : How African Immigrants Redefine the European Religious Heritage		
	Religious Sources of Solidarity (EURESOURCE)		
	Religion, Euroscepticism, and the Media		
	Extending and Enhancing the ISSP 2008 Module on Religion		
	Religion, mobility and place: training and developing innovative theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of religion in Europe		
	European Network on the Investigation of Religious Pluralism		

FP7 Health (SSH embedded)

Acronym	Title	Call	
AAA-PREVENT	Effective Environmental Strategies for the Prevention of Alcohol Abuse among Adolescents in Europe	FP7-HEALTH-2009-single-stage	CP-FP
ABC	Ascertaining Barriers for Compliance: policies for safe, effective and cost-effective use of medicines in Europe	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
AMPHORA	Alcohol Measures for Public Health Research Alliance (AMPHORA)	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
ANCIEN	Assessing Needs of Care In European Nations	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
BECAN	Balkan Epidemiological Study on Child Abuse and Neglect	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
BRIDGE	Scoping study of approaches to Brokering knowledge and Research Information to support the Development and Governance of health systems in Europe	FP7-SEC-2010-1	CP
CAMBRELLA	CAMbrella – A pan-European research network for Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM)	FP7-HEALTH-2009-sing	CSA-CA
CEDAR	Clinical decision making and outcome in routine care for people with severe mental illness	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
CHICOS	Developing a Child Cohort Research Strategy for Europe	FP7-HEALTH-2009-sing	CSA-CA
COPING	Children of Prisoners, Interventions & Mitigations to Strengthen Mental Health	FP7-HEALTH-2009-sing	CP-FP

COURAGE IN EUROPE	COURAGE in Europe - Collaborative Research on AGEing in Europe	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
DUQUE	Deepening our understanding of quality improvement in Europe	FP7-HEALTH-2009-single-stage	CP-FP
ECHOUTCOME	European Consortium in Healthcare Outcomes and cost-benefit research	FP7-HEALTH-2009-sing	CP-FP
ECOSH	Occupational Health and Safety Economics	FP7-HEALTH-2007-A	CSA-SA
EIS	Development of a European Implementation Score for measuring implementation of research into healthcare practice using vascular disease as an example	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
ENBREC	European Network of Bipolar Research Expert Centres	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CSA-SA
ENCE-CF-LAM-LTX	European Networks of Centres of Expertise for CF (Cystic Fibrosis), LAM (Lymphangiomyomatosis), and LTX (Lung Transplantation)	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CSA-SA
ENERGY	European Energy balance Research to prevent excessive weight Gain among Youth	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
EQUITABLE	Enabling universal and equitable access to healthcare for vulnerable people in poor resource settings	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-SICA
EQUITY-LA	Impact on equity of access and efficiency of Integrated Health care Networks (IHN) in Colombia and Brazil	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-SICA
EUCBCC	EUropean Cross Border Care Collaborations Short Title: CrossEurope	FP7-HEALTH-2009-single-stage	CP-FP
EUPRIMECARE	Quality and costs of primary care in Europe	FP7-HEALTH-2009-single-stage	CP-FP
EURODRG	EuroDRG – Diagnosis-Related Groups in Europe: towards Efficiency and Quality	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
EUROREACH	EuroREACH A Handbook to Access Health Care Data for Cross-country Comparisons of Efficiency and Quality	FP7-HEALTH-2009-single-stage	CSA-CA
FUTURAGE	FUTURAGE: A Roadmap for Ageing Research	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CSA-CA
GRADIENT	Tackling the Gradient: Applying Public Health Policies to Effectively Reduce Health Inequalities amongst Families and Children	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
HANDOVER	Improving the Continuity of patient care Through Identification and implementation of Novel patient handoff processes in Europe	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
HEALTHATWORK	An inquiry into the health and safety at work; a European Union perspective	FP7-HEALTH-2007-A	CSA-SA
HESVIC	Health system stewardship and regulation in Vietnam, India and China	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-SICA
HISCREENDIAG	Building a Tool to Evaluate and Improve Health Investments in Screening and Diagnosis of disease		
HITT-2008	Health in Times of Transition: Trends in Population Health and Health Policies in CIS Countries	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-SICA
HEMOCARE	Clinical Continuity by Integrated Care	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
HSREPP	Health Services Research into European Policy and Practice: preparation and organisation of a European Health Services Research Conference	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CSA-SA
INTEGRIS	“Improved methodology for data collection on accidents and disabilities – Integration of European Injury Statistics”	FP7-HEALTH-2007-A	CP-FP

INTERLINKS	Health systems and long-term care for older people in Europe – Modelling the INTERfaces and LINKS between prevention, rehabilitation, quality of services and informal care	FP7-HEALTH-2007-B	CP-FP
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FP7 Energy (SSH embedded)

Acronym	Title	Call	
ATEST	Analysing Transition planning and Systemic Energy Planning Tools for the implementation of the Energy Technology Information System	FP7-ENERGY-2007-1-RT	FP7-ENERGY
BARENERGY	Barriers for energy changes among end consumers and households	FP7-ENERGY-2007-1-RT	FP7-ENERGY
CHANGING BEHAVIOUR	Contextualising behavioural change in energy programmes involving intermediaries and policymaking organizations working towards changing BEHAVIOUR	FP7-ENERGY-2007-1-RT	FP7-ENERGY
EFONET	Energy Foresight Network	FP7-ENERGY-2007-1-RT	FP7-ENERGY
PLANETS	Probabilistic Long-term Assessment of New Energy Technology Scenarios	FP7-ENERGY-2007-1-RT	FP7-ENERGY
REACCESS	Risk of Energy Availability: Common Corridors for Europe Supply Security	FP7-ENERGY-2007-1-RT	FP7-ENERGY
SECURE	Security of Energy Considering its Uncertainty, Risk and Economic Implications	FP7-ENERGY-2007-1-RT	FP7-ENERGY

ERC

Acronym	Title	Call	
19TH-CENTURY_EUCLID	Nineteenth-Century Euclid: geometry and the literary imagination from wordsworth to wells	ERC-2007-STG, SH4	Starting Grant
ACAP	Agency costs and asset pricing	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
AFDMATS	Anton Francesco doni multimedia archive texts and sources	ERC-2007-StG, SH4	Starting Grant
AGRIWESTMED	Origins and spread of agriculture in the south-western Mediterranean region	ERC-2008-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
AIDA	Architectural design in dialogue with dis-ability theoretical and methodological exploration of a multi-sensorial design approach in architecture	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
ALMP_ECON	Effective evaluation of active labour market policies in social insurance programs - improving the interaction between econometric evaluation estimators and economic theory	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
ALREG	Analysing learning in regulatory governance	ERC-2008-AdG, SH2	Advanced Grant

ANXIETY & COGNITION	How anxiety transforms human cognition: an affective neuroscience perspective	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
AORVM	The effects of aging on object representation in visual working memory	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
BBSG	Bosnian bones, Spanish ghosts: 'Transitional justice' and the legal shaping of memory after two modern conflicts	ERC-2009-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
BRSCDP-TEA	Bounded rationality and social concerns in decision processes: theory, experiments, and applications	ERC-2008-AdG, SH1	Advanced Grant
CAJS	The Christian appropriation of the Jewish scriptures: allegory, pauline exegesis, and the negotiation of religious identities	ERC-2007-StG, SH4	Starting Grant
CCC	Context, content, and compositionality	ERC-2008-AdG, SH4	Advanced Grant
CHANGE-POINT TESTS	New results on structural change tests: theory and applications	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
CIDAM	Conflict, identity and markets	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
CODEC	Consequences of demographic change	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
CONANX	Consumer culture in an age of anxiety: political and moral economies of food	ERC-2008-AdG, SH3	Advanced Grant
CONTACTS	Traces of contact: language contact studies and historical linguistics	ERC-2008-AdG, SH5	Advanced Grant
DCFM	Default and Collateral in Financial Markets	ERC-2009-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
DESTABLE	Destabilisation of sociotechnical regimes as the key to transitions towards sustainability	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
DIGIDEAS	Social and ethical aspects of digital identities. Towards a value sensitive identity management	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
DIVLAB	Consumption Work and Societal Divisions of Labour	ERC-2009-AdG, SH2	Advanced Grant
ELITES08	Culturally composite elites, regime changes and social crises in multi-ethnic and multi-confessional Eastern Europe. (The Carpathian basin and the Baltics in comparison - cc. 1900-1950)	ERC-2008-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
EMOTIONS	The social and cultural construction of emotions: the Greek paradigm	ERC-2008-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
ENTANGLED BALKANS	Balkan histories: shared, connected, entangled	ERC-2008-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
EUCONRES	A European Approach to Conflict Resolution? Institutional Learning and the ESDP	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
EUNACON	The European and National constitutional law project	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
EUROPUBLICISLAM	Islam in the making of a European public sphere	ERC-2008-AdG, SH5	Advanced Grant
FINGOVEU	Financial services governance in the European Union	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
FLUCTUATIONS	Research on economic fluctuations and globalization	ERC-2009-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
FORESIGHT	Do Forecasts matter? early warnings and the prevention of armed conflict	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant

GENMOD	Generative models of human cognition	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
GHG	The transformation of global health governance: competing worldviews and crises	ERC-2008-AdG, SH2	Advanced Grant
GMI	Genetics of mental illness	ERC-2008-AdG, SH4	Advanced Grant
GTAPCL	Game theory and applications in the presence of cognitive limitations	ERC-2008-AdG, SH1	Advanced Grant
HFPSL	HISTORY OF THE FRENCH POLITICAL SCIENCE LEXICON	ERC-2007-StG, SH4	Starting Grant
HOLY AND LAY	Holy writ & lay readers. A social history of vernacular bible translations in the middle ages	ERC-2007-StG, SH4	Starting Grant
ICARUS	Innovation for Climate chAnge mitigation: a study of energy R&d, its Uncertain effectiveness and Spillovers	ERC-2009-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
IFA DYNAMICS	Countries external balance sheets, dynamics of international adjustment and capital flows	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
IHKDC	Exiting long run poverty: the determinants of asset accumulation in developing countries	ERC-2009-AdG, SH1	Advanced Grant
ILM	Islamic law materialized: Arabic legal documents (8th to 15th century)	ERC-2008-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
INMARWEL	Market Integration and the Welfare of Europeans	ERC-2008-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
INSPIRE	Interhemispheric stimulation promotes reading: two brains are better than one	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
INSTITUTIONS	How do values influence the functioning of institutions and the effects of policies?	ERC-2008-AdG, SH1	Advanced Grant
INTELEG	The intellectual and material legacies of late medieval sephardic judaism: an interdisciplinary approach	ERC-2007-StG, SH5	Starting Grant
LABPOL	Labor markets, economic fluctuations, and monetary policy	ERC-2008-AdG, SH1	Advanced Grant
LATIN INTO HEBREW	Latin Philosophy into Hebrew: Intercultural Networks in 13th and 14th Century Europe	ERC-2007-STG, SH4	Starting Grant
MACROCLIMATE	Quantitative dynamic macroeconomic analysis of global climate change and inequality	ERC-2008-AdG, SH1	Advanced Grant
MIGRANT SOCIALITIES	New migrant socialities: ethnic club cultures in urban Europe	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
MJCBE	MAPPING THE JEWISH COMMUNITIES OF THE BYZANTINE EMPIRE	ERC-2009-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
MORALS	Towards a critical moral anthropology	ERC-2008-AdG, SH2	Advanced Grant
NAFU	Narrating futures	ERC-2008-AdG, SH5	Advanced Grant
NEGOTIATINGMODERNITY	Negotiating modernity : history of modern political thought in East-Central Europe	ERC-2007-StG, SH5	Starting Grant
NEUROSEMANTICS	Neurosemantics: the human brain as a meaning processor	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
ON THE OTHER HAND	On the other hand: the linguistic impact of having two symmetrical articulators in sign language	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant

ORGDESIGN	The foundation of organization design	ERC-2009-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
OSSMA	Multiple systems of spatial memory: their role in reasoning and action	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
PARTYDEMOCRACY	Re-conceptualizing party democracy	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
PEOD	Political economies of democratisation	ERC-2007-StG, SH2	Starting Grant
POR	Perception of other religions	ERC-2008-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
PREFERENCES	Understanding preferences: measurement, prevalence, determinants and consequences	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
PREVENTING_CONFLICTS	Understanding and preventing conflicts: on the causes of social conflicts, and alternative institutional designs for their prevention	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
PRODUCTION OF WORK	The production of work. Welfare, labour-market and the disputed boundaries of labour (1880-1938)	ERC-2007-StG, SH5	Starting Grant
RATIONALISM	Rediscovering theological rationalism in the medieval world of Islam	ERC-2008-AdG, SH5	Advanced Grant
REDIRECT	Reconciling Biodiversity and Development through Direct Payments for Conservation	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
RELIGION	A theory of religious organizations	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
SEALINKS	Bridging continents across the sea: Multi-disciplinary perspectives on the emergence of long-distance maritime contacts in prehistory	ERC-2007-StG, SH5	Starting Grant
SELF	Studying developmental, neural, cognitive and affective aspects of the self in humans	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
SHANYEFFECTIVECOURTS	The promise and limits of international courts and tribunals exploring the conditions for effective international adjudication	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
SIWTW	Social insurance and welfare-to-work programs: optimal design and structural evaluation	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
SORTING	The role of sorting for estimation, market design and development	ERC-2007-StG, SH1	Starting Grant
SPATIAL MEMORY	Neural correlates of spatial memory in children and adults	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
SPIN	Natural speech comprehension: comprehension of speech in noise	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
SSALT	Subjectivity and selfhood in the arabic and latin traditions	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
SSD	Social capital and enforcement of informal contracts in developing economies	ERC-2008-AdG, SH1	Advanced Grant
TEMPUS_G	Temporal enhancement of motor performance using sensory guides	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
TEXTILE	An iconology of the textile in art and architecture	ERC-2009-StG, SH5	Starting Grant
THE LAST SONG	The last song of the troubadours: Linguistic codification and construction of a literary canon in the Crown of Aragon (14th and 15th centuries)	ERC-2009-StG, SH5	Starting Grant

TRANH	Tarskis Revolution: A New History. Semantics and Axiomatics from Bolzano to Tarski against the background of the Classical Model of Science	ERC-2007-StG, SH3	Starting Grant
U4IA	(Euphoria): Emerging Urban Futures the Opportune Repertoires of Individual Adaptation	ERC-2008-AdG, SH3	Advanced Grant
URKEW	Useful and reliable knowledge in global histories of material progress in the East and the West	ERC-2008-AdG, SH6	Advanced Grant
WATERWORLDS	Waterworlds: natural environmental disasters and social resilience in anthropological perspective	ERC-2008-AdG, SH2	Advanced Grant

Annex 3: Questionnaire

This questionnaire is an opportunity to provide evidence on the way your research project has contributed or is now contributing to the EU2020 targets (or to the Lisbon strategy), as well as the other scientific and policy/political impacts. Furthermore, some additional qualitative data may be collected through phone calls or videoconference interviews among some of the projects which complete the questionnaire. As a result of the analysis of the data you all will provide us with, a number of projects will be selected as Success Stories and will be invited to be studied in depth. In addition, all projects which provide evidence of scientific, policy/political and/or social impacts (and may not be among the top ones) will be acknowledged in the corresponding IMPACT-EV Report to the European Commission (EC). Finally, as one of the interests of the EC is also to know the reasons for the lack of scientific, policy/political and/or social impact of some Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research projects, some research projects that have not reached the expected impact will be also identified both from the responded questionnaires and from the incomplete or non-responded cases (anonymity in these cases will be assured). Therefore, please make sure that you provide all relevant evidence as regards the achievement of any scientific, policy/political and social impacts as well as impact on the ERA, of your SSH research project.

HOW TO FILL IN THIS QUESTIONNAIRE

The aim of this questionnaire is to map the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research impact in the European Union (EU), and to select those projects which have been successful in achieving social, scientific and policy/political impact from their results, as well as in strengthening the European Research Area (ERA). To this end, we are asking your collaboration in order to identify the scientific, policy/political, the ERA and especially the social impact that your project has reached.

This questionnaire contains five sets of questions each corresponding to the assessment of your research project in the four specific areas of impact (social, scientific, policy/political and the impact on the European Research Area), plus a set of introductory questions.

We will need you to provide specific information on the project. It is possible that in some cases you do not have this information available and need to look for it. You might also have to ask your consortium.

Please, be as precise as possible in providing the data. In case you do not have the exact numbers of some of the quantitative data asked, please provide an approximation.

In some of the questions, you will find rows to fill in your data. In case you might need more rows than those provided, please note that you will be able to attach a file with additional information at the end of the questionnaire.

You will have the option of saving the unfinished questionnaire and retrieve it and continue it later. To do so, follow these steps:

- To save the survey you select the "Resume Later" option, at the end of the survey. The system will then ask you to create a username and a password

(which you will need to access the questionnaire later). To regain access, log in using the original link to the survey and your username and password: you will then be able to recover the data saved with the option "Load unfinished survey". You can also access directly the saved data through the new link that you received by email.

- The following times you access the questionnaire, you will not need to log in nor save the questionnaire using the "Resume Later" option. You will only need to use the link that you will find in the last email you received, and the data will be automatically saved when you click in the "next" or "previous" buttons.
- The duration of each session will be of 24 hours. Make sure that you save the data before the time ends. For that, you must select the "Resume Later" option at the end of the questionnaire.
- When you finish the questionnaire, do not forget to select "Submit" to send the data.

We ask you to submit your data no later than July 23rd 2014.

Thank you in advance for your collaboration.

For any technical question, please contact us: impact-ev@ub.edu

There are 126 questions in this survey

Introductory questions

1. Please, write the acronym and full title of the research project you coordinated or you are coordinating now:

2. Project website: _____
3. Please indicate the grant type: FP7 Cooperation / FP7 ERC Ideas / FP6 Priority 8 / FP6 Priority 7 / Non SSH projects / HERA / NORFACE / Other: _____
4. Please indicate the grant agreement number: _____
5. Please indicate the funding received from the EC [in €]: _____
6. Name of the principal investigator: _____
7. The principal investigator of the project was/is:
 Male Female
8. Host institution where the project was/is based: _____
9. How many institutions form/formed the project consortium?

10. How many researchers form/formed the project consortium (excluding people employed with the project funds)?
11. Project Duration: Duration of months:____; Start date:_____; End date:_____
12. What percentage of the consortium members were/are women? ____%
13. How many people were/are being directly employed with the project's funds?

14. Please, provide the total number of months these people were/are being employed:

15. What percentage of people employed in the project was/is women? ____%
16. Was/is your project oriented towards either the Lisbon 2010 strategy or Europe 2020 target goals?
 Lisbon 2010 Europe 2020 Neither
17. Do you consider that your project's achievement entailed an EU-added value (achievements that could not be achieved with research at the national or local levels)?
Yes / No / Don't know

[IF 17 YES]

18. Please, explain what has been the EU-added value of your project.
19. Please, explain how the findings achieved by your project were coherent with its main objective.
20. Was/is the gender dimension included in the project as a cross-cutting issue?
 Yes No
21. What percentage of the aims of the project explicitly includes the gender dimension? (e.g. if the project had 5 objectives and one was about gender, it would be 20%) ____%
22. Are you aware of other research projects aimed at similar objectives?
Yes / No / Don't know

[IF 22 YES]

23. Could you provide the name/s of this/these project/s?

Project title	Programme	Website

[IF 22 YES]

24. Did your research take these projects into account?
Yes / No / Don't know

SCIENTIFIC IMPACT

The following questions refer to the scientific impact of the outcomes derived from your research project (quality of SSH research publications, their citation dynamics and the way they are shared in scientific networks among other information).

25. Please list the publications derived from the project (including accepted publications currently in press):

For each type of publication please use the following categories and include the numbers of cites these references have:

- | | |
|---|-----------------------------------|
| A = peer-reviewed journal article | B = journal editorial |
| C = journal letter | D = published abstract in journal |
| E = book | F = book chapter |
| G = non-peer-reviewed journal article
published conference proceedings | H = |
| I = publicly available full report | J = others (please specify) |

Different sources can be used for identifying citation of your research outcomes: *Web of Science*, *Scopus*, *Google Scholar*, *Book Citation Index*. For each publication please include the information for all the sources possible.

Reference	Category	JCR Quartile	Cites in Web of Science	Cites in Scopus	Cites in Google Scholar	Cites in Book Citation Index

<p>i.e. Please, indicate the reference of the article in APA style if possible, including the DOI when available.</p>	A	1	3		3	
<p>i.e. Please, indicate the reference of the book in APA style if possible, including the DOI when available.</p>	E		-	-	-	-

26. During or as a result of the project, have you or any member of the team presented papers related to the project at international scientific conferences?

Yes No Don't know

[If 26 YES]

27. Can you list all of them, and specify if they were presented by invitation or by submission and acceptance?

Paper	Conference	Year	Invited/Submitted & accepted

28. Have you or any member of the project team organized or attended any international seminar related to the project?

Yes No

[If 28 YES]

29. Can you list all of them and specify whether they were organized by the project research team or by others?

Seminar	Year	Organization/Attendance

30. Have the project's findings, methodology or theoretical developments generated subsequent research led by members of the original project team?

Yes No Don't know

[If 30 YES]

31. Could you provide more details?

Project title	Programme	National level / International level

32. Are you aware of any significant ways in which your project has contributed to further research conducted by others?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

[If 32 YES]

33. Could you provide more details and evidence you have on this?

POLICY / POLITICAL IMPACT

The policy/political impact of SSH research can be shown through a set of indicators (quantitative and qualitative) and standards regarding policy attribution to SSH research. IMPACT-EV's goal is to identify whether research outcomes have an influence on policy reforms at different levels (EU, national or regional and local) or whether other types of policy/political impact are achieved.

				(Y/N)
i.e. Please, provide the title	RC	N	i.e. Please, provide supporting evidence	Y

36. Have civil society organizations (i.e. NGOs, companies, unions, trusts, professional bodies and other stakeholders) developed any programmes using your project results?

Yes No

[If 36 YES]

37. Could you please indicate the civil society organizations implementing any programmes using the contributions of your project?

I = International E = European N = National L = Local

If possible, please give details and supporting evidence of the use of your project's findings in the adoption of the programme's decision.

Please, indicate also if the particular programme took the gender dimension explicitly into account.

Organization	Level	Evidence	Gender dimension (Y/N)

i.e. Please, indicate the name	I	i.e. Please, provide supporting evidence	Y
--------------------------------	---	--	---

38. Have you or any member of the research team presented the results of the investigation in political forums?

Yes No

[If 38 YES]

39. Could you specify these instances?

Name	Level
i.e. Please, indicate the name	E

I = International

E = European

N = National

L = Local

40. If you wish, please describe any other policy/political impacts of the research project that you expect.

41. Would you like to add any information related to the policy/political impact of the project? (e.g. whether it has been mentioned or quoted in any policy document –report, recommendation, policy brief–, whether members of the consortium are or have been members of advisory committees influencing policy makers, or acted as policy advisors for the design or implementation of a policy or action based on the research project results, etc.)

SOCIAL IMPACT

The social impact of SSH research occurs when the published and disseminated results, which have generated transference, involve improvement in relation to the objectives that the European society is stating. In the case of Horizon 2020 these refer to the objectives of the EU2020 strategy. This section of the questionnaire tries to gather evidence of these improvements attributed to the results of your project.

Two examples of social impact:

An interdisciplinary research of Humanities had results with impact on several areas of education, economic development and tourism after some discoveries were made. The results had positive impact in a particular deprived rural area where the paleontology discoveries were made and beyond. For example, the area started to receive tourists and visits from schools creating new employment opportunities and generating high economic returns.

Another interdisciplinary research from the field of Social Science had an impact on schools and high schools showing how the implementation of the results of their research generates higher educational attainment for all students. Thus, its impact reduces school dropout and early school leaving.

42. Are you aware of any type of social impact derived from your project or do you expect it in regards to the following targets of **Europe 2020**? (please, choose all that apply).

Targets for the EU in 2020

Employment

Increasing employment of the population aged 20-64 (EU target = 75% employed)

Climate change and energy sustainability

<input type="checkbox"/> Reducing greenhouse gas emissions (EU target = by reducing greenhouse gas emissions 20% (or even 30%, if the conditions are right) lower than 1990) <input type="checkbox"/> Increasing the use of energy from renewables (EU target = reaching the 20%) <input type="checkbox"/> Increasing energy efficiency (EU target = 20% increase)
<p>R&D</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Increasing the rate of EU's GDP to be invested in R&D (EU target = reaching 3%)
<p>Education</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Reducing the rate of early school leavers (EU target = being below 10%) <input type="checkbox"/> Increasing the rate of 30-34-year-olds completing third level education (EU target = 40% at least)
<p>Fighting poverty & social exclusion</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Reducing the number of people in or at risk of poverty and social exclusion (EU target = 20 million less)
<input type="checkbox"/> None of the above

[IF 42= None of the above]

43. Could you indicate whether your project had impact on any or some of the following targets from the Lisbon 2010 strategy?

Lisbon 2010 structural indicators
<p>Employment</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing Long-term Employment <input type="checkbox"/> Increasing Employment rate
<input type="checkbox"/> Increasing Employment rate of older workers

<input type="checkbox"/> Reducing the dispersion of regional employment rates
<p>Climate change and energy sustainability</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Reducing greenhouse gas emissions <input type="checkbox"/> Reducing energy intensity of the economy
<input type="checkbox"/> Reducing the volume of freight transport
<p>Education</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Increasing the number of 20 to 24 year olds having completed at least upper secondary education
<p>Poverty</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Reducing the rate of people at-risk-of-poverty after social transfers
<input type="checkbox"/> None of the above

[The following questions will appear to those who marked YES at Employment, either regarding Europe 2020 or Lisbon Structural Indicators]

44. Has the project, as a result of its findings, already contributed to create employment for the following groups in society?

	YES	NO	Don't know
a. 20 - 64 year-olds			
b. Older workers (aged between 55 and 64)			

c. Long-term Unemployed (12 months or more)			
---	--	--	--

[Filter the following questions according to the above specific groups]

[If 44a YES]

45. Could you provide the approximate number of people (aged between 20 and 64) who participated in specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Number of people ____

Don't know

No specific action has been implemented based on the project's findings.

46. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%

Don't know

47. Could you provide the percentage of people (aged between 20 and 64) who found a job as a result of the implementation of these actions? ____%

Don't know

[For example, the findings from a Humanities project that discovered a relevant archaeological site, generated employment for the people living in the surroundings, in the museum, hotels, restaurants, etc.].

[For example, in the case of Social Sciences, the findings of a project contributed to create a competitive cooperative in a poor neighbourhood creating more than 100 jobs].

48. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%

Don't know

[If 44b YES]

49. Could you provide the approximate number of older workers (people aged between 55 and 64) who participated in specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Number of people ____

Don't know

No specific action has been implemented based on the project's findings

50. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%

Don't know

51. Could you provide the percentage of these older workers who found a job as a result of the implementation of these actions? ____%

__ Don't know

52. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%

__ Don't know

[If 44c YES]

53. Could you provide the approximate number of long-term unemployed people who participated in specific actions carried out by stakeholders based on your project's findings?

Number of people ____

__ Don't know

__ No specific action has been implemented based on the project's findings

54. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%

__ Don't know

55. Could you provide the percentage of these long-term unemployed people who found a job as a result of the implementation of these actions? ____%

__ Don't know

56. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%

__ Don't know

[End of filters from question 44]

57. If possible, could you please give any further details and supporting evidence, about the contribution of your research to achieving the social impact on employment?

58. If you wish, please describe any impact of your research project on employment expected in the following five years.

[The following questions will appear to those who indicated YES at **Climate change and energy sustainability**, either regarding Europe 2020 or Lisbon Structural Indicators]

59. Has the project, as the result of the implementation of its findings, already contributed to the following EU 2020 targets?

	YES	NO	Don't know
a. Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions			
b. Promoting the use of renewable energies			
c. Promoting energy efficiency			
d. Reducing the volume of freight transport			

[Filter the following questions according to the above specific targets]

[IF 59a YES]

60. What types of gases have been reduced? _____

61. Could you provide the approximate percentage of gas reduction generated by specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Yes, specify ____% Don't know

62. Could you provide any evidence on how this reduction is attributed to your project's findings?

Yes, specify _____ Don't know

[IF 59b YES]

63. What type of renewable energy has been promoted? _____

64. Could you provide the approximate percentage of the increase of the use of renewable energy generated by specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Yes, specify ____% Don't know

65. Could you provide any evidence on how this increase is attributed to your project's findings?

Yes, specify _____ Don't know

[If 59c YES]

66. Could you provide the approximate percentage of the increase on energy efficiency generated by specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Yes, specify _____ Don't know

67. Could you provide any evidence on how this increase on energy efficiency is attributed to your project's findings?

Yes, specify _____ Don't know

[If 59d YES]

68. Could you provide the approximate percentage of reduction of freight transport generated by specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project findings?

Yes, specify _____ Don't know

69. Could you provide any evidence on how this reduction of freight transport is attributed to your project's findings?

Yes, specify _____ Don't know

[End of filters from question 59]

70. Could you provide more details and supporting evidence, if possible, about the contribution of your research to combat the climate change and promote energy sustainability?

71. If you wish, please describe any other impacts of the research project on combating climate change and energy sustainability that you expect to happen in the following five years.

[The following questions will appear to those who marked YES **R&D**, regarding Europe 2020 targets]

72. Has the project, as the result of the implementation of its findings, already contributed to increase the rate of GDP in R&D?

Yes No Don't know

[If 72 YES]

73. Could you provide details and supporting evidence, if possible, about the contribution of your research to the increase of GDP in R&D?

[The following questions will appear to those who marked YES at **Education**, either at Europe 2020 or Lisbon Structural Indicators]

74. Has the project, as the result of the implementation of its findings, already contributed to the following aims?

	YES	NO	Don't know
a. Reducing of Early School leaving			
b. Reducing School Absenteeism			

c. Increasing Student Academic Achievement			
d. Preventing violence in schools			
e. Promoting Participation of family/community in schools			
f. Increasing the rate of 30-34 year-olds completing third-level education			

[Filter the following questions according to the above specific aims]
 [If 74a, 74b, 74c or 74d YES]

75. Could you provide the approximate number of students (excluding third-level education) who participated in specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Number of people ___

___ Don't know

___ No specific action has been implemented based on the project's findings.

76. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ___%

___ Don't know

[If 74a YES]

77. Could you provide the percentage of these students who continued studying after reaching lower secondary education level (Compulsory education), as a result of the implementation of these actions? ___%

___ Don't know

78. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ___%

___ Don't know

[If 74b YES]

79. Could you provide the percentage of students who reduced their absenteeism as a result of the implementation of these actions? ____%
__ Don't know

80. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%
__ Don't know

[IF 74c YES]

81. Could you provide the percentage of students who increased their academic achievement as a result of the implementation of these actions? ____% __ Don't know

82. From those, could you provide what percentage were women? ____%
__ Don't know

[If 74d YES]

83. Could you provide the percentage of reduction in students' victims of violence in schools as a result of the implementation of these actions? ____%
__ Don't know

84. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%
__ Don't know

[If 74e YES]

85. Could you provide the approximate number of family/community members participating in specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Number of people ____

__ Don't know

__ No specific action has been implemented based on the project's findings.

86. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%
__ Don't know

87. Could you provide the percentage of these family/community members who increased their participation in schools as a result of the implementation of these actions? ____%
__ Don't know

88. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%
__ Don't know

[If 74f YES]

89. Could you provide the approximate number of third-level education students participating in specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Number of people ___

___ Don't know

___ No specific action has been implemented as a result of the project's findings.

90. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ___%

___ Don't know

91. Could you provide the percentage of students who finished third level education as a result of the implementation of these actions? ___%

___ Don't know

92. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ___%

___ Don't know

[End of filters from question 74]

93. If possible could you please give any further details and supporting evidence about the contribution of your research to achieving the social impact in education?

94. If you wish, please describe any other impacts of the research project on early school leaving or completion of the higher education that you expect in the following five years.

[The following questions will appear to those who indicated YES at **Fighting poverty & social exclusion**, either regarding Europe 2020 or Lisbon Structural Indicators]

95. Has the project, as the result of the implementation of its findings, already contributed to the following aims?

	YES	NO	Don't know
a. Improving health of people in or at risk of poverty			
b. Reducing violence in marginalized areas			
c. Increasing active participation of people in or at risk of poverty in associations linked to social justice			
d. Promoting social entrepreneurship by people in or at risk of poverty			

[Filter the following questions according to the above specific aims]

[If 95a, 95b, 95c or 95d YES]

96. Could you provide the approximate number of people in or at risk of poverty participating in specific actions carried out by stakeholders as a result of your project's findings?

Number of people ____

__Don't know

__No specific action has been implemented based on the project's findings.

97. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ____%

__Don't know

[If 95a YES]

98. Could you provide the percentage of people in or at risk who improved their health condition as a result of the implementation of these actions? ___%

___ Don't know

99. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ___%

___ Don't know

[If 95b YES]

100. Could you provide the percentage of reduction of victims of violence in marginalized areas recorded as a result of the implementation of these actions? ___%

___ Don't know

101. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ___%

___ Don't know

[If 95c YES]

102. Could you provide the percentage of people in or at risk of poverty participating in associations linked to social justice as a result of the implementation of these actions? ___%

___ Don't know

103. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ___%

___ Don't know

[If 95d YES]

104. Could you provide the percentage of people in or at risk of poverty who is carrying out social entrepreneurship initiatives as a result of the implementation of these actions? ___%

___ Don't know

105. From those, could you provide the percentage of women? ___%

___ Don't know

[End of filters from question 95]

106. If possible could you please give any further details and supporting evidence, about the contribution of your research to achieving the social impact in the field of poverty and social exclusion?

107. If you wish, please describe any other impacts you expect in relation to the fight against poverty and social exclusion in the following five years.

For those who marked NO at the beginning (neither Europe 2020 nor LISBON 2010)

108. Could you indicate other overall societal targets and/or indicators to which your project has significantly contributed? Could you indicate in which ways have you been able to track this impact and/or measure it?

109. Could you provide the percentage of stakeholders satisfied with the intervention/s –in any area– based on your project's findings?

_____%
Don't know.

110. Could you say the percentage of stakeholders that have a positive perception of the intervention/s –in any area– based on your project's findings?

_____%
Don't know.

[IF 110 DIFFERENT FROM DON'T KNOW]

111. Could you provide this information for different groups of stakeholders?

End-users: ____%	Don't know.
Professionals: ____%	Don't know.
Other (Specify): ____%	Don't know.

112. Are the effects of the intervention/s based on your project's findings being sustained after the end of the project life span?

Yes / No / Don't know

[IF 112 YES]

113. If possible, could you provide supporting evidence about the sustainability of the impact?

EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

The next set of questions refers to the impact of your project on strengthening the European Research Area.

114. Has your project consortium established collaborations with:

	YES	NO
a. Other EU FP projects		
b. Other EU non FP projects?		
c. Other EU research organizations?		

[If 114a YES]

115. Regarding the collaborations with other EU FP projects:

With how many projects has the consortium collaborated? ___

Which percentage of the main researchers of these projects are women? %

[If 114b YES]

116. Regarding the collaborations with other EU non FP projects:

With how many projects has the consortium collaborated? ___

Which percentage of the main researchers of these projects are women? %

[If 114c YES]

117. Regarding the collaborations with the research organizations:

With how many research organizations has the consortium collaborated?

Which percentage of these organization's main responsables are women? %

118. Could you please list their level of action?

European: ___

National: ___

International (non European): ___

119. If possible, please give details of any established collaboration with other research projects and/or organizations (e.g. aim of the collaboration, kind of activities developed, etc.)

120. Have the Consortium members collaborated in new research projects or mobility of researchers after the project was finished?

Yes No Not applicable (the project is still in process)

121. Has your project consortium established collaborations with European Research Infrastructures such as Dariah, Clariah or Cessda?

Yes [Please, give details of this collaboration] _____
 No

122. Which percentage of the project's researchers had mobility opportunities as a result of the project?

Percentage of researchers (out of the total of researchers): __

[IF 122>0]

123. In the case the mobility opportunity was facilitated by funding received, please indicate the funding scheme.

Funding scheme	Number of researchers
e.g. Marie Curie	e.g. 2

124. Has participation in the research directly led to career advancement for any members of the project team?

Yes

No

[If 124 YES]

125. Could you specify the number? _____

Please, give details.

Number of team members	Changes in post	
	From	To
For example: 1	Senior Lecturer	Professor
For example: 2	PhD	Lecturer

126. Would you like to add any information related to the project impact on strengthening ERA?

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

You can attach here a file with additional information that you would like to provide and have not been able to do so in the previous sections. In addition, any information you would like to add or elaborate on could be provided also through interviews, so please feel free to contact us to this address: impact-ev@ub.edu

Please upload at most one file.

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey.

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR YOUR CONTRIBUTION TO ANALYSING THE SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES (SSH) RESEARCH IMPACT IN THE EU.

The IMPACT-EV Team

Annex 4: Bibliometric analysis

The scientific impact of last call FP6–FP7 SSH projects

An exploratory analysis

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Introduction

- An exploration of the available Programme scholarly output: “visibility study” (not comprehensive nor representative: on the other hand, well reflects the retrievable stock of scholarly output yielded by the projects under study)
- For modelling scientific impact a framework of citation analysis was applied with context-corrected citation measures (i.e. factors accounting for citedness differences other than impact, such as the research field or age of publications etc. have been incorporated)
- Preliminary analysis – Revisited via advanced models (science mapping) in WP4.

Materials and methods

The analysis was based on a project list provided by WP leader party, the list covering a collection of last SSH-related call FP6–FP7 projects. Based on a pruned list of project acronyms (acronyms for which a database query was deemed sufficiently reliable), the scholarly output attributable to this collection of projects has been harvested from the Web of Science databases. Publication records containing any of the acronyms in the “Funding text” database field were retrieved. (WoS and the related Thomson-services have been chosen for a variety of reasons, including the (indirect) availability of benchmarks required for the analysis as well as the implicit requirement for Programme outputs to be visible via high standard international citation indexes.)

The final collection of publications (subjected to analysis) comprised a total of 320 items, ranging over the period 2008-2014 (year of publication). For each item all citations found in the Web of Science Science Citation Index (SCI) and Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) databases were obtained (from the date of publication up to the date of analysis). Also, for journal-level benchmarking the SCI/SSCI Journal Citation Reports (JCR) data of the period 2008–2012 period were used.

The characterization of the sample in terms of scientific impact was undertaken upon the so-called “item-oriented” model, whereby each item (publication) is individually evaluated (given the diverse nature of publications in terms of research fields, age,

document type etc.), and sample-level measurements are drawn from appropriate statistics of item-level (and, therefore, context-sensitive) characteristics. The indicators applied for estimating scholarly impact of individual items were the following:

- **TC**: the number of retrieved citations (absolute citedness).
- **J-REF**, journal-level reference citation value: The average citation number received by all citable items in the publishing journal in the same year and the same citation period as the item in question.
- **IF-AVG**, the average impact factor of the publishing journal, calculated from all available data of the SCI/SSCI Journal Citation Reports (JCR) in the period 2008-2018. The average was calculated as the total number of citations divided by the total number of citable items, i.e. as a weighted average, the weights being the annual number of publications.
- **IF-CATS** is the weighted average impact factor of all subject categories (again, the weights being the total number of publications) into which the publishing journal was categorized by Thomson-Reuters (ISI).

Based on the above indicators, the following derivative measures could be proposed to characterize scientific impact (along with a related measure of publication quality):

- **PSI, "Publication Strategy Index"**: $IF-AVG/IF-CATS$ characterizes the citation prestige of the chosen journal within its own field(s) – also a proxy for publication quality of the paper or the “publishing strategy” behind;
- **JRCE, "Journal-based Relative Citation Eminence"**: $TC/J-REF$ characterizes the citation eminence or impact of a given paper in the publishing journal's standards;
- **SRCE, "Subfield-based Relative Citation Eminence"**: $PSI*JRCE$ characterizes the citation eminence/scientific impact of a given paper in the subfield's standards;

Based on the above system of citation indices, we have conducted an exploration of our sample of SSH project results, covering the following dimensions:

- A descriptive analysis of impact achieved by the SSH sample as such;
- a comparative analysis of the impact achieved by *contributing research fields* within the SSH sample;
- a comparative analysis of the impact achieved within *Programme Activity Areas* within the SSH sample.

In the majority of analyses the first two measures are applied (PSI, JRCE), as these two induces the third (SRCE), so that contrasting PSI and JRCE convey the respective contribution of the two factors to the publication's total scientific impact.

Results

1. The relative citation impact and quality of the total output

Fig.1 The distribution of the three measures (JRCE, PSI, SRCE) over the full publication record. Value of 1 represents the average (“expected value”) in the respective field/journal.

Fig.1. The publication strategy (PSI) vs. the relative citation impact (JCRE) of the full publication record.

2. Relative citation impact and quality–publication strategy by research fields

Fig. 2 Quality/publication strategy (PSI) in the output by research fields

Fig. 3 Relative citation impact (JRCE) in the output by research fields

Fig. 4 The publication strategy (PSI) vs. the relative citation impact (JRCE) by research fields within the full publication record. Central tendencies of field values (medians) and publication years (averages) are shown.

Abbreviations:

AgriEP: Agricultural Economics & Policy | Biotech: Biotechnology & Applied Microbiology | CellB: Cell Biology | CheA: Chemistry, Analytical | CheM: Chemistry, Medicinal | Comp: Computer Science, Interdisciplinary Applications | Econ: Economics | Energ: Energy & Fuels | EnvEng: Engineering, Environmental | EnvS: Environmental Studies | EnvSci: Environmental Sciences | GeoM: Geosciences, Multidisciplinary | Geri: Geriatrics & Gerontology | Gero: Gerontology | Health1: Health Policy & Services | Health2: Health Care Sciences & Services | Health3: Public, Environmental & Occupational Health | Immu: Immunology | InfoL: Information Science & Library Science | Med: Medicine, General & Internal | Meteo: Meteorology & Atmospheric Sciences | MolBio: Biochemistry & Molecular Biology | Multi: Multidisciplinary Sciences | Ocean: Oceanography | Onc: Oncology | Psy1: Psychiatry | Psy2: Psychology | SocBio: Social Sciences, Biomedical | Stat: Statistics & Probability | SubA: Substance Abuse

3. Relative citation impact and quality–publication strategy by FP Activity Areas

Fig. 5 Quality/publication strategy (PSI) in the output by Programme Activity Areas

Abbreviations:

Democ: Democracy in a supranational context | *Emerge*: Emerging needs | *EU-cit*: Reassessing European Union citizenship | *Finance*: Changing the role of the financial system to better serve economic, social and environmental objectives | *Food*: Economic, social and political conditions for satisfying the world food needs | *GlobalCh*: Analysis of the impacts of global changes | *Ineq*: Inequalities in society and their consequences | *Knowledge*: Understanding knowledge | *Labour*: The relations between the labour market, employment and welfare regimes | *Lstyle*: Addictions and lifestyles in contemporary European societies | *Migration*: Migration | *Other*: Other areas (no reference to specific Activity Area) | *Policy*: Improved ways of measuring both the potential for and impact of policies | *S&T*: Blue Sky Research on Emerging Issues Affecting European S&T | *SocEcon*: New socio-economic concepts, paradigm shift and territorial dynamics in a long term perspective | *Stats*: Specific statistical issues

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Fig. 6 Relative citation impact (JRCE) in the output by Programme Activity Areas

Abbreviations:

Democ: Democracy in a supranational context | *Emerge*: Emerging needs | *EU-cit*: Reassessing European Union citizenship | *Finance*: Changing the role of the financial system to better serve economic, social and environmental objectives | *Food*: Economic, social and political conditions for satisfying the world food needs | *GlobalCh*: Analysis of the impacts of global changes | *Ineq*: Inequalities in society and their consequences | *Knowledge*: Understanding knowledge | *Labour*: The relations between the labour market, employment and welfare regimes | *Lstyle*: Addictions and lifestyles in contemporary European societies | *Migration*: Migration | *Other*: Other areas (no reference to specific Activity Area) | *Policy*: Improved ways of measuring both the potential for and impact of policies | *S&T*: Blue Sky Research on Emerging Issues Affecting European S&T | *SocEcon*: New socio-economic concepts, paradigm shift and territorial dynamics in a long term perspective | *Stats*: Specific statistical issues

Fig. 7 The publication strategy (PSI) vs. the relative citation impact (JRCE) by Programme Activity Areas within the full publication record. Central tendencies of field values (medians) and publication years (averages) are shown.

Abbreviations:

Democ: Democracy in a supranational context | *Emerge*: Emerging needs | *EU-cit*: Reassessing European Union citizenship | *Finance*: Changing the role of the financial system to better serve economic, social and environmental objectives | *Food*: Economic, social and political conditions for satisfying the world food needs | *GlobalCh*: Analysis of the impacts of global changes | *Ineq*: Inequalities in society and their consequences | *Knowledge*: Understanding knowledge | *Labour*: The relations between the labour market, employment and welfare regimes | *Lstyle*: Additions and lifestyles in contemporary European societies | *Migration*: Migration | *Other*: Other areas (no reference to specific Activity Area) | *Policy*: Improved ways of measuring both the potential for and impact of policies | *S&T*: Blue Sky Research on Emerging Issues Affecting European S&T | *SocEcon*: New socio-economic concepts, paradigm shift and territorial dynamics in a long term perspective | *Stats*: Specific statistical issues

Discussion and conclusion

- Policy warning: scholarly output of FP-projects is not sufficiently transparent in terms of public, international visibility (no standard indication of funding sources in publication metadata).
- The visible scholarly output of most SSH-project is highly multidisciplinary, and, interestingly, dominated by non-SSH fields (collaborating disciplines at the project level). Although the “database effect” partially accounts for this phenomenon (uneven representation of scholarly domains in WoS), the analysis of scientific impact should rely on international citation databases (for both coverage and benchmarking), and FP-results, also within SSH fields, should also be available (visible) for an international audience. A further consequence is that the scientific impact analysis of SSH projects differs from that of the SSH scholarly output.
- The overall quality and impact of the Programme output is centered around the world average, that is, the expected values (given the underlying research fields and further contextual factors). The dispersion of publications along the scale is much greater in terms of relative (journal-based) citation impact than of quality: the top 25% ranges from about 2 to 4 times the world impact average. On the relational map of the two factors a hypothesis can be formed that the combination of higher quality and lower citation eminence (impact) is more characteristic than vice versa, irrespective of the publication age (impact is already age-corrected, measured in the same cohort, but the time elapsed since publication still matters).
- In terms of contributing fields, SSH projects tend to disseminate their results in journals with multidisciplinary profiles. Based upon the explorative results a hypothesis can be formed that contributing *social sciences* (economics, agricultural economics and policy, social sciences biomedical etc.) target a smaller set of often multidisciplinary and high quality journals to gain recognition (and achieve impact) – quality above average – but their citation impact is moderate (below world average) in the longer run. This especially applies to the multidisciplinary journals. On the other hand, it is the project output within hard sciences that still achieves higher citation eminence (impact), which imposes a special profile on SSH projects, and reinforces the above finding, that the impact assessment of SSH projects and that of the output of SSH research are on a different par. (An exception to both tendencies is Information and Library Science on the positive side, and General Medicine on the negative side, the latter with an especially broad dispersion of values.)
- In terms of Programme Activity Areas (AAs), the majority AAs produces a publication output with a citation impact around the world average (based on item-level characteristics). However, by a closer inspection of the joint distribution of PSI and JRCE values, a hypothesis-inducing pattern can also be discovered. Activity Areas directly addressing “overarching societal issues” (such as *Democ*, *Migration*, *SocEcon*, *Lstyle* etc.) tend to produce a high quality output (above average) in terms of publication strategy (PSI), while AAs focusing on more (e.g. sector-) specific issues (Knowledge, Policy, S&T)

are being positioned in lower levels of journal eminence – given a similar journal-based citation impact, the former AAs achieves a higher level of scholarly attention (by field standards).

Sources of data of the exploratory analysis

The following tables shows the assignment of project acronyms to publications

ID	ACRO	CALL	PY	JRCE ⁴¹	PSI ⁴²	SRCE ⁴³
1	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	2,76	0
2	GLOBAL-IQ	FP7-SSH-2010-2	2014	0	0,03	0
3	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2014	0	0,79	0
4	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2014	0	1,3	0
5	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2014	0	1,3	0
6	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0,39	0	0
7	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2014	0	3,32	0
8	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2014	0	0,56	0
9	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	1,06	0
10	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2014	0	0,78	0
11	INGINEUS	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	1,15	0
12	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2014	2,06	1,38	2,84
13	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	0,26	0
14	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	2,13	1,23	2,62
15	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2014	0	1,23	0
16	CAP-IRE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	1,08	0
17	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2014	0	0,96	0
18	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2014	0	1,14	0
19	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	0,87	0
20	INEQ	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	2014	0	0,65	0
21	BLUE-ETS	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2014	0	0,4	0
22	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	0,67	0
23	NA	NA	2014	0	1,01	0
24	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-	2014	12,5	0	0

⁴¹ "Journal-based Relative Citation Eminence" (JRCE): TC/J-REF characterizes the citation eminence of a given paper in the publishing journal's standards;

⁴² "Publication Strategy Index" (PSI): IF-AVG/IF-CATS characterizes the citation prestige of the chosen journal within its own field(s);

⁴³ "Subfield-based Relative Citation Eminence" (SRCE): PSI*JRCE characterizes the citation eminence of a given paper in the subfield's standards;

		4				
25	SERVPPIN	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	0,85	0
26	MOPACT	FP7-SSH-2012-1	2014	0	1,3	0
27	GILDED	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	0,88	0
28	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	2,38	1,06	2,52
29	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	300	2,64	792
30	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	100	2,64	264
31	WIOD	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	1,84	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
32	SHARELIFE	4	2014	1,33	1,84	2,45
33	NA	NA	2014	0	0,7	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
34	SHARELIFE	4	2014	13,16	1,27	16,71
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
35	INEQ	5	2014	0	0,65	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
36	SHARELIFE	4	2014	5,26	0,94	4,94
37	FESSUD	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2014	0	0,52	0
38	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2014	0	3,11	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
39	MICRO-DYN	4	2014	0	1,4	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
40	SHARELIFE	4	2014	0	0,6	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
41	SHARELIFE	4	2014	0	0,6	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
42	SHARELIFE	4	2014	0	0,65	0
43	WWWFOREUROPE	FP7-SSH-2011-1	2014	0	0	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
44	SHARELIFE	4	2014	3,12	1,04	3,24
45	GLOBAL-IQ	FP7-SSH-2010-2	2014	1,64	0,91	1,49
46	GLOBAL-IQ	FP7-SSH-2010-2	2014	1,88	1,14	2,14
47	FOODSECURE	FP7-SSH-2011-1	2014	2,5	1,14	2,85
48	SUSTAINCITY	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2014	0	0,7	0
49	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	1,18	0
50	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	11,33	0	0
51	WIOD	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	4,92	0,91	4,48
52	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	4,72	1,55	7,32
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
53	EUROOCCUPATIONS	5	2014	0	0,33	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
54	INEQ	5	2014	0	0,65	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
55	SHARELIFE	4	2014	3,33	0	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
56	INEQ	5	2014	5,26	0,96	5,05

57	NA	NA	2014	0	0,94	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
58	SHARELIFE	4	2014	11,11	1,14	12,67
59	EURO-JUSTIS	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	0,84	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
60	SHARELIFE	4	2014	0	1,23	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
61	INEQ	5	2014	0	0,66	0
62	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	1,89	1,55	2,93
63	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	0,91	0
64	INDICSER	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2014	0	0,82	0
65	TEPSIE	FP7-SSH-2011-2	2014	0	0,57	0
66	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	1,43	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
67	INEQ	5	2014	0	0	0
68	MOPACT	FP7-SSH-2012-1	2014	1,41	1,28	1,8
69	FOODSECURE	FP7-SSH-2011-1	2014	7,14	0,68	4,86
70	FOODSECURE	FP7-SSH-2011-1	2014	5,95	0,68	4,05
71	NA	NA	2014	7,14	0,68	4,86
72	NA	NA	2014	0	1,05	0
73	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	0	1,14	0
74	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	1,69	1,24	2,1
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
75	SHARELIFE	4	2014	3,7	0,47	1,74
76	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2014	1,39	1,09	1,52
77	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2014	0	1,09	0
78	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	0,67	0
79	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0,47	0,55	0,26
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
80	PROKNOW	5	2013	0	1,57	0
81	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0,41	1,06	0,43
82	LIPSE	FP7-SSH-2012-2	2013	0,19	1,7	0,32
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
83	SHARELIFE	4	2013	4,35	0,13	0,57
84	FOODSECURE	FP7-SSH-2011-1	2013	0	0,68	0
85	NA	NA	2013	5	0,21	1,05
86	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	1,74	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
87	SHARELIFE	4	2013	0	0,79	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
88	SHARELIFE	4	2013	0,61	1,31	0,8
89	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2013	1,92	1,13	2,17
90	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2013	0	0,38	0
91	FESSUD	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	0,2	0	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
92	SHARELIFE	4	2013	0,37	1,36	0,5

93	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	0	0,13	0
94	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	8,65	1,27	10,99
95	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	7,43	0,94	6,98
96	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	1,52	0
97	INCLUD-ED	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	0,54	0,65	0,35
98	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	1,57	2,62	4,11
99	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	1,33	0,36	0,48
100	NA	NA	2013	0	NA	NA
101	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	1,52	0
102	FOODSECURE	FP7-SSH-2011-1	2013	2,78	1,22	3,39
103	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	0	0
104	MOPACT	FP7-SSH-2012-1	2013	2,05	0,78	1,6
105	FOODSECURE	FP7-SSH-2011-1	2013	0,85	0,98	0,83
106	NA	NA	2013	0,89	1,05	0,93
107	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	2,42	0,81	1,96
108	SUSTAINCITY	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2013	0,45	1,71	0,77
109	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	2,24	0,92	2,06
110	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2013	0,81	1,16	0,94
111	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	0,36	0
112	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	NA	NA
113	NA	NA	2013	0,6	1,01	0,61
114	NA	NA	2013	0,18	2,07	0,37
115	GLOBAL-IQ	FP7-SSH-2010-2	2013	0,54	0,65	0,35
116	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	0,41	0,79	0,32
117	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2013	0,73	1,38	1,01
118	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	0,31	1,17	0,36
119	FESSUD	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	1,37	0	0
120	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0,56	0,62	0,35
121	EREP	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	2013	0	0,77	0
122	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	1,61	0,6	0,97
123	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2013	3,03	1,32	4
124	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	0,95	1,14	1,08
125	SCIFI-GLOW	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	1,03	1,15	1,18
126	NA	NA	2013	0	0,21	0
127	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2013	1,49	1,5	2,23
128	CAP-IRE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	2,22	0,3	0,67

		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
129	SHARELIFE	4	2013	4,86	1,19	5,78
130	NA	NA	2013	2,62	1,36	3,56
131	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0,81	0,81	0,66
132	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2013	0,66	1,84	1,21
133	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	3,28	1,3	4,26
134	NA	NA	2013	1,25	0,37	0,46
135	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0,9	1,23	1,11
136	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0,41	1,06	0,43
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
137	SHARELIFE	4	2013	2,13	0,39	0,83
138	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	1,68	0
139	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	1,23	0,35	0,43
140	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	1,23	0,35	0,43
141	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	1,23	0,35	0,43
142	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	3,7	0,35	1,29
143	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	1,23	0,35	0,43
144	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0	0,19	0
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
145	SHARELIFE	4	2013	0	0,25	0
146	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2013	0,65	1,18	0,77
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
147	INEQ	5	2013	2,88	0,75	2,16
148	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	4,5	0,68	3,06
149	RISQ	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2013	0,63	1,63	1,03
150	FESSUD	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2012	0,4	1,3	0,52
151	CAP-IRE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,56	0,91	0,51
152	GLOBAL-IQ	FP7-SSH-2010-2	2012	0,51	0,65	0,33
153	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,17	1,3	0,22
154	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	1,58	1,55	2,45
155	RISQ	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,63	0,51	0,32
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
156	SHARELIFE	4	2012	2,23	1,41	3,14
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
157	SHARELIFE	4	2012	0,58	0,78	0,45
158	SCIFI-GLOW	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0	1,36	0
159	EFIGE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	2,41	2,66	6,41
160	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,67	0,77	0,52
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
161	SHARELIFE	4	2012	0,45	1,36	0,61
162	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,49	1,48	0,73
163	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	1,67	0,67	1,12
164	CAP-IRE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,53	0,21	0,11
165	NA	NA	2012	1,98	1,18	2,34
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
166	SHARELIFE	4	2012	0,83	1,23	1,02

167	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,76	0,83	0,63
168	ALICE RAP	FP7-SSH-2010-1	2012	1,41	1,09	1,54
169	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	1,45	0,89	1,29
170	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2012	8,92	0,94	8,38
171	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2012	0,98	1,14	1,12
172	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2012	2,16	1,22	2,64
173	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2012	0,87	2,04	1,77
174	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2012	0,96	1,32	1,27
175	SHRINK SMART	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,87	1,16	1,01
176	MICROCON	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2012	0,22	1,06	0,23
177	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	4,95	0,68	3,37
178	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,39	0,89	0,35
179	CAP-IRE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	1	1,08	1,08
180	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2012	0,66	1,45	0,96
181	POLHIA	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	3,12	0,63	1,97
182	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	2,49	1,29	3,21
183	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	1,06	0,41	0,43
184	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2012	1,31	1,19	1,56
185	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,17	0,81	0,14
186	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2012	1,65	1,23	2,03
187	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,42	1,3	0,55
188	MICROCON	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2012	0,33	1,51	0,5
189	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,34	1,68	0,57
190	SHARELIFE	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2012	3,11	1,04	3,23
191	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	1,14	0,83	0,95
192	NA	NA	2012	0	0,31	0
193	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,33	1,7	0,56
194	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0	1,01	0
195	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2012	0,47	0,4	0,19
196	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	2,66	0,41	1,09
197	NA	NA	2012	0,3	1,01	0,3
198	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2012	0,84	1,32	1,11
199	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	2,49	0,53	1,32
200	MICROCON	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	2012	1	1,08	1,08
201	NA	NA	2012	1,34	0,84	1,13
202	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	3,37	0,67	2,26
203	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,59	0,81	0,48
204	NA	NA	2012	0,31	0,65	0,2

205	SUSTAINCITY	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2012	1,08	0,26	0,28
206	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,26	0,79	0,21
207	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	1,54	0,19	0,29
208	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,89	0,52	0,46
209	REMEDIE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	2,13	0,21	0,45
210	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	5,09	1,3	6,62
211	PASHMINA	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2012	2,78	0,91	2,53
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
212	EREP	5	2012	3,15	0,4	1,26
213	RISQ	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2012	0,88	0,59	0,52
214	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,24	1,79	0,43
215	CAP-IRE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,94	0,36	0,34
216	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,58	0,78	0,45
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
217	CIVICWEB	5	2011	1,76	0,44	0,77
218	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	2,01	4,16	8,36
219	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,15	1,52	1,75
220	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,22	1,29	1,57
221	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,95	1,06	2,07
222	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,71	0,67	1,15
223	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	2,47	0,67	1,65
224	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,76	0,67	0,51
225	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,48	0,2	0,1
226	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	2,79	0,45	1,26
227	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,83	1,04	1,9
228	POLHIA	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,41	0,87	0,36
229	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,44	0,87	1,25
230	CIT-PART	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,12	1,23	0,15
231	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,33	0,89	0,29
232	GILDED	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,22	2,02	0,44
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
233	EREP	5	2011	1,08	0,11	0,12
234	SCIFI-GLOW	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	3,22	1,15	3,7
235	INDICSER	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2011	0	1,02	0
236	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,98	1,4	2,77
237	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,24	0,91	0,22
238	IAREG	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,39	1,35	0,53
239	FINNOV	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,53	1,31	0,69
240	RISQ	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	4,02	0,33	1,33
241	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,41	0,89	0,36
242	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,52	0,96	0,5
243	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,61	1,27	0,77
244	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,35	1,3	0,45
245	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,48	0,25	0,12
246	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,52	1,3	1,98

247	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,18	0,67	0,79
248	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	2,18	1,07	2,33
249	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,08	1,36	0,11
250	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,57	1,36	0,78
251	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,69	0,17	0,12
252	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	0,53	0,52	0,28
253	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	1,14	0,89	1,01
254	SCIFI-GLOW	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2011	4,41	1,33	5,87
255	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	2,78	1,48	4,11
256	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,82	0,67	0,55
257	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,15	1,55	0,23
258	REMEDIE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,79	1,05	0,83
259	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	3,62	1,3	4,71
260	REMEDIE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,46	0,88	0,4
261	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	1,49	0,89	1,33
262	SCIFI-GLOW	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	2,18	1,15	2,51
263	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	1,75	0,81	1,42
264	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,37	0,49	0,18
265	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,93	0,87	0,81
266	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	1,59	1,59	2,53
267	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	1,76	1,09	1,92
268	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,71	1,4	0,99
269	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	3,16	0,95	3
270	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	1,42	1,48	2,1
271	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,38	1,38	0,52
272	ASSPRO CEE 2007	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,2	0,65	0,13
273	GILDED	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0	0,65	0
274	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,62	1,02	0,63
275	NA	NA	2010	0,75	1,17	0,88
276	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,61	1,48	0,9
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
277	MICROCON	4	2010	2,21	1,27	2,81
278	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	1,4	1,08	1,51
279	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	1,21	0,62	0,75
280	SCIFI-GLOW	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,65	1,15	0,75
281	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	3,72	0,52	1,93
		FP6-2004-CITIZENS-				
282	MICROCON	4	2010	0,2	7,7	1,54
283	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,78	0,89	0,69
284	REMEDIE	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	1,54	1,64	2,53
285	RISQ	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	0,94	0,71	0,67
286	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	3,4	1,3	4,42
287	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2010	3,14	1,18	3,71
288	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	1,97	0,64	1,26
289	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,5	0,95	0,48

290	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,17	1,65	0,28
291	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	1,26	0,89	1,12
292	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,16	1,24	0,2
293	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	2,08	1,09	2,27
294	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,92	1,84	1,69
295	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	1,55	1,27	1,97
296	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,81	1,19	0,96
297	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	4,22	1,68	7,09
298	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	1,13	0,5	0,56
299	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	1,11	0,89	0,99
300	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,33	1,21	0,4
301	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	1,11	0,89	0,99
302	INFU	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	1,01	0,55	0,56
303	TOLERACE	FP7-SSH-2009-A	2009	0,71	0,12	0,09
304	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,62	1,48	0,92
305	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,76	1,4	1,06
306	U-KNOW	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	2009	0,88	1,57	1,38
307	EREP	FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	2009	2,18	0,95	2,07
308	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,05	0,89	0,04
309	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	1,53	0,26	0,4
310	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,09	0,64	0,06
311	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2009	0,13	0,54	0,07
312	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2008	1,11	0,62	0,69
313	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2008	1,1	0,97	1,07
314	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2008	0,28	0,48	0,13
315	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2008	0,27	1,48	0,4
316	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2008	4,64	0,32	1,48
317	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2008	1,61	1,36	2,19
318	TRANS-NET	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2008	0,21	0,61	0,13
319	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2008	0,99	1,05	1,04
320	ENACT	FP7-SSH-2007-1	2001	0,56	1,12	0,63

For all items all citations found in the Web of Science Science Citation Index (SCI) and Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) databases (from the date of publication up to the date of analysis) were retrieved. For the analysis SCI/SSCI Journal Citation Reports (JCR) data of the period 2008–2012 period were used.

ID	SO ⁴⁴	PY ⁴⁵	TC ⁴⁶	J-REF ⁴⁷	AVG-IF ⁴⁸	IF-CATS ⁴⁹	Cat1 ⁵⁰	Cat1 F1	Cat2	Cat1 F2	Cat3	Cat1 F3	Cat4	Cat1 F4	Cat5	Cat1 F5	Cat6	Cat1 F6
1	ANGEWANDTE CHEMIE-INTERNATIONAL EDITION	2014	0	2,32	11,82	4,28	CHEMISTRY, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	4,28	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
2	ENVIRONMENT	2014	0	0,07	0,07	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
3	JOURNALS OF GERONTOLOGY SERIES B-PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES	2014	0	0,63	2,19	2,78	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
4	BMC MEDICINE	2014	0	0,81	5,36	4,13	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	4,13	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
5	BMC MEDICINE	2014	0	0,81	5,36	4,13	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	4,13	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
6	NATURE CLIMATE CHANGE	2014	1	2,56	0,00	2,46	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

⁴⁴ Source (name of the publication)

⁴⁵ Year of the publication

⁴⁶ Number of retrieved citations

⁴⁷ Average citation number received in the same citation period as the paper in question by all citable items published in the same journal in the same year.

⁴⁸ Average impact factors of the journals (IF-AVG) were calculated from all available data of the SCI/SSCI Journal Citation Reports (JCR) in the period 2008-2018. The average was calculated as the total number of citations divided by the total number of citable items, i.e. as a weighted average, the weights being the annual number of publications.

⁴⁹ Weighted average impact factor of all subject categories (again, the weights being the total number of publications) into which the journal was categorized by Thomson-Reuters (ISI).

⁵⁰ All next columns contain the subject categories of the journal (max. 6) together with the average impact factor (weighted by the total number of publications in each journal) of the categories.

								SCIENCES										
7	PLOS MEDICINE	2014	0	1,76	13,70	4,13	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	4,13	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
8	PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	0	0,29	1,22	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
9	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	0	0,42	2,29	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
10	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	0	0,43	1,69	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
11	SCIENTOMETRICS	2014	0	0,34	1,97	1,72	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
12	ADDICTION	2014	2	0,97	4,11	2,97	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
13	JOURNAL OF APPLIED SPECTROSCOPY	2014	0	0,04	0,47	1,80	SPECTROSCOPY	1,80	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
14	SOCIAL SCIENCE & MEDICINE	2014	1	0,47	2,64	2,14	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	1,84	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
15	SOCIAL SCIENCE & MEDICINE	2014	0	0,47	2,64	2,14	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	1,84	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

							HEALTH												
16	JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS	2014	0	0,16	1,20	1,11	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & POLICY	1,11		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
17	BMC PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	0	0,19	2,08	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
18	PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	2014	0	1,60	9,58	8,43	MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES	8,43		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
19	CANCER GENE THERAPY	2014	0	0,42	3,34	3,82	BIOTECHNOLOGY & APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY	2,99	GENETICS & HEREDITY	4,38	MEDICINE, RESEARCH & EXPERIMENTAL	3,29	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	
20	SCANDINAVIAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	0	0,15	1,42	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
21	STATISTICAL PAPERS	2014	0	0,24	0,46	1,15	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
22	HEALTH POLICY	2014	0	0,44	1,34	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
23	RAPID COMMUNICATIONS IN MASS SPECTROMETRY	2014	0	0,45	2,82	2,78	BIOCHEMICAL RESEARCH METHODS	3,38	CHEMISTRY, ANALYTICAL	2,70	SPECTROSCOPY	1,80		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
24	BMC ORAL HEALTH	2014	1	0,08	0,00	1,71	DENTISTRY, ORAL SURGERY & MEDICINE	1,71		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
25	TELECOMMUNICATIONS POLICY	2014	0	0,05	1,11	1,31	TELECOMMUNICATIONS	1,31		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
26	AGING CELL	2014	0	1,19	6,93	5,35	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	GERIATRICS &	2,94		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

									GERONTOLOGY										
27	ENERGY AND BUILDINGS	2014	0	0,57	1,84	2,09	CONSTRUCTION & BUILDING TECHNOLOGY	1,18	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81	ENGINEERING, CIVIL	1,51	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
28	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	1	0,42	2,29	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
29	TRENDS IN BIOTECHNOLOGY	2014	3	0,01	7,89	2,99	BIOTECHNOLOGY & APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY	2,99	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
30	TRENDS IN BIOTECHNOLOGY	2014	1	0,01	7,89	2,99	BIOTECHNOLOGY & APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY	2,99	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
31	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	2014	0	0,71	4,72	2,57	ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENTAL	2,88	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
32	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	1	0,75	4,00	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
33	NATURE COMMUNICATIONS	2014	0	1,57	5,92	8,43	MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES	8,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
34	JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN GERIATRICS SOCIETY	2014	5	0,38	3,73	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
35	SCANDINAVIAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	0	0,15	1,42	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
36	AGE AND AGEING	2014	2	0,38	2,77	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
37	PHYSICA A-STATISTICAL MECHANICS AND ITS	2014	0	0,55	1,46	2,81	PHYSICS, MULTIDISCIPLIN	2,81	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	

	APPLICATIONS						ARY											
38	BMJ-BRITISH MEDICAL JOURNAL	2014	0	0,58	12,85	4,13	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	4,13	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
39	SEPARATION AND PURIFICATION TECHNOLOGY	2014	0	0,45	2,66	1,90	ENGINEERING, CHEMICAL	1,90	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
40	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY INTERNATIONAL	2014	0	0,48	1,75	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
41	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY INTERNATIONAL	2014	0	0,48	1,75	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
42	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	0	0,28	1,61	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
43	NATURE CLIMATE CHANGE	2014	0	2,56	0,00	2,46	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
44	COMMUNITY DENTISTRY AND ORAL EPIDEMIOLOGY	2014	1	0,32	2,13	2,04	DENTISTRY, ORAL SURGERY & MEDICINE	1,71	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
45	ENERGY POLICY	2014	1	0,61	2,36	2,58	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
46	PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	2014	3	1,60	9,58	8,43	MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES	8,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
47	PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	2014	4	1,60	9,58	8,43	MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES	8,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
48	NETWORKS & SPATIAL ECONOMICS	2014	0	0,21	0,93	1,33	OPERATIONS RESEARCH & MANAGEMENT SCIENCE	1,43	TRANSPORTATION SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	1,04	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

49	BIRTH-ISSUES IN PERINATAL CARE	2014	0	0,23	2,18	1,85	NURSING	1,09	OBSTETRICS & GYNECOLOGY	2,25	PEDIATRICS	1,80	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
50	NATURE CLIMATE CHANGE	2014	29	2,56	0,00	2,46	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
51	ENERGY POLICY	2014	3	0,61	2,36	2,58	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
52	JOURNAL OF CLIMATE	2014	5	1,06	3,77	2,44	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
53	JOURNAL OF OFFICIAL STATISTICS	2014	0	0,06	0,38	1,15	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
54	STOCHASTIC ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND RISK ASSESSMENT	2014	0	0,56	1,38	2,11	ENGINEERING, CIVIL	1,51	ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENTAL	2,88	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15	WATER RESOURCES	1,73	0	0,00
55	BMC GERIATRICS	2014	1	0,30	0,00	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
56	BMC PUBLIC HEALTH	2014	1	0,19	2,08	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
57	SPECTROCHIMICA ACTA PART A-MOLECULAR AND BIOMOLECULAR SPECTROSCOPY	2014	0	0,90	1,70	1,80	SPECTROSCOPY	1,80	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
58	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF ORAL SCIENCES	2014	2	0,18	1,95	1,71	DENTISTRY, ORAL SURGERY & MEDICINE	1,71	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
59	JOURNAL OF THE ROYAL STATISTICAL SOCIETY SERIES C-APPLIED STATISTICS	2014	0	0,54	0,97	1,15	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
60	SOCIAL SCIENCE & MEDICINE	2014	0	0,47	2,64	2,14	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL	2,17	SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	1,84	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

							HEALTH													
61	JOURNAL OF URBAN HEALTH-BULLETIN OF THE NEW YORK ACADEMY OF MEDICINE	2014	0	0,18	2,06	3,12	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	4,13	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00		
62	JOURNAL OF CLIMATE	2014	2	1,06	3,77	2,44	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
63	ECOTOXICOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY	2014	0	0,44	2,28	2,51	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	TOXICOLOGY	2,65	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
64	OXFORD BULLETIN OF ECONOMICS AND STATISTICS	2014	0	0,20	0,94	1,15	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
65	INFORMATION SYSTEMS MANAGEMENT	2014	0	0,07	0,85	1,50	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INFORMATION SYSTEMS	1,50		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
66	BIOGEOSCIENCES	2014	0	0,54	3,52	2,46	ECOLOGY	2,89	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
67	BMJ OPEN	2014	0	0,28	0,00	4,13	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	4,13		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
68	AGEING RESEARCH REVIEWS	2014	2	1,42	6,83	5,35	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
69	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS	2014	6	0,84	0,75	1,11	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & POLICY	1,11		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
70	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS	2014	5	0,84	0,75	1,11	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & POLICY	1,11		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
71	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS	2014	6	0,84	0,75	1,11	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & POLICY	1,11		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
72	FORENSIC TOXICOLOGY	2014	0	0,70	2,77	2,65	TOXICOLOGY	2,65		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
73	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE	2014	0	0,42	2,81	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL	2,47		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	

	AND POLLUTION RESEARCH						L SCIENCES											
74	CHEMOSPHERE	2014	1	0,59	3,07	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
75	ARCHIVES OF GERONTOLOGY AND GERIATRICS	2014	1	0,27	1,39	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
76	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CANCER	2014	2	1,44	4,85	4,43	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
77	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CANCER	2014	0	1,44	4,85	4,43	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
78	HEALTH POLICY	2013	0	1,73	1,34	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
79	FITOTERAPIA	2013	1	2,11	1,54	2,78	CHEMISTRY, MEDICINAL	2,58	PHARMACOLOGY & PHARMACY	2,85	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
80	TECHNOVATION	2013	0	1,44	2,21	1,41	ENGINEERING, INDUSTRIAL	1,37	OPERATIONS RESEARCH & MANAGEMENT SCIENCE	1,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
81	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2013	1	2,45	2,29	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
82	CLIMATE DYNAMICS	2013	1	5,25	4,14	2,44	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
83	EUROPEAN GERIATRIC MEDICINE	2013	2	0,46	0,39	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
84	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS	2013	0	1,11	0,75	1,11	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & POLICY	1,11	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
85	IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INFORMATION AND SYSTEMS	2013	1	0,20	0,29	1,37	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INFORMATION SYSTEMS	1,50	COMPUTER SCIENCE, SOFTWARE ENGINEERING	1,21	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

86	MEDICAL MYCOLOGY	2013	0	2,76	2,18	1,25	MYCOLOGY	1,85	VETERINARY SCIENCES	1,18	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00		
87	JOURNALS OF GERONTOLOGY SERIES B- PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES	2013	0	2,43	2,19	2,78	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00		
88	ANNALS OF EPIDEMIOLOGY	2013	1	1,64	2,85	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
89	BIOMASS & BIOENERGY	2013	5	2,60	3,30	2,93	AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING	2,97	BIOTECHNOLOGY & APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY	2,99	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
90	JOURNAL OF THE TEXTILE INSTITUTE	2013	0	0,66	0,43	1,13	MATERIALS SCIENCE, TEXTILES	1,13		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
91	SCIENTIFIC REPORTS	2013	1	5,10	0,00	8,43	MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES	8,43		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
92	PLOS ONE	2013	1	2,67	4,22	3,10	BIOLOGY	3,10		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
93	EUROPEAN GERIATRIC MEDICINE	2013	0	0,46	0,39	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
94	JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN GERIATRICS SOCIETY	2013	16	1,85	3,73	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
95	AGE AND AGEING	2013	11	1,48	2,77	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
96	GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH LETTERS	2013	0	3,61	3,19	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
97	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUBLIC HEALTH	2013	1	1,84	1,61	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
98	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EPIDEMIOLOGY	2013	7	4,46	5,69	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL	2,17		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	

							HEALTH											
99	JOURNAL OF INCLUSION PHENOMENA AND MACROCYCLIC CHEMISTRY	2013	2	1,50	1,31	3,64	CHEMISTRY, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	4,28	CRYSTALLOGRAPHY	1,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
100	IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON CYBERNETICS	2013	0	3,90	#N/A	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A
101	GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH LETTERS	2013	0	3,61	3,19	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0
102	ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH LETTERS	2013	8	2,88	3,00	2,46	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
103	CURRENT STEM CELL RESEARCH & THERAPY	2013	0	2,72	0,00	5,95	CELL & TISSUE ENGINEERING	5,95		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0
104	AGING-US	2013	7	3,41	4,41	5,69	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0
105	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS	2013	1	1,17	1,09	1,11	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & POLICY	1,11		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0
106	FORENSIC TOXICOLOGY	2013	5	5,60	2,77	2,65	TOXICOLOGY	2,65		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0
107	BMC HEALTH SERVICES RESEARCH	2013	3	1,24	1,63	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0
108	TRANSPORTATION RESEARCH PART A-POLICY AND PRACTICE	2013	1	2,21	1,78	1,04	TRANSPORTATION SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	1,04		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0
109	CHIRALITY	2013	5	2,23	2,52	2,75	CHEMISTRY, ANALYTICAL	2,70	CHEMISTRY, MEDICINAL	2,58	CHEMISTRY, ORGANIC	2,73	PHARMACOLOGY & PHARMACY	2,85	0	0,00	0	0,00
110	ENVIRONMENTAL MODELLING & SOFTWARE	2013	4	4,94	2,77	2,39	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72	ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENTAL	2,88	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

111	JOURNAL OF INCLUSION PHENOMENA AND MACROCYCLIC CHEMISTRY	2013	0	1,50	1,31	3,64	CHEMISTRY, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	4,28	CRYSTALLOGRAPHY	1,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
112	OCEAN SCIENCE JOURNAL	2013	0	0,86	#N/A	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	####	#N/A	
113	ACS APPLIED MATERIALS & INTERFACES	2013	4	6,65	3,21	3,17	MATERIALS SCIENCE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,80	NANOSCIENCE & NANOTECHNOLOGY	4,24	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
114	ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY	2013	1	5,54	5,60	2,70	CHEMISTRY, ANALYTICAL	2,70		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
115	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUBLIC HEALTH	2013	1	1,84	1,61	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
116	JOURNALS OF GERONTOLOGY SERIES B- PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES	2013	1	2,43	2,19	2,78	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
117	GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY BIOENERGY	2013	3	4,11	3,27	2,37	AGRONOMY	1,48	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
118	JOURNAL OF AFFECTIVE DISORDERS	2013	1	3,21	3,51	3,00	CLINICAL NEUROLOGY	2,95	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
119	SCIENTIFIC REPORTS	2013	7	5,10	0,00	8,43	MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES	8,43		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
120	NATURAL HAZARDS	2013	1	1,80	1,29	2,08	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44		1,73	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
121	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON AUTONOMOUS AND ADAPTIVE SYSTEMS	2013	0	0,07	1,20	1,55	COMPUTER SCIENCE, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	1,82	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INFORMATION SYSTEMS	1,50		1,24	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
122	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY INTERNATIONAL	2013	3	1,86	1,75	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
123	CLIMATIC CHANGE	2013	8	2,64	3,24	2,46	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	

									SCIENCES											
124	DRUG AND ALCOHOL DEPENDENCE	2013	3	3,15	3,39	2,97	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00		
125	SCIENTOMETRICS	2013	2	1,94	1,97	1,72	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
126	IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INFORMATION AND SYSTEMS	2013	0	0,20	0,29	1,37	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INFORMATION SYSTEMS	1,50	COMPUTER SCIENCE, SOFTWARE ENGINEERING	1,21	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
127	OCCUPATIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL MEDICINE	2013	4	2,68	3,25	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
128	OUTLOOK ON AGRICULTURE	2013	1	0,45	0,43	1,43	AGRICULTURE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	1,43		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
129	SCANDINAVIAN JOURNAL OF WORK ENVIRONMENT & HEALTH	2013	18	3,70	2,59	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
130	PLOS ONE	2013	7	2,67	4,22	3,10	BIOLOGY	3,10		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
131	BMC HEALTH SERVICES RESEARCH	2013	1	1,24	1,63	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
132	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	2013	3	4,58	4,72	2,57	ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENTAL	2,88	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
133	JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL OCEANOGRAPHY	2013	10	3,05	2,36	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
134	OPTICAL ENGINEERING	2013	1	0,80	0,77	2,06	OPTICS	2,06		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	

135	SOCIAL SCIENCE & MEDICINE	2013	2	2,21	2,64	2,14	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	1,84	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00			
136	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2013	1	2,45	2,29	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00		
137	SWISS MEDICAL WEEKLY	2013	2	0,94	1,63	4,13	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	4,13		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00		
138	JOURNAL OF MATERIALS CHEMISTRY C	2013	0	5,71	5,22	3,11	CHEMISTRY, PHYSICAL	3,49	MATERIALS SCIENCE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,80	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
139	SUBSTANCE USE & MISUSE	2013	1	0,81	1,01	2,90	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
140	SUBSTANCE USE & MISUSE	2013	1	0,81	1,01	2,90	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
141	SUBSTANCE USE & MISUSE	2013	1	0,81	1,01	2,90	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
142	SUBSTANCE USE & MISUSE	2013	3	0,81	1,01	2,90	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
143	SUBSTANCE USE & MISUSE	2013	1	0,81	1,01	2,90	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
144	MACEDONIAN JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	2013	0	0,52	0,66	3,45	CHEMISTRY, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	4,28	ENGINEERING, CHEMICAL	1,90	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
145	JOURNAL OF MAPS	2013	0	1,11	0,56	2,21	GEOGRAPHY, PHYSICAL	2,21		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
146	FOOD AND CHEMICAL TOXICOLOGY	2013	2	3,07	2,47	2,10	FOOD SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	1,79	TOXICOLOGY	2,65	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
147	JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH POLICY	2013	3	1,04	1,59	2,13	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	

148	HUMAN IMMUNOLOGY	2013	5	1,11	2,84	4,20	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
149	JOURNAL OF THE ROYAL STATISTICAL SOCIETY SERIES A-STATISTICS IN SOCIETY	2013	1	1,59	1,88	1,15	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
150	PHYSICAL REVIEW E	2012	2	5,00	2,40	1,84	PHYSICS, FLUIDS & PLASMAS	2,02	PHYSICS, MATHEMATICAL	1,71	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
151	ENERGY POLICY	2012	3	5,39	2,36	2,58	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
152	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUBLIC HEALTH	2012	2	3,91	1,61	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
153	JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL OCEANOGRAPHY	2012	1	5,89	2,36	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
154	JOURNAL OF CLIMATE	2012	16	10,13	3,77	2,44	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
155	INTERNATIONAL STATISTICAL REVIEW	2012	1	1,59	0,59	1,15	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
156	JOURNAL OF EPIDEMIOLOGY AND COMMUNITY HEALTH	2012	9	4,04	3,07	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
157	INTERNATIONAL PSYCHOGERIATRICS	2012	2	3,44	2,33	2,97	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
158	PLOS ONE	2012	0	6,74	4,22	3,10	BIOLOGY	3,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
159	ECONOMETRICA	2012	16	6,63	3,38	1,27	MATHEMATICS, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,40	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
160	ACTA NEUROLOGICA SCANDINAVICA	2012	3	4,50	2,27	2,95	CLINICAL NEUROLOGY	2,95	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
161	PLOS ONE	2012	3	6,74	4,22	3,10	BIOLOGY	3,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
162	JOURNAL OF GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH-OCEANS	2012	3	6,11	3,10	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLIN	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

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163	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF LIPID SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	2012	5	2,99	1,49	2,21	FOOD SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	1,79	NUTRITION & DIETETICS	3,07	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
164	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND WORLD ECOLOGY	2012	2	3,77	0,60	2,89	ECOLOGY	2,89		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
165	IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INFORMATION FORENSICS AND SECURITY	2012	12	6,07	1,76	1,49	COMPUTER SCIENCE, THEORY & METHODS	1,24	ENGINEERING, ELECTRICAL & ELECTRONIC	1,53	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
166	SOCIAL SCIENCE & MEDICINE	2012	5	6,05	2,64	2,14	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	1,84	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
167	INORGANICA CHIMICA ACTA	2012	4	5,26	1,95	2,34	CHEMISTRY, INORGANIC & NUCLEAR	2,34		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
168	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CANCER	2012	14	9,96	4,85	4,43	ONCOLOGY	4,43		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
169	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2012	11	7,61	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
170	AGE AND AGEING	2012	24	2,69	2,77	2,94	GERIATRICS & GERONTOLOGY	2,94		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
171	WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT	2012	5	5,08	1,83	1,61	ENGINEERING, CIVIL	1,51	WATER RESOURCES	1,73	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
172	GLOBALIZATION AND HEALTH	2012	7	3,24	2,65	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
173	JOURNAL OF DENTAL RESEARCH	2012	7	8,06	3,48	1,71	DENTISTRY, ORAL SURGERY & MEDICINE	1,71		0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

174	CLIMATIC CHANGE	2012	8	8,30	3,24	2,46	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
175	ENVIRONMENTAL MODELLING & SOFTWARE	2012	8	9,19	2,77	2,39	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72	ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENTAL	2,88	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
176	ECONOMICS & HUMAN BIOLOGY	2012	1	4,45	2,31	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
177	HUMAN IMMUNOLOGY	2012	10	2,02	2,84	4,20	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
178	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2012	3	7,61	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
179	JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS	2012	2	2,00	1,20	1,11	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & POLICY	1,11	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
180	BIOENERGY RESEARCH	2012	4	6,08	3,73	2,58	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
181	KNOWLEDGE ENGINEERING REVIEW	2012	6	1,92	1,15	1,82	COMPUTER SCIENCE, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
182	TALANTA	2012	19	7,64	3,49	2,70	CHEMISTRY, ANALYTICAL	2,70	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
183	NATURAL PRODUCT COMMUNICATIONS	2012	2	1,88	0,87	2,11	CHEMISTRY, MEDICINAL	2,58	FOOD SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	1,79	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
184	ENERGY	2012	12	9,14	2,92	2,46	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81	THERMODYNAMICS	1,70	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
185	JOURNAL OF THE INTERNATIONAL NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL SOCIETY	2012	1	5,81	2,70	3,34	CLINICAL NEUROLOGY	2,95	NEUROSCIENCES	3,83	PSYCHIATRY	3,08	PSYCHOLOGY	2,67	0	0,00	0	0,00
186	SOCIAL SCIENCE & MEDICINE	2012	10	6,05	2,64	2,14	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL	2,17	SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	1,84	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

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187	JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL CHEMISTRY	2012	4	9,55	5,30	4,08	BIOCHEMISTRY & MOLECULAR BIOLOGY	4,08	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
188	AGRICULTURAL SYSTEMS	2012	2	6,08	2,16	1,43	AGRICULTURE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	1,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
189	PROGRESS IN OCEANOGRAPHY	2012	2	5,95	3,06	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
190	COMMUNITY DENTISTRY AND ORAL EPIDEMIOLOGY	2012	11	3,54	2,13	2,04	DENTISTRY, ORAL SURGERY & MEDICINE	1,71	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
191	INORGANICA CHIMICA ACTA	2012	6	5,26	1,95	2,34	CHEMISTRY, INORGANIC & NUCLEAR	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
192	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PATTERN RECOGNITION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	2012	0	0,37	0,57	1,82	COMPUTER SCIENCE, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
193	CLIMATE DYNAMICS	2012	3	9,05	4,14	2,44	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
194	BJU INTERNATIONAL	2012	0	3,15	2,87	2,83	UROLOGY & NEPHROLOGY	2,83	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
195	ENVIRONMENTAL MODELING & ASSESSMENT	2012	1	2,13	0,98	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
196	NATURAL PRODUCT COMMUNICATIONS	2012	5	1,88	0,87	2,11	CHEMISTRY, MEDICINAL	2,58	FOOD SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	1,79	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
197	ACS APPLIED MATERIALS & INTERFACES	2012	4	13,44	3,21	3,17	MATERIALS SCIENCE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,80	NANOSCIENCE & NANOTECHNOLOGY	4,24	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
198	CLIMATIC CHANGE	2012	7	8,30	3,24	2,46	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

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199	ANTONIE VAN LEEUWENHOEK INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF GENERAL AND MOLECULAR MICROBIOLOGY	2012	11	4,41	1,82	3,46	MICROBIOLOGY	3,46	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
200	JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS	2012	2	2,00	1,20	1,11	AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS & POLICY	1,11	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
201	JOURNAL OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL SCIENCE	2012	6	4,48	1,77	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
202	BIOPOLYMERS	2012	16	4,75	2,64	3,92	BIOCHEMISTRY & MOLECULAR BIOLOGY	4,08	BIOPHYSICS	3,25	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
203	BMC HEALTH SERVICES RESEARCH	2012	2	3,40	1,63	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
204	PATTERN RECOGNITION LETTERS	2012	1	3,27	1,19	1,82	COMPUTER SCIENCE, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
205	TRANSPORTATION RESEARCH RECORD	2012	1	0,93	0,37	1,42	ENGINEERING, CIVIL	1,51	TRANSPORTATION SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	1,04	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
206	OCEAN SCIENCE	2012	1	3,81	1,74	2,20	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
207	MACEDONIAN JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	2012	1	0,65	0,66	3,45	CHEMISTRY, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	4,28	ENGINEERING, CHEMICAL	1,90	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
208	JOURNAL OF COORDINATION CHEMISTRY	2012	4	4,50	1,22	2,34	CHEMISTRY, INORGANIC & NUCLEAR	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
209	NEW GENETICS AND SOCIETY	2012	3	1,41	0,76	3,59	BIOTECHNOLOGY & APPLIED	2,99	GENETICS & HEREDITY	4,38	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

							MICROBIOLOGY												
210	JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL OCEANOGRAPHY	2012	30	5,89	2,36	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
211	ENERGY POLICY	2012	15	5,39	2,36	2,58	ENERGY & FUELS	2,81		ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
212	SIMULATION-TRANSACTIONS OF THE SOCIETY FOR MODELING AND SIMULATION INTERNATIONAL	2012	4	1,27	0,61	1,52	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72		COMPUTER SCIENCE, SOFTWARE ENGINEERING	1,21	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
213	JOURNAL OF STATISTICAL PLANNING AND INFERENCE	2012	2	2,28	0,68	1,15	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
214	COMPOSITES SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	2011	3	12,59	2,70	1,51	MATERIALS SCIENCE, COMPOSITES	1,51	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
215	SPANISH JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH	2011	2	2,12	0,51	1,43	AGRICULTURE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	1,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
216	JOURNAL OF ATMOSPHERIC AND OCEANIC TECHNOLOGY	2011	3	5,21	1,78	2,29	ENGINEERING, OCEAN	0,96		METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
217	SOCIAL SCIENCE COMPUTER REVIEW	2011	9	5,11	0,75	1,72	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
218	NATURE GEOSCIENCE	2011	42	20,91	8,73	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
219	GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH LETTERS	2011	15	13,04	3,19	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
220	TALANTA	2011	13	10,69	3,49	2,70	CHEMISTRY, ANALYTICAL	2,70	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	
221	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2011	10	5,12	2,29	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL &	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	

							OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH													
222	HEALTH POLICY	2011	9	5,27	1,34	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	0	0,00	
223	HEALTH POLICY	2011	13	5,27	1,34	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	0	0,00	
224	HEALTH POLICY	2011	4	5,27	1,34	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	0	0,00	
225	JOURNAL OF MEDICINAL PLANTS RESEARCH	2011	1	2,09	0,51	2,58	CHEMISTRY, MEDICINAL	2,58		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	0	0,00	
226	JOURNAL OF MOLECULAR STRUCTURE	2011	14	5,02	1,58	3,49	CHEMISTRY, PHYSICAL	3,49		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	0	0,00	
227	POLYHEDRON	2011	11	6,00	1,96	1,88	CHEMISTRY, INORGANIC & NUCLEAR	2,34	CRYSTALLOGRAPHY	1,34		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	
228	ECOLOGICAL ECONOMICS	2011	3	7,36	2,27	2,62	ECOLOGY	2,89	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	
229	DYNAMICS OF ATMOSPHERES AND OCEANS	2011	7	4,86	1,92	2,21	GEOCHEMISTRY & GEOPHYSICS	2,22	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82		0	0,00		0	0,00	0	0,00
230	SOCIAL SCIENCE & MEDICINE	2011	1	8,50	2,64	2,14	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	SOCIAL SCIENCES, BIOMEDICAL	1,84		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	
231	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2011	4	12,19	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	
232	GLOBAL ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGE-HUMAN AND POLICY DIMENSIONS	2011	4	18,25	4,99	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	0	0,00	
233	ADVANCES IN COMPLEX SYSTEMS	2011	2	1,85	0,67	5,84	MATHEMATICS, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,40	MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES	8,43		0	0,00		0	0,00		0	0,00	

234	SCIENTOMETRICS	2011	23	7,14	1,97	1,72	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
235	JOURNAL OF HEALTH ECONOMICS	2011	0	6,38	2,05	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
236	DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTIONS	2011	44	22,17	3,96	2,83	BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION	2,55	ECOLOGY	2,89	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
237	JOURNAL OF LEUKOCYTE BIOLOGY	2011	3	12,26	4,52	4,97	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	HEMATOLOGY	4,89	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
238	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION ECONOMICS	2011	3	7,78	1,82	1,35	ENGINEERING, INDUSTRIAL	1,37	ENGINEERING, MANUFACTURING	1,22	OPERATIONS RESEARCH & MANAGEMENT SCIENCE	1,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
239	NEW JOURNAL OF PHYSICS	2011	6	11,24	3,67	2,81	PHYSICS, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,81	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
240	JOURNAL OF OFFICIAL STATISTICS	2011	7	1,74	0,38	1,15	STATISTICS & PROBABILITY	1,15	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
241	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2011	5	12,19	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
242	BMC PUBLIC HEALTH	2011	4	7,66	2,08	2,17	PUBLIC, ENVIRONMENTAL & OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	2,17	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
243	TRANSPLANTATION	2011	5	8,24	3,72	2,94	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	SURGERY	2,08	TRANSPLANTATION	2,79	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
244	JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL CHEMISTRY	2011	5	14,22	5,30	4,08	BIOCHEMISTRY & MOLECULAR BIOLOGY	4,08	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
245	IMMUNOTHERAPY	2011	2	4,17	1,03	4,20	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

246	JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL OCEANOGRAPHY	2011	14	9,22	2,36	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
247	PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS	2011	9	7,61	1,89	2,83	BIOCHEMICAL RESEARCH METHODS	3,38	CHEMISTRY, ANALYTICAL	2,70	PLANT SCIENCES	2,51	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
248	JOURNAL OF NATURAL PRODUCTS	2011	23	10,57	2,91	2,71	CHEMISTRY, MEDICINAL	2,58	PHARMACOLOGY & PHARMACY	2,85	PLANT SCIENCES	2,51	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
249	PLOS ONE	2011	1	12,30	4,22	3,10	BIOLOGY	3,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
250	PLOS ONE	2011	7	12,30	4,22	3,10	BIOLOGY	3,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
251	POLISH JOURNAL OF CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY	2011	1	1,44	0,34	1,98	CHEMISTRY, APPLIED	2,12	ENGINEERING, CHEMICAL	1,90	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
252	JOURNAL OF COORDINATION CHEMISTRY	2011	3	5,67	1,22	2,34	CHEMISTRY, INORGANIC & NUCLEAR	2,34	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
253	JOURNAL OF IMMUNOTHERAPY	2011	9	7,88	3,67	4,11	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	MEDICINE, RESEARCH & EXPERIMENTAL	3,29	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
254	JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR INFORMATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	2011	29	6,57	1,99	1,50	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INFORMATION SYSTEMS	1,50	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
255	JOURNAL OF GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH-OCEANS	2010	32	11,52	3,10	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
256	IMMUNOGENETICS	2010	8	9,81	2,87	4,28	GENETICS & HEREDITY	4,38	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
257	JOURNAL OF CLIMATE	2010	3	19,57	3,77	2,44	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
258	REPRODUCTIVE BIOMEDICINE ONLINE	2010	7	8,86	2,54	2,42	OBSTETRICS & GYNECOLOGY	2,25	REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY	2,79	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
259	JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL OCEANOGRAPHY	2010	50	13,81	2,36	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
260	REGENERATIVE MEDICINE	2010	4	8,76	2,82	3,22	CELL & TISSUE ENGINEERING	5,95	ENGINEERING, BIOMEDICAL	2,74	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
261	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY	2010	21	14,08	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

	IMMUNOTHERAPY																	
262	SCIENTOMETRICS	2010	20	9,18	1,97	1,72	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
263	BMC HEALTH SERVICES RESEARCH	2010	15	8,57	1,63	2,01	HEALTH CARE SCIENCES & SERVICES	2,01	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
264	CELL STRESS & CHAPERONES	2010	4	10,91	2,76	5,69	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
265	DYNAMICS OF ATMOSPHERES AND OCEANS	2010	7	7,53	1,92	2,21	GEOCHEMISTRY & GEOPHYSICS	2,22	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES	2,44	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
266	JOURNAL OF APPLIED ECOLOGY	2010	35	21,99	4,60	2,89	ECOLOGY	2,89	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
267	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CANCER	2010	47	26,71	4,85	4,43	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
268	JOURNAL OF IMMUNOLOGY	2010	16	22,45	5,86	4,20	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
269	DEEP-SEA RESEARCH PART II-TROPICAL STUDIES IN OCEANOGRAPHY	2010	40	12,66	1,72	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
270	FASEB JOURNAL	2010	32	22,49	6,48	4,37	BIOCHEMISTRY & MOLECULAR BIOLOGY	4,08	BIOLOGY	3,10	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
271	GLOBAL AND PLANETARY CHANGE	2010	5	13,24	2,92	2,12	GEOGRAPHY, PHYSICAL	2,21	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
272	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUBLIC HEALTH	2010	2	10,24	1,61	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
273	APPLIED PHYSICS A-MATERIALS SCIENCE & PROCESSING	2010	0	6,24	1,74	2,67	MATERIALS SCIENCE, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,80	PHYSICS, APPLIED	2,51	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
274	JOURNAL OF CELLULAR AND	2010	10	16,17	4,94	4,84	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	MEDICINE,	3,29	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

	MOLECULAR MEDICINE								RESEARCH & EXPERIMENTAL									
275	JOURNAL OF CLINICAL MICROBIOLOGY	2010	12	15,90	4,04	3,46	MICROBIOLOGY	3,46	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
276	JOURNAL OF GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH-OCEANS	2010	7	11,52	3,10	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
277	OCEANOGRAPHY	2010	25	11,33	2,32	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
278	BREAST CANCER RESEARCH AND TREATMENT	2010	22	15,74	4,78	4,43	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
279	JOURNAL OF OCEANOGRAPHY	2010	7	5,79	1,12	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
280	SCIENTOMETRICS	2010	6	9,18	1,97	1,72	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS	1,72	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
281	TISSUE ANTIGENS	2010	9	2,42	2,43	4,67	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	PATHOLOGY	2,74	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
282	LANCET	2010	32	161,81	31,81	4,13	MEDICINE, GENERAL & INTERNAL	4,13	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
283	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2010	11	14,08	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
284	HUMAN REPRODUCTION	2010	9	5,86	3,98	2,42	OBSTETRICS & GYNECOLOGY	2,25	REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY	2,79	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
285	JOURNAL OF OPTICAL COMMUNICATIONS AND NETWORKING	2010	6	6,37	1,22	1,71	COMPUTER SCIENCE, HARDWARE & ARCHITECTURE	1,21	COMPUTER SCIENCE, INFORMATION SYSTEMS	1,50	OPTICS	2,06	TELECOMMUNICATIONS	1,31	0	0,00	0	0,00
286	JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL OCEANOGRAPHY	2010	47	13,81	2,36	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
287	PHYTOCHEMISTRY	2010	41	13,04	2,95	2,51	PLANT SCIENCES	2,51	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
288	CYTOKINE	2009	7	3,55	2,86	4,49	BIOCHEMISTRY & MOLECULAR BIOLOGY	4,08	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

289	DEEP-SEA RESEARCH PART II-TOPICAL STUDIES IN OCEANOGRAPHY	2009	8	16,00	1,72	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
290	BIOSENSORS & BIOELECTRONICS	2009	5	29,41	5,35	3,24	BIOPHYSICS	3,25	BIOTECHNOLOGY & APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY	2,99	CHEMISTRY, ANALYTICAL	2,70	ELECTROCHEMISTRY	2,96	NANOSCIENCE & NANOTECHNOLOGY	4,24	0	0,00
291	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2009	25	19,78	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
292	CHEMOSPHERE	2009	3	18,77	3,07	2,47	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
293	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CANCER	2009	51	24,52	4,85	4,43	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
294	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	2009	25	27,07	4,72	2,57	ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENTAL	2,88	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	2,47	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
295	OCEANOGRAPHY	2009	35	22,53	2,32	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
296	BIOLOGY DIRECT	2009	19	23,35	3,69	3,10	BIOLOGY	3,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
297	PROGRESS IN OCEANOGRAPHY	2009	100	23,69	3,06	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
298	SCANDINAVIAN JOURNAL OF IMMUNOLOGY	2009	11	9,75	2,08	4,20	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
299	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2009	22	19,78	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
300	DEEP-SEA RESEARCH PART I-OCEANOGRAPHIC RESEARCH PAPERS	2009	5	15,05	2,21	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
301	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2009	22	19,78	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
302	JOURNAL OF AOAC INTERNATIONAL	2009	6	5,95	1,26	2,28	CHEMISTRY, ANALYTICAL	2,70	FOOD SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	1,79	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
303	ACM SIGPLAN NOTICES	2009	3	4,22	0,15	1,21	COMPUTER SCIENCE, SOFTWARE ENGINEERING	1,21	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

304	JOURNAL OF GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH-OCEANS	2009	10	16,21	3,10	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
305	JOURNAL OF IMMUNOLOGY	2009	22	28,78	5,86	4,20	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
306	TECHNOVATION	2009	15	17,11	2,21	1,41	ENGINEERING, INDUSTRIAL	1,37	OPERATIONS RESEARCH & MANAGEMENT SCIENCE	1,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
307	AUTONOMOUS AGENTS AND MULTI-AGENT SYSTEMS	2009	19	8,71	1,66	1,75	AUTOMATION & CONTROL SYSTEMS	1,64	COMPUTER SCIENCE, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
308	CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IMMUNOTHERAPY	2009	1	19,78	3,87	4,33	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	ONCOLOGY	4,43	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
309	EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF HISTOCHEMISTRY	2009	9	5,89	1,48	5,69	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
310	FRONTIERS IN BIOSCIENCE	2009	1	11,71	2,95	4,58	BIOCHEMISTRY & MOLECULAR BIOLOGY	4,08	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
311	MARINE GEODESY	2009	1	7,48	1,11	2,04	GEOCHEMISTRY & GEOPHYSICS	2,22	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	REMOTE SENSING	1,92	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
312	JOURNAL OF OCEANOGRAPHY	2008	9	8,08	1,12	1,82	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
313	VETERINARY AND COMPARATIVE ONCOLOGY	2008	9	8,18	1,15	1,18	VETERINARY SCIENCES	1,18	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
314	CELL AND TISSUE RESEARCH	2008	5	17,64	2,71	5,69	CELL BIOLOGY	5,69	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
315	JOURNAL OF GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH-OCEANS	2008	5	18,27	3,10	2,10	GEOSCIENCES, MULTIDISCIPLINARY	2,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
316	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF IMMUNOGENETICS	2008	23	4,96	1,36	4,28	GENETICS & HEREDITY	4,38	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
317	PLOS ONE	2008	47	29,13	4,22	3,10	BIOLOGY	3,10	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
318	CLINICAL AND VACCINE IMMUNOLOGY	2008	3	14,49	2,34	3,81	IMMUNOLOGY	4,20	INFECTIOUS DISEASES	3,60	MICROBIOLOGY	3,46	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
319	OCEAN MODELLING	2008	18	18,27	2,32	2,20	METEOROLOGY & ATMOSPHERIC	2,44	OCEANOGRAPHY	1,82	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

							SCIENCES											
320	MINI-REVIEWS IN MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY	2001	13	23,11	2,88	2,58	CHEMISTRY, MEDICINAL	2,58	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00

Bibliometric analysis based on project's reported data

Authors: CREA-UB

A bibliometric analysis has been conducted based on a sample of 47 projects. Those projects were primarily selected based on 2 criteria: 1) those having completed the IMPACT-EV questionnaire and reported scientific publications; 2) those having reported the greatest number of scientific publications in the reports available on SESAM. Therefore, it is not an exhaustive bibliometric analysis of EU funded SSH research but an analysis carried out based on a limited sample, and taking into account only the publications reported by the projects consortium.

For each individual publication reported, the research team searched for indicators of scientific impact: JCR quartile, number of cites in WoS, number of cites in Scopus, number of cites in Google Scholar, and whether books publishers are indexed in the Book Citation Index – Web of Science.

This bibliometric analysis points out some publication dynamics within EU funded SSH research. Additionally, this analysis has been the basis –along with data on participation in conferences and seminars and subsequent research generated– to evaluate the scientific impact of SSH EU funded research and to select the success stories with scientific impact (see Publications section of the Success Stories with scientific impact table).

Number and type of publications

Overall, 1056 publications were analysed which are distributed as shown in the graph according to the type of publication: peer-reviewed articles, books or book chapters and other publications.

Each project reported as an average 22,5 publications; the maximum number of publications by project is 123. Publications are distributed between projects according to the next chart; 18 projects report up to 10 publications (which is the most frequent situation), while 4 projects report more than 50 publications.

Out of the 594 articles published, 265 have been published in journals ranked in JCR, which is the 44,6%. Almost three quarters of these articles are published in the most relevant journals according to this ranking, as the 71% are published in journals in the first or second quartiles. As average, each project published 12,6 articles in peer reviewed journals, and 5,6 articles in JCR ranked journals.

As regards publications in books, projects had as average 4,2 books or book chapters; the maximum of this type of publication for a single project is 37. 71 out of the 191 publications in books are published in publishers indexed in the Book Citation Index – Web of Science, which is the 35,7% of the books and book chapters published.

Citation dynamics

196 publications have been cited in Web of Science (18,56% of all the publications), with an average number of 7,47 cites per publication. 234 have been cited in Scopus (22,15%), with an average number of 8,1 cites per publication. 460 have been cited in Google Scholar (43,56%), with an average number of 18,4 cites per publication. When citation is analysed at the project level, we find that projects have an average of 31,2 cites in Web of Science, and the maximum number of cites achieved by a project is 227. In the case of Scopus, the average number of cites is 40,5, and the maximum number of cites achieved is 253. In Google Scholar, the average number of cites is 180,23, and the maximum number of cites achieved is 1033.

Summary table

The following chart summarizes the information collected regarding the number and type of publications reported by the project sample, as well as the citations received.

	Funding Scheme	N Articles	Journal articles				Journal articles			Books / Chapter		Others
			Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Cites WOS	Cites Scopus	Cites Google Scholar	N books / Chapter	Book citation index	N other publ.
AIDA	FP7 ERC	20	2	6	1	1	15	41	139	13	11	43
ANTICORRP	FP7 CP-FP	6	5	0	0	1	1	0	18	2	0	2
ASPA	FP7 CP-FP	47	7	4	8	3	227	253	1033	5	1	0
ASPRO CEE 2007	FP7 CP-FP	41	6	6	8	0	89	115	358	0	0	0
CAP-IRE	FP7 CP-FP	10	7	1	0	1	9	11	21	0	0	0
CEDAR	FP7 CP-FP	7	0	7	0	0	10	0	25	1	0	0
CHANGING BEHAVIOUR	FP7 ENERGY	20	0	0	0	0	31	0	10	10	0	1
CONSENSUS	FP7 CP-FP	3	1	0	0	0	13	20	19	0	0	17
CONSENT	FP7 CP-FP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
DEMHOW	FP7 CP-FP	15	0	0	0	1	10	20	147	3	1	1
DERREG	FP7 CP-FP	26	1	0	0	0	14	0	10	7	6	
DIASPEACE	FP7 CP-FP	6	0	0	0	0	0	1	70	2	1	13
EFIGE	FP7 CP-IP	11	5	1	1	0	49	65	487	0	0	27
ELDIA	FP7 CP-FP	18	1	0	0	0	0	0	10	4	0	4
EUGRASP	FP7 CP-FP	5	1	0	0	0	3	3	23	16	2	102
EUMARGINS	FP7 CP-FP	11	0	4	2	0	20	25	129	2	1	1
FamiliesAndSocieties	FP7 CP-IP	12	3	7	0	0	5	5	83	1	0	0
FIDUCIA	FP7 CP-FP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
FINNOV	FP7 CP-FP	9	2	2	3	0	38	44	171	1	1	1
GEITONIES	FP7 CP-FP	9	0	1	0	1	3	3	20	3	0	0
GINI	FP7 CP-FP	36	12	8	2	1	64	97	404	7	7	0
GUSTO	FP7 CP-FP	24	1	4	6	1	114	199	524	8	6	0
HI-POD	FP7 CP-FP	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	493	1	0	0

HOLY AND LAY	FP7 ERC	3	0	0	0	0	1	3	1	7	0	0
ICATSEM	FP7 CP-FP	19	8	1	0	2	51	76	430	7	6	1
IME	FP7 CP-FP	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	12	5	7
INCLUD-ED	FP6 IP	73	1	18	8	12	99	141	833	4	2	0
INFU	FP7 CP-FP	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
INNOS&T	FP7 CP-FP	3	2	0	0	0	7	7	21	0	0	1
KNOWANDPOL	FP6 IP	7	1	1	0	1	88	171	299	2	0	0
LOCALISE	FP7 CP-FP	6	1	5	0	0	0	2	16	1	0	0
MELA	FP7 CP-FP	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	37	10	0
MERCURY	FP7 CP-FP	11	1	0	0	0	29	9	135	13	8	0
MULTILINKS	FP7 CP-FP	20	1	6	1	0	78	69	403	0	0	
PICK-ME	FP7 CP-FP	6	2	1	2	0	1	2	14	4	0	0
POLHIA	FP7 CP-FP	23	1	16	3	0	175	212	790	0	0	0
POLINARES	FP7 CP-FP	2	0	1	0	0	1	7	14	4	1	0
REMEDIE	FP7 CP-FP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
SELUSI	FP7 CP-FP	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	18
SIMPATIC	FP7 CP-FP	3	1	1	0	0	8	11	62	1	1	4
SUSTAINCITY	FP7 CP-FP	2	1	0	0	0	8	10	40	0	0	18
SYRTO	FP7	6	1	1	2	0	3	3	55	0	0	0
TAP	HERA	18	0	0	0	0	2	4	10	4	0	0
TENLAW	FP7 CP-FP	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
TRANSLEARN	FP6 STREP	11	3	1	1	0	139	194	465	6	0	
WIOD	FP7 CP-IP	13	7	1	0	0	56	75	619	0	0	0
WWWforEurope	FP7 CP-FP	9	0	0	0	2	4	6	34	1	0	0
TOTAL		594	85	104	48	28	1465	1904	8471	199	71	263

Conclusions

- Publications in peer-reviewed journals are the most frequent type of publication, reaching more than half of the items analysed.
- Publications in JCR journals represent near half of the articles published. In these cases, articles tend to be published in journals in the 1st and 2nd quartiles.
- Book publications by indexed publishers –in the Book Citation Index– are less frequent, approximately one third.
- Publications derived from the projects are slightly more likely to be cited in Scopus than in Web of Science (1,2 times more cites), and more in Google Scholar than in Scopus (1,9 times more cites).
- The number of cites received per publication in Google Scholar is more than twice than those received in the Web of Science or Scopus. The number of cites received by the publications of a given project is 1,3 times higher in Scopus than in the Web of Science, and 4,5 times higher in Google Scholar than in Scopus. These data suggest that tools which provide open access to scientific publications contribute to make more visible such publications.

Articles analysed:

Publication							
Reference	Journal articles				Books / Chapter	Others	
	JCR Quartile	Cites WOS	Cites Scopus	Cites Google Scholar	Publisher Indexed (yes=1; no=0)		
Bartolini F., Viaggi D. (2012): Analysis of the policy scenario effects on adoption of energy production/energy crops on the farm. a case study in emilia romagna (Italy), Energy policy, 51, 454 – 464.	1	3	3	7			
Lange, A., Piorr, A., Siebert, R. & Zasada, I., 2013. Spatial differentiation of farm diversification: How rural attractiveness and vicinity to cities determine farm households response to the CAP. Land Use Policy 31(1), 136-144.	1	1	2	7			
Raggi M., Sardonini L., Viaggi D. (2013): The effects of the common agricultural policy on exit strategies and land re-allocation, Land Use Policy,31, 114-125.	1	3	3	11			
Bartolini, F., Viaggi, D. (2013): The common agricultural policy and the determinants of changes in EU farm size. Land Use Policy, 31, 126-135.	1	6	6	23			
Viaggi D., Raggi M. Bartolini F., and Sardonini L. (2013). Spatial patterns of change in agriculture and the role of the Common Agricultural Policy, Outlook on Agriculture, 42 (1), 25–32.	4	1	1	2			
Roberts, D., Majewski E., & Sulewski P. (2012) Farm household interactions with local economies: A comparison of two EU case study areas. Land Use Policy DOI: 10.1016/j.landusepol.2011.09.012	1			3			
Giannoccaro, G., & Berbel, J. (2013). Farmers' stated preference analysis towards resources use under alternative policy scenarios. Land Use Policy, 31, 145-155.	1	1	1	2			
Was A., Majewski E., Cyganski L., Bartolini F., Floridi M., Viaggi D. (2011): Assessment of economic effects of innovations in automatic milking systems in Podlaskie region (Poland) with the use of real option approach., Acta Scientiarum Polonorum-Oeconomia, vol. 10 (2), pp. 107 - 120.	0	0		2			
Latruffe, L., Dupuy, A., Desjeux, Y. (2013). What would farmers' strategies be in a no-CAP situation? An illustration from two regions in France. Journal of Rural Studies, 32, 10-25	2		1	2			
B. Manos, T. Bournaris, P. Hatzinikolaou, J. Berbel, D. Nikolov (2013) 'Effects of CAP policy on farm household behaviour and social sustainability', Land Use Policy, 31 (2013) 166– 181	1		2	5			
TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	10				0	0	
CHANGING BEHAVIOUR							
Hodson, M., & Marvin, S. (2009). 'Urban ecological security': a new urban paradigm?. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research, 33(1), 193-215.	0		0	129			
Hodson, M., & Marvin, S. (2009). Cities mediating technological transitions: understanding visions, intermediation and consequences. Technology Analysis & Strategic Management, 21(4), 515-534.	3		38	59			
Heiskanen, E., Johnson, M., & Vadovics, E. (2013). Learning about and involving users in energy saving on the local level. Journal of Cleaner Production, 48, 241-249.	1	2	0	5			
Heiskanen, E., & Lovio, R. (2010). User- Producer interaction in housing energy innovations. Journal of Industrial Ecology, 14(1), 91-102.	2	11	13	21			
Heiskanen, E., Johnson, M., Robinson, S., Vadovics, E., & Saastamoinen, M. (2010). Low-carbon communities as a context for individual behavioural change. Energy Policy, 38(12), 7586-7595.	2	32	0	113			
Hodson, M., & Marvin, S. (2010). Can cities shape socio-technical transitions and how would we know if they were?. Research Policy, 39(4), 477-485.	1	65	0	145			
Breukers, S. C., Heiskanen, E., Brohmann, B., Mourik, R. M.,	1	6	14	21			

	& Feenstra, C. F. J. (2011). Connecting research to practice to improve energy demand-side management (DSM). <i>Energy</i> , 36(4), 2176-2185.						
	Hodson, M., & Marvin, S. (2010). Urbanism in the anthropocene: Ecological urbanism or premium ecological enclaves?. <i>City</i> , 14(3), 298-313.	0		0	48		
	Backhaus, J. (2010). Intermediaries as innovating actors in the transition to a sustainable energy system. <i>Central European Journal of Public Policy</i> , (1), 86-109.	0		0	3		
	Heiskanen, E., & Hodson, M. (2009). A rose by any other name? New contexts and players in European energy efficiency programmes. <i>eceee Summer Study Proceedings</i>		31		10		1
	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	9				0	1

AIDA: Architectural design In Dialogue with disAbility	Elsen, C., Heylighen, A. (2014). Representations of sensory experiences in the early phases of architectural design: there is more than meets the eye. <i>Journal of Design Research</i> (in print)	0		0			
	Van Steenwinkel, I., Van Audenhove, C., Heylighen, A. (2014). Mary's Little Worlds. Changing Person-Space Relationships when Living with Dementia. <i>Qualitative Health Research</i> , 24 (8), 1023-1032.	3	0	0			
	Heylighen, A., Nijs, G. (2014). Designing in the absence of sight: Design cognition re-articulated. <i>Design Studies</i> , 35, 113-132.	2	0	1	2		
	Heylighen, A., Herzsens, J. (2014). Designerly ways of not knowing: What designers can learn about space from people who are blind. <i>Journal of Urban Design</i> , 19 (3), 285-301.	0	0	0	1		
	Heylighen, A. (2014). About the nature of design in universal design. <i>Disability and Rehabilitation</i> , 36 (16), 1360-1368.	2	0	0	1		
	Wastiels, L., Schifferstein, H., Wouters, I., Heylighen, A. (2013). Touching materials visually: About the dominance of vision in building material assessment. <i>International Journal of Design</i> , 7 (2), 31-41.	2	0	2	1		
	Heylighen, A., Bianchin, M. (2013). How does inclusive design relate to good design?. <i>Design Studies</i> , 34, 93-110.	2	2	0	9		
	Heylighen, A., Van Doren, C., Vermeersch, P. (2013). Enriching our understanding of architecture through disability experience. <i>Open House International</i> , 38 (1), 7-19.	4	1	2	2		
	Herzsens, J., Heylighen, A. (2012). Blind Photographers: An (Im)material Quest into the Spatial Experiences of Children Born Blind. <i>Children, Youth and Environments</i> , 22 (1), 99-124.	0		0	1		
	Heylighen, A., Strickfaden, M. (2012). Materiality: Designing for more sense/s. <i>Space & Culture</i> , 15 (3), 180-185.	2		0	1		
	Baumers, S., Heylighen, A. (2015) Capturing Experience: An Autistic's Approach to Designing Space, <i>The Design Journal</i>	0	0	0	0		
	Nijs, G., Heylighen, A. (2015) Turning disability experience into expertise in assessing building accessibility: A contribution to articulating disability epistemology. <i>Alter</i>	0	0	0	0		
	Van der Linden, V., Annemans, M., Heylighen, A. (2015) Architects' approaches of healing environment in designing a Maggie's Cancer Caring Centre, <i>The Design Journal</i>	0	0	0	0		
	Wastiels, L., Schifferstein, H., Wouters, I., Heylighen, A. (2013). Touching materials visually: About the dominance of vision in building material assessment. <i>International Journal of Design</i> 7(2):31-41	2	0	2	1		
	Nijs, G., Daems, A. (2012). And what if the tangible were not? And vice versa. <i>Space & Culture</i> 2012 15:186-197.	0	0	0	3		
	Van Steenwinkel, I., Baumers, S., Heylighen, A. (2012) Home in later life: A framework for the architecture of home environments. <i>Home Cultures</i> 9 (2), 195-218.	0	0	0	3		
	Wastiels, L., Schifferstein, H., Heylighen, A., Wouters, I. (2012). Relating material experience to technical parameters: A case study on visual and tactile warmth perception of indoor wall materials. <i>Building and Environment</i> , 49, 359-367.[abstract]	1	4	4	7		
	Wastiels, L., Schifferstein, H., Heylighen, A., Wouters, I. (2012). Red or rough, what makes materials warmer?. <i>Materials & Design</i> , Volume 42, December 2012,	1	2	3	3		
	Coomans, K., De Smet, H., Heylighen, A. (2011). In Search of a Future for Large-Scale Care Homes in Flanders. <i>Journal of Housing for the Elderly</i> , 25 (4) 329-351.	0	0	0	0		

Heylighen, A. (2008). Sustainable and inclusive design: a matter of knowledge?. <i>Local Environment</i> , 13 (6), 531-540.	0	0	13	19		
Annemans, M., Karanastasi, E., Poponcini, M., Heylighen, A. (2015). A Maggie's Centre for Leuven: Shaping Places of Care by Empathizing with Patients and Carers. In: Jencks C. (Ed.), <i>The Architecture of Hope</i> , Frances Lincoln.					0	
Heylighen, A. (2015). Enacting the socio-material: Matter and meaning reconfigured through disability experience. In: Lindsay G., Morhayim L. (Eds.), <i>The Death and Life of Social Factors in Environmental Design</i> , Chapt. 4. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.					0	
Annemans, M., Heylighen, A. (2014). De beleving van de ruimte vanuit bed. In: van Hoof J., Wouters E. (Eds.), <i>Het verpleeghuis van de toekomst is (een) thuis</i> , Chapt. 37. Houten: Bohn Stafleu van Loghum (Springer Media), 139-140.					1	
Annemans, M., Van Audenhove, C., Vermolen, H., Heylighen, A. (2014). Being Transported into the Unknown: How Patients Experience the Route to the Operation Room. In: Langdon P. et al. (Eds) <i>Inclusive Designing. Joining Usability, Accessibility and Inclusion</i> . London: Springer, pp.189-200					1	
Annemans, M., Karanastasi, E., Heylighen, A. (2014). From designing for the patient to designing for a person. In: Langdon P. et al. (Eds) <i>Inclusive Designing. Joining Usability, Accessibility and Inclusion</i> . London: Springer, pp. 131-141					1	
Baumers, S., Heylighen, A. (2014). Performing their Version of the House. Interpretations of an Architectural Response to Autism. In: Maudlin D., Vellinga M. (Eds.), <i>Consuming Architecture: On the Occupation, Appropriation and Interpretation of Buildings</i> , Chapt. 4 Routledge, pp.57-69.					1	
Kinnaer, M., Baumers, S., Heylighen A. (2014). How do people with autism (like to) live? In: Langdon P. et al. (Eds) <i>Inclusive Designing. Joining Usability, Accessibility and Inclusion</i> . London: Springer, pp.175-185					1	
Langdon, P., Lazar, J., Heylighen, A., Dong, H. (Eds) (2014). <i>Inclusive Designing: Joining Usability, Accessibility, and Inclusion</i> . London: Springer.					1	
Annemans, M., Van Audenhove, C., Vermolen, H., Heylighen, A. (2012) Hospital Reality from A Lying Perspective: Exploring a Sensory Research Approach. In: Langdon P., Clarkson P., Robinson P., Lazar J., Heylighen A. (Eds.), <i>Designing Inclusive Systems</i> , Chapt. 1 (pp. 3-12). London: Springer-Verlag					1	
Heylighen, A. (2012) Inclusivity of built heritage as a matter of concern: A field experiment. In: Langdon P., Clarkson P., Robinson P., Lazar J., Heylighen A. (Eds.), <i>Designing Inclusive Systems</i> , Chapt. 21 (pp. 207-216). London: Springer-Verlag.					1	
Langdon, P., Clarkson, J.P., Robinson, P., Lazar, J., Heylighen, A. (eds.) (2012) <i>Designing Inclusive Systems</i> . London: Springer-Verlag.					1	
Van Steenwinkel, I., Van Audenhove, C., Heylighen, A. (2012) Spatial Clues for Orientation: Architectural Design Meets People with Dementia. In: Langdon P., Clarkson P., Robinson P., Lazar J., Heylighen A. (Eds.), <i>Designing Inclusive Systems</i> , Chapt. 23 (pp. 227-236). London: Springer-Verlag.					1	
Heylighen, A., Vermeir, G., Rychtarikova, M. (2008). The Sound of Inclusion: A Case Study on Acoustic Comfort for All. In: Langdon P., Clarkson J., Robinson P. (Eds.), <i>Designing Inclusive Futures</i> (pp. 77-86). London: Springer-Verlag					1	
Heylighen, A. (2012). Challenging prevailing ways of understanding and designing space. In: Bhatt, M., Hoelscher, C., Shipley, T. (Eds.), <i>Spatial Cognition for Architectural Design SCAD 2011 Symposium Proceedings. Spatial Cognition for Architectural Design</i> (pp. 23-40). Bremen/Freiburg: Transregional Collaborative Research Center SFB/TR 8 Spatial Cognition Universität Bremen / Universität Freiburg.	0	0	0	2		1
Vermeersch, P., Heylighen, A. (2010). Blindness and multi-sensoriality in architecture. In Hayes, R., Ebbert, V. (Eds.), <i>The Place of Research, the Research of Place</i> . ARCC/EAAE 2010 International Conference on Architectural Research. (pp. 393-400) Architectural Research Centers Consortium	0	0	0	3		1
Annemans, M., Van Audenhove, C., Vermolen, H., Heylighen, A. (2011) Lying architecture: experiencing space from a hospital bed. <i>WELL-BEING 2011: the First International Conference Exploring the Multi-dimensions of</i>	0	0	0	1		1

Well-being. Birmingham City University & the Royal Institute of British Architects						
Baumers, S., Heylighen, A. (2011) Performing their version of the house: An interpretation of an architectural response to autism. Fixed? Architecture, Incompleteness and Change. Plymouth, 7-8 April, 2011. Plymouth: University of Plymouth.	0	0	0	0		1
Baumers, S., Heylighen, A. (2011) Just a Different World: An autistic's approach to designing space. <i>THE DEATH + LIFE OF SOCIAL FACTORS. Reexamining Behavioral and Cultural Research in Environmental Design</i> . Berkeley: UC Berkeley	0	0	0	0		1
Heylighen, A. (2011). Studying the unthinkable designer. In: Gero J. (Eds.), <i>Design Computing and Cognition DCC'10</i> (pp. 23-34) Springer. DCC'10 Best Presentation Award	0	0	2	2		1
Heylighen, A., Baumers, S., Herssens, J., Nijs, G. and Vermeersch, P.W. (2011). Enacting the Socio-Material: Matter and Meaning Reconfigured through Disabled Experience. <i>THE DEATH + LIFE OF SOCIAL FACTORS. Reexamining Behavioral and Cultural Research in Environmental Design</i> . Berkeley: UC Berkeley	0	0	0	0		1
Heylighen, A., Nijs, G. (2011). Studying (Architecture) in Dialogue with Disability. In: Simons M., Decuyper M., Vlieghe J., Masschelein J. (Eds.), <i>Curating the European University</i> (pp.9-16). Leuven: Leuven University Press.	0	0	0	4		1
Herssens, J., Heylighen, A. (2011). Challenging Architects to Include Haptics in Design: Sensory Paradox between Content and Representation. In: Leclercq P., Martin G., Heylighen A. (Eds.), <i>Designing Together - CAADfutures 2011</i> (pp. 685-700). Liege: Les Editions de l'Universite de Liege	0	0	0	1		1
Vermeersch, P., Nijs, G., Heylighen, A. (2011). Mediating artifacts in architectural design: a non-visual exploration. In Leclercq, P., Heylighen, A., Martin, G. (Eds.), <i>Designing Together - CAADfutures 2011</i> (pp. 721-734). Liege: Les Editions de l'Universita de Liege	0	0	0	6		1
Baumers, S., Heylighen, A. (2010). <i>Harnessing Different Dimensions of Space</i> . In: Langdon P., Clarkson J., Robinson P. (Eds), <i>Designing Inclusive Interactions</i> (pp. 13-23). London, UK: Springer-Verlag	0	2	1	8		1
Baumers, S., Heylighen, A. (2010). Beyond the Designers' View. In Lalande, P., et al. (Eds), <i>Design and Complexity. Proceedings of the Design Research Society Conference 2010. Design Research Society Conference. Montreal, 7-9 July 2010</i> (art.nr. 417)	0	0	0	3		1
Herssens, J., Heylighen, A. (2010). Blind Body Language. In Clarkson, P., Langdon, P., Robinson, P. (Eds), <i>Proceedings of the 5th Cambridge Workshop on Universal Access and Assistive Technology</i> , (art.nr. 11) (pp. 109-118). Cambridge (UK): University of Cambridge. Best Paper Award in the Doctoral Consortium	0	0	0	9		1
Heylighen, A., Bianchin, M. (2010). Can crap design be inclusive?. In Clarkson, P., Langdon, P., Robinson, P. (Eds), <i>Proceedings of the 5th Cambridge Workshop on Universal Access and Assistive Technology</i> , art.nr. 6) (pp. 55-65). Cambridge (UK): University of Cambridge.	0	0	0	5		1
Heylighen, A., Neyt, E., Baumers, S., Herssens, J., Vermeersch, P. (2010). Conservation Meets Inclusion. Model Meets Reality. In Clarkson, P., Langdon, P., Robinson, P. (Eds), <i>Proceedings of the 5th Cambridge Workshop on Universal Access and Assistive Technology</i> , (art.nr. 21) (pp. 209-218). Cambridge (UK): University of Cambridge.	0	0	0	3		1
Heylighen, A., Baumers, S., Herssens, J., Nijs, G., Vermeersch, P. (2010). Challenging prevailing boundaries in design. In: <i>Borderline - Pushing design over the limit</i> . Cumulus.	0	0	0	0		1
Nijs, G., Heylighen, A. (2010). "Well, the building made the decision". Annual Meeting of the Society for the Social Studies of Science. Tokyo, 25-29 August 2010.	0	0	0	0		1
Nijs, G., Vermeersch, P., Devlieger, P., Heylighen, A. (2010). Extending the Dialogue between Design(ers) and Disabled Use(rs). <i>Proceedings of Design 2010 - International Design Conference</i> . Design Society.	0	0	2	6		1
Vermeersch, P.W., Nijs, G., Heylighen, A. (2010). Scaling tactility ? tactilely scaling. Scale - AHRA Conference. Canterbury, 19-20 November 2010.	0	0	0	0		1
De Cauwer, P., Clement, M., Buelens, H., Heylighen, A. (2009). Four reasons not to teach inclusive design. 5 Include 2009. London, 5-8 April 2009.	0	0	0	3		1

Heressens, J., Heylighen, A. (2009). A lens into the haptic world. 5 Include 2009. London, 5-8 April 2009.	0	0	0	4	1
Heylighen, A., Rychtarikova, M., Vermeir, G. (2009). Designing Spaces for Every Listener. Universal Access in the Information Society, 9(3), art.nr. 388.	4	4	9	11	1
Heylighen, A., Heressens, J., Froyen, H. (2009). Architecture Criticism Blindfolded. 5 Include 2009. London, 5-8 April 2009.	0	0	0	3	1
Froyen, H., Heressens, J., Heylighen, A. (2008). Buildings Revis(it)ed. A+ Belgisch Tijdschrift voor Architectuur, (210), 82-85.	0	0	0	1	1
(2012) Architectuur voor de liggende patient. Onderzoek naar een meer menselijke architectuur voor ziekenhuizen. Zorgwijzer 28, pp.26-27	0	0	0	0	1
Verbeylen, W. (2013). Bouwen voor alle zintuigen. Blinde ontwerpers werpen nieuw licht op architectuur. Campuskrant, 24(5), 3-3.	0	0	0	0	1
Sioen, L., Kets, J. (2012). Jonge topwetenschappers in België en hoe ze hier te houden. In: dS Weekblad, 50-55	0	0	0	0	1
Stroobants, J. Vermeir, G.(2011). Grote Aula in een nieuw kleedje. In: Campuskrant, 23 (3).	0	0	0	0	1
de Meyere A (2010). Onderzoek peilt naar hoe patienten zorggebouwen liggend ervaren In: de Specialisten, 16 september 2010	0	0	0	0	1
Verbeylen W (2009). Blinde kinderen wijzen de weg In: Campuskrant, 21 oktober 2009, pp.1,8	0	0	0	0	1
Van Baelen J (2009). Wie maakt Leuven Groot? In: Knack, 27 april 2009, pp.12-20	0	0	0	0	1
Heylighen, A., Baemers, S., Heressens, J., Nijs, G., & Vermeersch, P. W. (2011). Enacting the socio-material: Matter and meaning reconfigured through disabled experience. In The Death+ Life of Social Factors Conference Proceedings.	0	0	0	0	1
Schaevebeke, R., Aarts, H., & Heylighen, A. (2014). Imagining Space. How To Teach Drawing as a Tool to Explore Spatiality?. Unspoken Issues in Architectural Education.	0	0	0	0	1
Annemans, M., Van Audenhove, C., Vermolen, H., & Heylighen, A. (2014). How to Introduce Experiential User Data: The Use of Information in Architects' Design Process. In Design's Big Debates. The Design Research Society's 2014 conference.	0	0	0	0	1
Coomans, K., De Smet, H., & Heylighen, A. (2012). Designing a Future for Large-Scale Care Homes in Flanders. status: published.	0	0	0	0	1
Heressens, J., Heylighen, A. (2012). Haptic design research. In Hayes, R. (Ed.), Ebbert, V. (Ed.), The Place of Research, the Research of Place. ARCC/EAAE 2010 International Conference on Architectural Research. (pp. 374-382) Architectural Research Centers Consortium (ARCC)	0	0	0	5	1
Van Steenwinkel, I., Van Audenhove, C., Heylighen, A. (2013). In case of dementia: orientating in an (e)motional way. International and Interdisciplinary Conference on Emotional Geographies. Groningen, 1-3 July 2013.	0	0	0	0	1
Heylighen, A. (2013). Transferring disability experience to design practice. In Nimkulrat, N., Niedderer, K., Evans, M. (Eds.), Knowing Inside Out - experiential knowledge, expertise and connoisseurship. EKSIG 2013. Loughborough University, 4-5 July 2013. Loughborough: Loughborough University	0	0	0	0	1
Rychtarikova, M., Heressens, J., Heylighen, A. (2012). Towards more inclusive approaches in soundscape research. INTER- NOISE 2012. Proceedings - National Conference on Noise Control Engineering. art. nr. 855.	0	0	0	0	1
Baemers, S., & Heylighen, A. (2009). The eyes of the mind. architecture and mental disability. <i>Engaging Artifacts</i> .	0	0	0	2	1
Annemans, M., Van Audenhove, C., Vermolen, H., & Heylighen, A. (2012). What makes an environment healing? Users and designer about the Maggie's Cancer Caring Centre London. In Out of Control. Proceedings of the 8th International Design and Emotion Conference (pp. 1-8).	0	0	0	2	1
Vermeersch, P. W., & Heylighen, A. (2013). Rendering the tacit observable in the learning process of a changing body. Knowing Inside Out-experiential knowledge, expertise and connoisseurship, 259-270.	0	0	0	1	1
Wauters, H., Vermeersch, P. W., & Heylighen, A. (2014). Reality check: Notions of accessibility in today's architectural design practice. In Design's Big Debates. The	0	0	0	0	1

Design Research Society's 2014 conference.							
TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	20					13	43

INCL-ED							
Aguilera, A., Mendoza, M. Racionero, S. & Soler, M. (2009). "Lectura dialógica: interacciones que mejoran y aceleran la lectura." (The role of the university in Learning Communities). <i>Revista Interuniversitaria de Formación del Profesorado</i> , 67 (24-1), 45-56.	0	0	0	41			
Aubert, A. (2011). Moving beyond social exclusion through dialogue. <i>International Studies in Sociology of Education</i> , 21 (1), 63-75.	0	0	8	22			
Aubert, A., & López, C. (2010). Dimensiones demográficas de la superación de la exclusión social. <i>Revista Educación y Pedagogía</i> , 56, 79-89.	0	0	0	1			
Aubert, A., Melgar, P., & Valls, R. (2011). Communicative Daily Life Stories and Focus Groups: Proposals for Overcoming Gender Violence among Teenagers. <i>Qualitative Inquiry</i> , 17 (3), 295-303.	2	3	3	18			
Aubert, A., García, C., & Racionero, S. (2009). Dialogic Learning. <i>Cultura y Educación</i> , 21 (2), 129-139.	0	0	3	30			
Brown, M., Gómez, A. & Munté, A. (2013). Procesos dialógicos de planificación de los servicios sociales: el proceso de cambio en los barrios de La Milagrosa y La Estrella (Albacete). <i>Scripta Nova</i> , Vol. XVII, núm. 427.	4	0	0	3			
Christou, M., & Puigvert, L. (2011). The role of "Other Women" in current educational transformations. <i>International Studies in Sociology of Education</i> , 21 (1), 77-90.	0	0	3	7			
Díez, D., Gatt, S., & Racionero, S. (2011). Placing Immigrant and Minority Family and Community Members at the School's Centre: the role of community participation. <i>European Journal of Education</i> , 46 (2), 184-196.	3	3	5	20			
Díez-Palomar, J., Rue, L., & García P. (2010). Matemàtiques i grups interactius: ensenyament i aprenentatge des del punt de vista de les interaccions. <i>Temps d'Educació</i> , 38, 135-151.	0	0	0	7			
Díez-Palomar, J., Santos Pitanga, T. & Álvarez Cifuentes, P. (2013). La Paz School. From a Ghetto to a Magnet School. <i>International Review of Qualitative Research</i> , 6(2): 198-209.	0	0	0	1			
Elboj, C., & Niemelä, R. (2010). Sub-communities of Mutual Learners in the Classroom: The case of Interactive groups. Special Issue, <i>Journal of Psychodidactics</i> , 15 (2), 177-189.	2	6	6	35			
Engel, L., Holford J., & Pimlott-Wilson, H. (2010). Effectiveness, inequality and ethos in three English schools. <i>International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy</i> , 30 (3/4), 140-154	0	0	0	3			
Flecha, A., García, R., Gómez, A. & Latorre, A. (2009). "Participación en las escuelas de éxito: una investigación comunicativa del proyecto Includ-ed" [Participation in successful schools: a communicative study of the Includ-ed project]. <i>Cultura y Educación: Revista de teoría, investigación y práctica</i> , 21 (2), 183-196	0	0	7	38			
Flecha, A., García, R., & Rudd, R. (2011). Using Health Literacy in School to Overcome Inequalities. <i>European Journal of Education</i> , 46 (2), 209-218.	3	1	1	8			
Flecha, A., Pulido C., & Christou, M. (2011). Transforming violent selves through reflection in critical communicative research. <i>Qualitative Inquiry</i> , 17 (3), 246-255.	2	2	2	8			
Flecha, A., Ruiz, L. & Vreecer, N. (2013). La alfabetización en salud y el empoderamiento de las comunidades. <i>Scripta Nova</i> , Vol. XVII, núm. 427.	4	0	0	0			
Flecha, A., García, R., Gómez, A., & Latorre, A. (2009). Participation in successful schools: A communicative research study from the Includ-ed Project. <i>Cultura y Educación</i> , 21 (2), 183-196.	4	4	5	2			
Flecha, R. & Soler, M. (2014). Communicative Methodology: Successful Actions and Dialogic Politics. <i>Current Sociology</i> , 62(2): 232-242.	3	4	3	4			
Flecha, R. & Soler, M. (2013). Turning difficulties into possibilities: engaging Roma families and students in school through dialogic learning. <i>Cambridge Journal of Education</i> , DOI: 10.1080/0305764X.2013.819068	3	3	3	11			
Flecha, R. (2009). Change, inclusion and quality in learning communities. <i>Cultura y Educación</i> , 21 (2), 157-169.	0	0	6	24			

Flecha, R. (2011). The dialogic sociology of education. <i>International Studies in Sociology of Education</i> , 21 (1), 7–20.	0	0	5	27		
Flecha, R. (2012). European research, social innovation and successful cooperativist actions. <i>International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences</i> , 4(4), 332 – 344.	0	0	0	1		
Flecha, R. (2014). Using mixed methods from a communicative orientation: Researching with grassroots Roma. <i>Journal of Mixed Methods Research</i> (in press).	2	0	0	0		
García, C. (2009). Dialogue and Learning (Introduction to the Monograph). <i>Cultura y Educación</i> , 21 (2), 125-128.	2	1	2	8		
García, C., Ferrada, D., & Ruiz, L. (2011). Other Women in research: overcoming social inequalities and improving scientific knowledge through the inclusion of all voices. <i>Qualitative Inquiry</i> , 17 (3), 284-294.	0	0	0	0		
García, C., Leena, A. & Petreñas, C. (2013). Comunidades de Aprendizaje. <i>Scripta Nova</i> , Vol. XVII, núm. 427.	4	0	0	3		
García, C., Tellado, I., & Chiapelli, T. (2010). Visió general de la discussió sobre les àrees d'exclusió del projecte INCLUD-ED. <i>Temps d'Educació</i> , 38, 185-202.	2	0	2	11		
García, R., Mircea, T., & Duque, E. (2010). Socio-cultural Transformation and the Promotion of Learning. Special Issue, <i>Journal of Psychodidactics</i> , 15 (2), 207-222.	0	0	4	17		
Gatt, S., Ojala, M., & Soler, M. (2011). Promoting social inclusion counting with everyone: Learning Communities and INCLUD-ED. <i>International Studies in Sociology of Education</i> , 21(1), 33–47 .	0	0	4	17		
Gatt, S., Puigdellívol, I., & Molina, S. (2010). Mead's Contributions to Learners' Identities. Special Issue, <i>Journal of Psychodidactics</i> , 15(2), 223-238.	2	0	0	0		
Gómez, A., Racionero, S. & Sordé, T. (2010). "Ten years of critical communicative methodology" <i>International Review of Qualitative Researching</i> , 3 (1), 17-44.	0	0	0	35		
Gómez, A. (2014). New Developments in Mixed Methods with Vulnerable Groups. <i>Journal of Mixed Methods Research</i> (in press).	1	0	0	0		
Gómez, A., Elboj, C. & Capllonch, M. (2013). Beyond Action Research. The Communicative Methodology of Research. <i>International Review of Qualitative Research</i> , 6(2): 183-197.	0	0	0	1		
Gómez, A., Puigvert, L., & Flecha R. (2011). Critical Communicative Methodology: Informing real social transformation through research. <i>Qualitative Inquiry</i> , 17 (3), 235-245.	2	22	19	53		
Gómez, A., Racionero, S., & Sordé, T. (2010). Ten years of critical communicative methodology. <i>International Review of Qualitative Research</i> , 3, 1, 17-44	0	0	0	35		
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Herrero, C., & Brown, M. (2010). Distributed Cognition in Community-based Education. Special Issue, <i>Journal of Psychodidactics</i> , 15(2), 253-268.	2	1	1	7		
Kardeliënė, Laimutė; Zuzevičiūtė, Vaiva (2009). "The main innovations in education: in pursue of aims of Bologna (1999) and Bergen (2005) processes" <i>Journal Education Physical training Sport</i> . 2, 43-52.	0	0	0	0		
Melgar, P., Larena, R., Ruiz, L., & Rammel, S. (2011). How to Move from Power-based to Dialogic Relations? Lessons from Roma Women. <i>European Journal of Education</i> , 46(2), 219–227.	3	0	0	1		
Mello, R. (2009). Dialogue and school in Brazil: Learning communities. <i>Cultura y Educación</i> , 21(2), 171-181.	0	0	0	3		
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Mircea, T., & Sordé, T. (2011). How to turn difficulties into opportunities: drawing from diversity to promote social cohesion. <i>International Studies in Sociology of Education</i> , 21(1), 49 – 62.	0	0	6	16		
Munté, A., Serradell, O., & Sordé, T. (2011). From research to policy: Roma participation through communicative organization. <i>Qualitative Inquiry</i> , 17 (3), 256-266.	2	4	3	12		
Oliver, E., & Gatt, S. (2010). De los actos comunicativos de poder a los actos comunicativos dialógicos en las aulas organizadas en grupos interactivos. Número Especial Monográfico, <i>Signos</i> , 43 (2), 279-294.	4	2	2	12		

Oliver, E., de Botton, L., Soler, M., & Merril B. (2011). Cultural intelligence to overcome educational exclusion. <i>Qualitative Inquiry</i> , 17 (3), 267-276.	2	0	2	8		
Oliver, E., Soler, M., & Flecha, R. (2009). Opening schools to all (women): efforts to overcome gender violence in Spain British. <i>Journal of Sociology of Education</i> , 30 (2), 207-218.	0	0	10	40		
Oliver, E.; Soler, M.; Flecha, R. (2009). Opening schools to all (women): efforts to overcome gender violence in Spain British, <i>Journal of Sociology of Education</i> , Vol. 30, No. 2, pp. 207-218.	2	8	10	43		
Padrós, M., & Zepa, B. (2010). Actuaciones de éxito en el aprendizaje de lenguas: aproximaciones desde la investigación. <i>Revista Educación y Pedagogía</i> , 56, 91-99.	0	0	0	0		
Padrós, M., García, R., de Mello, R., & Molina S. (2011). Contrasting scientific knowledge with knowledge from the lifeworld: The Dialogic Inclusion Contract. <i>Qualitative Inquiry</i> , 17 (3), 304-312.	2	6	0	17		
Petreñas, C., Puigdel·l·ivol, I. & Campdepadrós, R. (2013). From Educational Segregation to Transformative Inclusion. <i>International Review of Qualitative Research</i> , 6(2): 210-225.	0	0	0	0		
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Puigvert, L., Christou, M. & Holdford, J. (2012). Critical Communicative Methodology: including vulnerable voices in research through dialogue. <i>Cambridge Journal of Education</i> , 42 (4)	4	8	0	18		
Pulido, C., & Zepa, B. (2010). La interpretación interactiva de los textos a través de las tertulias literarias dialógicas. <i>Número Especial Monográfico, Signos</i> , 43 (2), 295-309.	4	0	0	7		
Racionero, S., & Padrós, M. (2010). The Dialogic Turn in Educational Psychology. Special Issue, <i>Journal of Psychodidactics</i> , 15 (2), 143-162.	2	1	2	28		
Ramis, M., & Krastina, L. (2010). Cultural Intelligence in the School. Special Issue, <i>Journal of Psychodidactics</i> , 15 (2), 239-252.	2	4	3	26		
Redondo, G., Santa Cruz, I., & Rotger J. (2011). Why Mondragon? Analyzing what works in overcoming inequalities. <i>Qualitative Inquiry</i> , 17 (3), 277-283.	2	0	0	3		
Ríos, O., & Christou, M. (2010). Más allá del lenguaje sexista. Actos comunicativos en las relaciones afectivo-sexuales de los y las adolescentes. <i>Número Especial Monográfico, Signos</i> , 43 (2), 311-326.	4	1	1	3		
Ríos, O., Herrero, C. & Rodríguez, H. (2013). From Access to Education. The Revolutionary Transformation of Schools as Learning Communities. <i>International Review of Qualitative Research</i> , 6(2): 239-253.	0	0	0	1		
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Santa Cruz, I., & Redondo, G. (2010). Actos comunicativos en las empresas. <i>Número Especial Monográfico, Signos</i> , 43 (2), 327-341.	4	0	0	0		
Santa Cruz, I., Siles, G., & Vrečer, N. (2011). Invest for the Long Term or Attend to Immediate Needs? Schools and the Employment of Less Educated Youths and Adults. <i>European Journal of Education</i> , 46 (2), 197-208.	3	0	0	3		
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Soler, M. (2011). Editorial. <i>European Journal of Education</i> , 46 (2), 169-172.	3	0	0	0		
Soler, M., & Flecha, R. (2010). Desde los Actos de Habla de Austin a los actos comunicativos. <i>Perspectivas desde Searle, Habermas y CREA. Número Especial Monográfico, Signos</i> , 43 (2), 363-375.	4	0	1	4		
Sordé, T., & Ojala, M. (2010). Actos comunicativos dialógicos y actos comunicativos de poder en la investigación. <i>Número Especial Monográfico, Signos</i> , 43 (2), 377-391.	4	4	4	9		
Tellado, I., & Sava, S. (2010). The Role of Non-expert Adult Guidance in the Dialogic Construction of Knowledge.	2	3	1	11		

	Special Issue, Journal of Psychodidactics, 15 (2), 163-176.							
	Valls, R. & Kyriakides, L. (2013). The power of Interactive Groups: how diversity of adults volunteering in classroom groups can promote inclusion and success for children of vulnerable minority ethnic populations. Cambridge Journal of Education, 43 (1) p. 17-33.	0	0	0	1			
	Valls, R., & Mulcahy, C. (2010). Projecte integrat INCLUD-ED: cohesió social i impacte polític a Europa. Presentació. Temps d'Educació, 38, 91-94.	0	0	0	1			
	Valls, R., & Padrós, M. (2011). Using Dialogic Research to Overcome Poverty: from principles to action. European Journal of Education, 46 (2), 173-183.	3	5	3	11			
	Valls, R., Soler, M. & Flecha, R. (2008). "Lectura dialógica: interacciones que mejoran y aceleran la lectura." [Dialogic Reading: interactions that improve and accelerate reading]. Revista Iberoamericana de Educación, 46.	0	0	0	41			
	Wells, G., & Haneda, M. (2009). The contribution of inquiry to second language. Cultura y Educación, 21 (2), 141-156.	0	0	0	5			
	Zuzevičiūtė, V., & Miliušienė, M. (2009). Reaching the social cohesion in education: Perspective of Lithuanian teachers. Journal of teacher education for sustainability, 11 (1), 43-49.	0	0	0	0			
	Racionero, Sandra; Ortega, Sara; García, Rocío; Flecha, Ramón. (2012). Aprendiendo contigo. Barcelona: Hipatia Editorial. ISBN: 978-84-938226-3-7.						1	
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	Flecha, Ramon. (2015). Successful Educational Actions for Inclusion and Social Cohesion in Europe. Series: SpringerBriefs in Education. Springer Editorial. ISBN: 978-3-319-11176-6						1	
	Campani, G. (2008). "Dalle minoranze agli immigrati. La questione del pluralismo culturale e religioso in Italia" Giovanna Campani (From minorities to immigrants. The question of cultural and religious pluralism in Italy).						0	
	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	73					4	0

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	Tramonata F., Westerhoff F., Gardini L. (2010). On the complicated price dynamics of a simple one-dimensional discontinuous financial market model... Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization, 74(3); 187-205.	2	12	14	27		
	Battiston S., Delli Gatti D., Gallegati M., Greenwald B.C., Stiglitz J.E. (2009). LIASONS DANGEREUSES: INCREASING CONNECTIVITY, RISK SHARING, AND SYSTEMIC RISK, NBER Working Paper Series, NO. 15611	2	27	35	216		
	Baglioni A. Liquidity crunch in the interbank market: Is it credit or liquidity risk, or both? J Financ Serv Res. 2011, in press. Springer. Germany	2	0	3	10		
	Delli Gatti D., Gallegati M., Greenwald B., Russo A., Stiglitz J.E. (2010). The financial accelerator in an evolving credit network, Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control, 34(9); 1627-1650.	2	14	16	61		
POLHIA	Bargili L., Gallegati M. (2011). Random digraphs with given expected degree sequences: A model for economic networks. Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization, 78(3); 396-411.	2	5	5	14		
	Hommes C., Wagener F. Does educative stability imply evolutionary stability? Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization. 2010; 75(1); Elsevier. 25-39	2	2	0	12		
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	Vona F., Patriarca F. Income inequality and the development of environmental technologies. Ecological Economics. 2011 9/15. Elsevier	1	6	0	20		
	Femminis G., Martini G. Irreversible investment and R&D spillovers in a dynamic duopoly. Journal of Economic. Elsevier Dynamics and Control	2	2	3	7		
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	Tramontata F. Economics as a compartmental system: a simple macroeconomic example. Int Rev Econ 2010; 57; Springer-Verlag	0	0	2	6		
	Creel J., Saraceno F. European Fiscal Rules after the crisis. Journal of Innovation Economics. 2010; 6(2); De Boeck Université	0	0	0	6		
	Anufriev M., Arifovic J., Ledyard J., Panchenko V. Efficiency of continuous double auctions under individual evolutionary learning with full or limited information. Journal of Evolutionary Economics	3	4	5	11		
	Gaffard J.L, Saraceno F. International trade and domestic distortion. Journal of Evolutionary Economics 2011, in press Springer	3	0	0	3		
	Cars Hommes, Thomas Lux. INDIVIDUAL EXPECTATIONS AND AGGREGATE BEHAVIOR IN LEARNING-TO-FORECAST EXPERIMENTS, Macroeconomic Dynamics, Vol. 17/Issue 02	2	8	15	43		
	Dosi G., Fagiolo G., Napoletano M., Roventini A. (2013). Structural change and income distribution: An inverted-U relationship, Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control, 37(8); 1598–1625.	2	7	9	43		
	Luca Riccetti , Alberto Russo , Mauro Gallegati. Leveraged network-based financial accelerator. Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control, Vol. 37/Issue 8.	2	4	6	19		
	Domenico Massaro. Heterogeneous expectations in monetary DSGE models. Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control, Vol. 37/Issue 3.	2	4	3	13		
	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	23				0	0

EUMARGINS	Thomas Johansson & Rita Olofsson (2011) The art of becoming Swedish: Immigrant youth, school careers, and life plans, Ehtnicities, 11(2): 184-201	3	1	2	8		
	Fangen, Katrine & Paasche, Erlend (2013). Young adults of ethnic minority background on the Norwegian labour market: The interactional co-construction of exclusion by employers and customers . Ethnicities. ISSN 1468-7968. 13(5), pp. 607- 624	3	0	0	2		
	Thomas Johansson & Nils Hammaren (2012) The art of choosing the right tram: Schooling, segregation and youth culture, Acta Sociologica, 54(1): 45-59.	2	3	2	9		
	Herz, Marcus & Thomas JOhansson (2012): The experience of being stopped: young immigrants, social exclusion and strategies, Nordic Journal of Youth Research (YOUNG), 20(2): 157-176	2	1	1	2		
	Fangen, Katrine (2009) Sosial ekskludering av unge med innvandringsbakgrunn: Den relasjonelle, stedlige og politiske dimensjonen, Tidsskrift for ungdomsforskning, 9(2): 91-112	0	0	0	2		
	Fangen, Katrine (2010). Social exclusion and inclusion of young immigrants Presentation of an analytical framework. Young - Nordic Journal of Youth Research. ISSN 1103-3088. 18(2), pp. 133- 156 .	2	8	11	28		
	Les Back and Shamsir Sinha (2012) New hierarchies of belonging, European Journal of Cultural Studies, 15(2): 139-154.	2	7	9	16		
	Katrine Fangen. Inclusion and Exclusion of Young Adult Migrants in Europe - Barriers and Bridges. Research in Migration and Ethnic Relations Series June 2010	0	0	0	23,00		

	Thomas Johansson and Nils Hammarén. Konstn att valja ratt spåravn En studie av segregation, skolval och unga människors studieplaner.- Sociologisk Forskning	0	0	0	4,00		
	Katrine Fangen, Thomas Johansson and Nils Hammarén. Young Migrants: Exclusion and Belonging in Europe Migration, Diasporas and Citizenship Series	0	0	0	12,00		
	Les Back. The New Hierarchies of Belonging. European Journal of Cultural Studies	0	0	0	22,00		
	Katrine Fangen; Nils Hammaren & Thomas Johansson (ed.), Young Migrants – Exclusion and Belonging in Europe. Palgrave Macmillan. ISBN 9780230298873.					1	
	Fangen, K., Fossan, K. and Mohn, F. A. (eds.). 2010. Inclusion and Exclusion of Young Adult Migrants in Europe – Barriers and Bridges, Surrey: Ashgate					0	
	Erlend Paasche & Katrine Fangen (2011) Ethnic school segregation, Effects and policies	0			1		1
	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	11				2	1

ANTICORRP P. Anticorruption Policies Revisited. Global trends and European responses to the challenge of corruption	Charron, N., Dijkstra, L., & Lapuente, V. (2014). Mapping the Regional Divide in Europe: A Measure for Assessing Quality of Government in 206 European Regions. Social Indicators Research, 1-32.	1	0	0	0		
	Bågenholm, A., & Charron, N. (2014). Do Politics in Europe Benefit from Politicising Corruption?. West European Politics, 37(5), 903-931.	1	0	0	0		
	Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (2014). The Transformative Power of Europe Revisited. Journal of Democracy, 25(1), 20-32.	1	0	0	5		
	Hanley, S., & Sikk, A. (2014). Economy, corruption or floating voters? Explaining the breakthroughs of anti-establishment reform parties in eastern Europe. Party Politics, 1354068814550438.	1	0	0	0		
	Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (2013). Controlling corruption through collective action. Journal of Democracy, 24(1), 101-115.	1	0	0	13		
	Pop, R., Doroftei, I. M., & Dimulescu, V. (2013). Risks of corruption and the management of EU funds in Romania. Romanian Journal of Political Sciences, (01), 101-123.	4	1	0	0		
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	Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (2013). The Good, the Bad and the Ugly: Controlling Corruption in the European Union. Hertie School of Government Policy, Paper for Discussion in the European Parliament.–2013–9 April–63 p.	0			0		
Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (2013). Global comparative trend analysis report. ANTICORRP project, available at http://anticorpp.eu/publications/global-comparative-trend-analysisreport-1 .	0			0			1
TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	6					2	2

HI-POD	Brian A	0			76		
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Ozga, J., Seddon, T., & Popkewitz, T. S. (Eds.). (2013). World Yearbook of Education 2006: Education, Research and Policy: Steering the Knowledge-Based Economy. Routledge.							0	
TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	7						2	0

CEDAR Clinical decision making and outcome in routine care for people with severe mental illness	Puschner B, Steffen S, Slade M, Kaliniecka H, Maj M, Fiorillo A, Munk-Jørgensen P, Larsen JI, Egerhazi A, Nemes Z, Rössler W, Kawohl W, Becker T (2010). Clinical decision making and outcome in routine care for people with severe mental illness (CEDAR): study protocol. BMC Psychiatry 10, 90.	2	5		17			
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	Puschner B, Neumann P, Jordan H, Slade M, Fiorillo A, Giacco D, Égerházi A, Ivánka T, Bording MK, Sørensen HØ, Bär A, Kawohl W, Loos S (2013). Development and psychometric properties of a five-language multiperspective instrument to assess clinical decision making style in the treatment of people with severe mental illness (CDMS). BMC Psychiatry 13, 48.	2	1		4			
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TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	7						1	0
TENLAW Tenancy Law and Housing Policy in Multi-level Europe	Rumo a um Direito Comum do Arrendamento Urbano Europeu? O Impacto do Tribunal Europeu dos Direitos Humanos no Direito do Arrendamento, Marta dos Santos Silva, Christoph U. Schmid & Jason R. Dinse, in <i>Boletim da Faculdade de Direito da Universidade de Coimbra</i> , Vol. LXXXIX. Coimbra Editora: Coimbra, forthcoming in 2014.	0	0	0		0		
	József Hegedűs, Vera Horváth & Nóra Tosics (2014): Economic and legal conflicts between landlords and tenants in the Hungarian private rental sector, <i>International Journal of Housing Policy</i> , DOI: 10.1080/14616718.2014.908571	0	0	0			1	
	Christoph U. Schmid & Jason R. Dinse, <i>European Dimensions of Residential Tenancy Law, ERCL 2013</i> ; 9(3):201-220	0	0	0		0		
	Towards a Common Core of Residential Tenancy Law in Europe? The Impact of the European Court of Human Rights on Tenancy Law, Christoph U. Schmid and Jason Dinse, in <i>Life Time Contracts: Social Long-term Contracts in Labour, Tenancy and Consumer Credit Law</i> , Luca Nogler & Udo Reifner eds., Eleven International Publishing, 2014, p. 605.							0
TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	3						1	0
GEITONIES Generatin g Interethni c Tolerance and Neighbour hood Integratio n in European Urban Spaces	Górny , A. , Toruńczyk-Ruiz, S. 2013. Neighbourhood Attachment in Ethnically Diverse Areas: The Role of Interethnic Ties. <i>Urban Studies</i>	2	3	3		11		
	Fonseca, M.L.; McGarrigle, J. (Guest editors) (2013) <i>Finisterra – Revista Portuguesa de Geografia – special issue Neighbourhood integration, social relations and participation in European multi-ethnic cities</i> , XLVIII, (96).	0	0	0		0		
	Malheiros, J., Carvalho, R. and Mendes, L. (2013) “Gentrification, residential ethnicization and the social production of fragmented space: theory and evidence from two multi-ethnic neighbourhoods, in Lisbon and Bilbao”. <i>Finisterra – Revista Portuguesa de Geografia</i> , XLVIII (96).	0	0	0		0		
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	Ruiz Vieytez, Eduardo Javier; Maiztegui Oñate, Concepción; Ibarrola Armendariz, Aitor; Bartolomé Peral, Edurne (2011) <i>Inmigración E Integración Urbana. Primeros Resultados Del Proyecto Geitonies: Generando Tolerancia Interétnica E Integración Local En Espacios Urbanos Europeos / Revista Española De Ciencia Política</i> , 166 (64-77) ISBNAR: 12216720	0	0	0		0		

	Schnell, Philipp; Kohlbacher, Josef; Reeger, Ursula (2012) Neighbourhood Embeddedness in Six European Cities: Differences Between Types of Neighbourhoods and Immigrant Background. Polish Sociological Review 4/180: 523-544.	4	0	0	1		
	Kohlbacher, Josef; Reeger, Ursula; Schnell, Philipp (2013) Strong ties inside and outside the neighbourhood. An exploratory analysis of the spatial dimension of ego/alter relations in three urban settings in Vienna. Finisterra 94: 43-64.	0	0	0	0		
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	Kohlbacher, Josef; Reeger, Ursula; Schnell, Philipp (2012) Neighbourhood Embeddedness and Social Coexistence. Immigrants and Natives in three Urban Settings in Vienna; Wien: Verlag der ÖAW.	0	0		0	0	
	Fonseca, M. L. (coord.); McGarrigle, J. (coord.); Esteves, A.; Sampaio, D.; Carvalho, R.; Malheiros, J. and Moreno, L. (2012) Modes of interethnic coexistence in three neighbourhoods in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area: A comparative perspective	0	0	0	4	0	
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Families and Societies - Changing families and sustainable societies: Policy contexts and diversity over the life course and across generations	Bernardi, F. and Radl, J. (2014). "The Long-Term Consequences of Parental Divorce for Children's Educational Attainment". Demographic Research, 30(61): 1653-1680	2	0	0	2		
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	Juan Díez Medrano, Clara Cortina, Ana Safranoff and Teresa Castro-Martín (2014). Euromarriages in Spain: Recent trends in the context of European integration. Population, Space and Place 20(2):	1	0	0	4		
	Rahnu, Leen, Puur, Allan, Sakkeus, Luule and Martin Klesment. (2014). Varying association between education and second births in Europe: comparative analysis based on the EU-SILC data. Demographic Research, 31. Forthcoming.	2	0	0	1		
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	Teresa Castro-Martín and Teresa Martín-García, T. (2014). The fertility gap in Spain: Late parenthood, few children and unfulfilled reproductive desires. In Gøsta Esping-Andersen (Coord.), <i>The Fertility Gap in Europe</i> . Social Studies Collection no. 36. Barcelona: la Caixa Foundation.						0	
	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	12					1	0

HOLY AND LAY	Corbellini, S. et al., 'Challenging the Paradigms: Holy Writ and Lay Readers in Late Medieval Europe', <i>Church History and Religious Culture</i> 93 (2013) 171-188.	0	0	0	0		
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	S. Corbellini, 'Vernacular Bible Manuscripts in Late Medieval Italy: Cultural Appropriation and Textual Transformation', in E. Poleg, L. Light ed., <i>Form and Function in the Late Medieval Bible</i> , Leiden 2013, 261-281.						0
	S. Corbellini, ed., <i>Cultures of Religious Reading in the Late Middle Ages. Instructing the Soul, Feeding the Spirit, and Awakening the Passion</i> , Turnhout 2013.						0
	Corbellini, S., 'The Plea for Lay Bibles in Fourteenth and Fifteenth Century Tuscany. The Role of Confraternities' in S. Pastore, N. Terpstra & A. Prosperi (eds.), <i>Brotherhoods and Boundaries</i> (Turnhout 2012) 87-112.						0
	Corbellini, S., 'Orthodoxy and Heterodoxy: a Focus on Fifteenth-Century Reading Techniques', in S. Corbellini (ed.), <i>Instructing the Soul, Feeding the Spirit and Awakening the Passion. Cultures of Religious Reading in the Late Middle Ages</i> (Turnhout 2013) 33-53.						0
	S. Corbellini, 'Instructing the Soul, Feeding the Spirit and Awakening the Passion: Holy Writ and Lay Readers in Medieval Europe', in B. Gordon, M. McLean ed., <i>Shaping the Bible in the Reformation. Books, Scholars and Their Readers in the Sixteenth Century</i> , Leiden 2012, 15-39.						0
	Corbellini, S., 'Retelling the Bible in Medieval Italy. The Case of the Italian Gospel Harmonies', in L. Dolezalova and T. Visi (eds.), <i>Retelling the Bible. Literary, Historical, and Social Contexts</i> (Frankfurt am Main, 2011) 213-228						0
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TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	3					7	0

FIDUCIA New European Crimes and Trust-Based Policy	Maffei-Markopolou, <i>Fiducia New European Crimes And Trust-Based Policy</i> , vol. 1						0
	Maffei-Markopolou, <i>Fiducia New European Crimes And Trust-Based Policy</i> , Vol. II						0
	Hough, M., Jackson, J. and Bradford, B. 'Trust in Justice and the Legitimacy of Legal Authorities: Topline Findings from a Comparative European Study', in Body-Gendrot, S., Lévy, R., Hough, M. Snacken, S. and Kerezi, K. <i>The Routledge Handbook of European Criminology</i> , Oxon: Routledge, 2013						0
	Bradford, B., Jackson, J. and Hough, M. (in press). 'Police Legitimacy in Action: Lessons for Theory and Practice', in Reising, M. & Kane, R. (eds.) <i>The Oxford Handbook of Police and Policing</i> . Oxford: Oxford University Press						0
	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	0					4

LOCALISE (Local Worlds of Social Cohesion. The Local	"European worlds of inclusive activation: The organisational challenges of coordinated service provision" by Martin Heidenreich & Patrizia Aurich-Berheide. <i>International Journal of Social Welfare</i> (Article first published online on 27 July 2014; D.O.I.: 10.1111/ijsw.12098)	2	0	0	0		
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Dimension of Integrated Social and Employment Policies)	"Towards 'activation-friendly' integration? Assessing the progress of activation policies in six European countries" by Thierry Berthet & Clara Bourgeois. International Journal of Social Welfare (Article first published online on 31 March 2014, D.O.I.: 10.1111/ijsw.12088)	2	0	0	2		
	"Towards standby-ability: Swedish and Danish activation policies in flux" by Mattias Bengtsson. International Journal of Social Welfare (Article first published online on 16 January 2014, D.O.I.: 10.1111/ijsw.12075)	2	0	1	6		
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	"Between cooperation and competition: The organisation of employment service delivery in the UK and Germany" by Vanesa Fuertes, Bastian Jantz, Tanja Klenk & Ronald McQuaid. International Journal of Social Welfare (Article first published online on 7 August 2014, D.O.I.: 10.1111/ijsw.12100)	2	0	0	5		
	"Stakeholder participation and policy integration in local social and employment policies: Germany and Italy compared" by Patrizia Aurich-Beerheide, Serida Catalano, Paolo Graziano & Katharina Zimmermann. Journal of European Social Policy, most likely forthcoming in Vol. 25/Issue 3 (2015).	1	0	0	0		
	"Lost in activation? The governance of activation policies in Europe" by Martin Heidenreich and Paolo Graziano. Forthcoming in: International Journal of Social Welfare.						0
	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	6					1

PICK-ME Policy Incentives for the Creation of Knowledge: Methods and Evidence	Antonelli, C., Fassio, C., "The economics of the light economy. Globalization, skill biased technological change and slow growth" Technological Forecasting & Social Change, forthcoming. doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2013.11.006	1	0	1	6		
	Krafft, J., Quatraro F. and Saviotti P.P., 2014, Knowledge characteristics and the dynamics of technological alliances in Pharmaceuticals: Empirical evidence from Europe, US and Japan, Journal of Evolutionary Economics 24, 587-622.	3	0	0	1		
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	Colombelli, A., Krafft, J. and Quatraro, F., 2014, The emergence of new technology-based sectors in European regions: A proximity-based analysis of nanotechnology, Research Policy, forthcoming	1	1	0	2		
	Antonelli, C., Patrucco, P.P., (2014), Organizational innovations, ICTs and knowledge governance: The case of platforms, in J. M. Bauer and M. Latzer (eds.), Handbook on the Economics of the Internet, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, forthcoming.						0
	Antonelli, C. "The dynamics of knowledge governance", Forthcoming in Antonelli, C. and Link, A. (eds.) Handbook on the economics of knowledge, Routledge, London, 2014, forthcoming.						0
	Antonelli, C. "Towards non exclusive intellectual property rights", in Antonelli, C. and Link, A. (eds.) Handbook on the economics of knowledge, Routledge, London, 2014, forthcoming.						0
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TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	6					4	0

TAP - The Assembly Project	Hobæk, Halldis 2013. Tracing Medieval Administrative Systems: Hardanger, Western Norway. In: Debating the Thing in the North I. Selected Papers from Workshops Organized by The Assembly Project (Eds. Sanmark, Iversen, Mehler and Semple.) Journal of the North Atlantic. Eagle Hill Institute. Special Issue 5 2013, 64-75	0	0	0	0		
	Iversen, Frode, 2013. Concilium and Pagus – Revisiting the Early Germanic Thing-system of Northern Europe. Debating the Thing in the North I. Selected Papers from Workshops Organized by The Assembly Project (Eds. Sanmark, Iversen, Mehler and Semple) In Journal of the North Atlantic, 5-17. Eagle Hill Institute. Special Issue 5 2013.	0	0	0	0		
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	Sanmark, A. 2013. 'Patterns of Assembly. Norse Thing Sites in Shetland', Journal of the North Atlantic, Special Volume: The Assembly Project: Debating the Thing in the North I.	0	0	0	0		
	Sanmark, A. 'The Case of the Greenlandic Assembly Sites', Journal of the North Atlantic, Special Volume 2 (2009-10), 178-192	0	0	0	0		
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	Iversen, Frode 2011 The Beauty of Bona Regalia and the Growth of Supra-regional Powers in Scandinavia. I: Viking Settlements and Viking Society: Papers from the Proceedings of the Sixteenth Viking Congress, Reykjavik and Reykholt, 16-23 August 2009. University of Iceland Press, p. 225-244	0	0	0	0		
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	Iversen, Frode; Hobæk, Halldis and Ødegaard, Marie 2011. Comment on Inger Storli's article: 'Court Sites of Arctic Norway: Remains of Thing Sites and Representations of Political Consolidation Processes in the Northern Germanic World during the First Millennium AD?' Norwegian Archaeological Review 2011; Volume 44. (1) s. 89-117.	0	0	0	0		
	Natascha Mehler, Thing-, Markt- und Kaufmannsbuden im westlichen Nordeuropa. Wurzeln, Gemeinsamkeiten und Unterschiede eines Gebäudetyps. Mitteilungen der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Archäologie des Mittelalters und der Neuzeit 24, 2012, 45-56.	0	0	0	0		
	Natascha Mehler, Pingvellir: a place for assembly and a market? Journal of the North Atlantic, special volume (in press).	0	0	0	0		
	Símun Arge and Natascha Mehler, Adventures far from home: hanseatic trade with the Faroe islands. In: Henrik Harnow, David Cranstone, Paul Belford and Lene Høst Masden (eds.), Across the North Sea. Later Historical Archaeology in Denmark and Britain. Studies in History and Social Sciences Vol. 444, 175-187.	0	0	0	3		
	Natascha Mehler, Frode Iversen, Alexandra Sanmark and Sarah Semple, Gerichtsplätze der Wikinger – das Thing in Nordeuropa. Archäologie in Deutschland 1/2014, 60-63.	0	0	0	0		
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and minerals	Critical Thinking about Critical Materials, Assessing risks related to resource security. Bram Buijs and Henrike Sievers, CIEP/BGR report							0	
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	Leitner, K-H, Sundic, M.: Crowdsourcing als Innovationsstrategie: Erfahrungen ausgewählter Unternehmen, Submitted to Zeitschrift für Organisation	0	0	0	0				
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	M. de Graaf-Zijl en T. Ooms, 'Sociaal beleid en inkomensongelijkheid', in: <i>TPEdigitaal</i> 2013 jaargang 7 (1) 95-118.	0	0	0	0		
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	Wiemer Salverda, Brian Nolan, Daniele Checchi, Ive Marx, Abigail McKnight, István György Tóth, and Herman van de Werfhorst. (Ed.). (2014). <i>Changing Inequalities in Rich Countries Analytical and Comparative Perspectives</i> . Oxford: Oxford University Press.	0	0	0	0	1	
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Gordeev, V. S., Pavlova, M., & Groot, W. (2011). Two decades of reforms. Appraisal of the financial reforms in the Russian public healthcare sector. <i>Health policy</i> , 102(2), 270-277.	2	4	5	8			
Tomini, S., Groot, W., & Pavlova, M. (2012). Informal payments and intra-household allocation of resources for health care in Albania. <i>BMC health services research</i> , 12(1), 17.	3	3	3	5			
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Jelena Arsenijević, Milena Pavlova, Wim Groot. Household health care spending and health care reforms in Serbia. <i>Scripta Scientifica Medica</i> 2011, 43 (7): 151-154.	0	0	0	0		
FLORESCU, S., Mihăescu PINȚIA, C., & GALAON, M. (2012). PERSPECTIVE OF ROMANIAN HEALTH CARE CONSUMERS ON PATIENT CO-PAYMENTS (I). <i>Management in Health</i> , 16(2), 33-39.	0	0	0	0		
FLORESCU, S., Mihăescu PINȚIA, C., GĂLĂON, M., & CONSTANTINESCU, V. (2012). PERSPECTIVE OF ROMANIAN HEALTH CARE CONSUMERS ON PATIENT CO-PAYMENTS (II). <i>Management in Health</i> , 16(3), 22-29.	0	0	0	2		

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GUSTO	Burroni, L., & Keune, M. (2011). Flexicurity: A conceptual critique. <i>European Journal of Industrial Relations</i> , 17(1), 75-91.	2	10	23	56		
	Crouch, C. (2012). Employment, Consumption, Debt, and European Industrial Relations Systems. <i>Industrial Relations: A Journal of Economy and Society</i> , 51(s1), 389-412.	2	0	1	10		
	Crouch, C. (2012). Beyond the Flexibility/Security Trade-Off: Reconciling Confident Consumers with Insecure Workers. <i>British Journal of Industrial Relations</i> , 50(1), 1-22.	2	3	5	17		
	Crouch, C. (2010). Flexibility and security in the labour market: An analysis of the governance of inequality. <i>Zeitschrift für ArbeitsmarktForschung</i> , 43(1), 17-38.	0	0	0	17		
	Crouch, C. (2009). Privatised Keynesianism: An unacknowledged policy regime. <i>The British Journal of Politics & International Relations</i> , 11(3), 382-399.	2	82	102	224		
	Muffels, R. J. A., & Wilthagen, A. C. J. M. (2011). Flexwerk en werkzekerheid in tijden van crisis. <i>Economische Statistische Berichten</i> , 96(4602), 54-57.	0	0	0	9		
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	Artiles, A. M., López-Roldán, P., & Molina, Ó. (2011). Movilidad ascendente de la inmigración en España :¿ asimilación o segmentación ocupacional?.(2011): 1311-1338	0	0	3	10		
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	Meardi, G., Martín, A., & Riera, M. L. (2012). Constructing uncertainty: Unions and migrant labour in construction in Spain and the UK. <i>Journal of Industrial Relations</i> , 54(1), 5-21.	3	4	6	22		
	Marier, P. (2013). Who pays the piper calls the tune? Comparing Canada's and the European Union's expansionary roles in pensions. <i>Canadian Public Administration</i> , 56(2), 322-337.	4	2	2	3		
	Casey, B. H., & Dostal, J. M. (2013). Voluntary Pension Saving for Old Age: Are the Objectives of Self-responsibility and Security Compatible?. <i>Social Policy & Administration</i> , 47(3), 287-309.	1	0	0	3		
	Casey, B. H. (2012). The implications of the economic crisis for pensions and pension policy in Europe. <i>Global Social Policy</i> , 12(3), 246-265.	0	0	8	21		
	Ebbinghaus, B., & Whiteside, N. (2012). Shifting responsibilities in Western European pension systems: What future for social models?. <i>Global Social Policy</i> , 12(3), 266-282.	0	0	3	10		
	Glassner, V., Keune, M., & Marginson, P. (2011). Collective bargaining in a time of crisis: developments in the private sector in Europe. <i>Transfer: European review of labour and research</i> , 17(3), 303-322.	0	0	14	38		
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	Barbier, J. C., & Colomb, F. (2012). EU Law as Janus bifrons, a sociological approach to "Social Europe". <i>EUROPEAN INTEGRATION ONLINE PAPERS-EIOP</i> , 16.	3	3	3	5		

	Barbier, Jean-Claude (ed.). (2012). 'EU Law, Governance and Social Policy', European Integration online Papers (EIoP), Special Mini-Issue 1, Vol. 16.	3	0	0	0			
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	Marginson, P., & Keune, M. (2012). European social dialogue as multi-level governance: Towards more autonomy and new dependencies. European Integration online Papers (EIoP), Vol. 16.	3	0	1	2			
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	Crouch, C. (2012). National Varieties of Labour Market Exposure. In Morgan, G. and Whitley, R. (eds). Capitalism and Capitalisms in the Twenty-First Century. Oxford: Oxford University Press.		1				1	
	Whiteside, N. (2011). Creating public value: the case of pensions. In J. Benington and M.E. Moore (eds) Public Value (pp. 74-85). Basingstoke, UK: Macmillan Palgrave.		1				1	
	Whiteside, N. (2012). Britain's Pensions. In D. Natali (ed.) The New Pensions Mix: supplementary schemes in Europe. Brussels: Peter Lang.		1				0	
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	Conen, W. S., Henkens, K., & Schippers, J. J. (2011). Are employers changing their behavior toward older workers? An analysis of employers' surveys 2000-2009. Journal of Aging & Social Policy, 23(2), 141-158.	4	0	0	28		
	Conen, W.S. Europese werkgevers en vergrijzing op de werkvloer; de visie van Nederlandse werkgevers in Europees perspectief Demos, bulletin over bevolking en samenleving	0	0	0	2		
	Dalen, H. V., Ederveen, S., & Henkens, C. J. I. M. (2008). De productiviteit van de oudere werknemer. Economisch Statistische Berichten, 93.	0	0	0	0		

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Ehlers, A., Naegele, G., & Reichert, M. (2011). Volunteering by older people in the EU.	0	0	0	10		
Henkens, C. J. I. M. (2010). Pensioen in beweging: over sociologische aspecten van langer werken.	0	0	0	1		
Henkens, C. J. I. M., Solinge, V. H., & Dalen, V. H. (2009). Doorstarten na pensioen. Gids voor Personeelsmanagement: vaktijdschrift voor de HR professional.	0	0	0	0		
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Henkens, K., Solinge, H. V., & Dalen, H. V. (2009). Beslissingen rond langer werken: de onzichtbare drempels voor een later pensioen. Tijdschrift voor HRM, 3, 64-79.	0	0	0	0		
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Hershey, D. A., Henkens, K., & Van Dalen, H. P. (2009). What Drives Pension Worries in Europe? A Multilevel Analysis.	2	0	9	13		
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Principi, A., Chiatti, C., & Lamura, G. (2012). Motivations of older volunteers in three European countries. International	3	3	1	4		

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Principi, A., Chiatti, C., Lamura, G., & Frerichs, F. (2012). The engagement of older people in civil society organizations. <i>Educational Gerontology, 38</i> (2), 83-106.	3	6	4	10				
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van Dalen, H. P., Henkens, C. J. I. M., & Schippers, J. (2010). De lange mars van besef naar beleid: Werkgevers en (hun) oudere werknemers. <i>Handboek HRM in de praktijk, (48)</i> , 1-26.	0	0	0	0				
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Van Dalen, H. P., Henkens, K., & Schippers, J. (2009). Dealing with older workers in Europe: a comparative survey of employers' attitudes and actions. <i>Journal of european social policy, 19</i> (1), 47-60.	1	24	34	79				
Van Dalen, H. P., Henkens, K., & Schippers, J. (2010). How do employers cope with an ageing workforce? Views from employers and employees. <i>Demographic Research, 22</i> (32), 1015-1036.	2	0	0	29				
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van Dalen, H. P., Henkens, K., & Schippers, J. J. (2008). Leeftijdsbewust personeelsbeleid van Nederlandse werkgevers mist doel. <i>Kwartaalschrift Economie, 5</i> (1), 21-45.	0	0	0	1				
Van Dalen, H. P., Henkens, K., Henderikse, W., & Schippers, J. (2006). Dealing with an ageing labour force: What do European Employers expect and do?. <i>NiDi Report, (73)</i> .	0	0	0	28				
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Henkens, K., & Schippers, J. (2008). Labour market policies regarding older workers in the Netherlands. <i>Ageing labour forces: promises and prospects, 141-57</i> .							0	
Schippers, J. Extending work lives in Europe: employers' opinions and actions In: K. Busch et al. (Eds.). <i>Socially imbalanced Europe. Socio-political proposals in times of crisis</i>							0	
Frerichs, Policy of active ageing in employment in the EU - challenges and prospects. In: Busch, K. et al (eds). <i>Socially unbalanced Europe. Socio-Political proposals in times of crisis</i> .							0	
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	Camroux, d. (2012). Regionalism in Asia as Disguised Multilateralism : A Critical Analysis of the East-Asia Summit and the Trans-Pacific Partnership. The International Spectator, 47(1):97-115	0	0	0	5				
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	Řiháčková, V., & Weiss, T. (2010). Promoting Multilateralism? Conceptualizing Multilateralism in the Czech Foreign Policy. Perspectives. Review of International Affairs, (1), 5-21.	0	0	0	1				
	Olivier, G. (2010). Regionalism in Africa: cooperation without integration	0	0	0	5				
	Pirozzi, N. (2010). Towards an Effective Africa–EU Partnership on Peace and Security: Rhetoric or Facts?. The International Spectator, 45(2), 85-101.	0	0	5	6				
	Olivier, G. (2011). From Colonialism to Partnership in Africa–Europe Relations?. The International Spectator, 46(1), 53-67.	0	0	0	4				
	Pirozzi, N. (2010). The EU's contribution to the effectiveness of the UN Security Council: representation, coordination and outreach. Documenti IAI,1014.	0	0	0	4				
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	Fioramonti, L. (2012). Conclusion–Building Regions from Below: Has the Time Come for Regionalism 2.0?. The International Spectator, 47(1), 151-160.							1	
	Camroux, D. (2012). regionalism in asia as Disguised Multilateralism: a Critical analysis of the East asia Summit and the Trans-Pacific Partnership. The International Spectator, 47(1), 97-115.							1	
	Šlosarčík, I. (2010). Politický a právní rámec evropské integrace [Political and Legal Framework of the European Integration] - Wolters Kluwer							1	
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	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	11						13	0

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EFIGE	Joseph Alba, Jung Hur, and Donghyun Park. (2010). Do Hub-and-Spoke Free Trade Agreements Increase Trade? A Panel Data Analysis. No. 46. ADB Working Paper Series on Regional Economic Integration.	3	0	0	0			
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	Tax credit, exports and regional disparity: microevidence from Hungary -(with Péter Harasztosi), EFIGE Working Paper#56, August 2012							1
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	Klaus Desmet & Esteban Rossi-Hansberg, 2010. "On Spatial Dynamics," Journal of Regional Science, Wiley Blackwell, vol. 50(1), pages 43-6							1
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EUGRASP	Abass, A. (2012) 'The African Union and the responsibility to protect: principles and limitations', in J. Hoffman and A. Francis Baert. (2011) Book Review of Pace edited volume. Journal of Common Market Studies	1	3	2	7				
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	George Christou and Seamus Simpson (2011) The EU's Commitment to Effective Multilateralism in the Field of Security: Theory and Practice . Journal of European Public Policy	0	0	0	9				
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Sijbren de Jong, Steven Sterkx & Jan Wouters (2010) The EU as a Regional Actor: A Framework for Analysis							1
Sijbren de Jong, Steven Sterkx & Jan Wouters (2010) The EU as a Regional Actor: Regional Conflicts							1
Sijbren de Jong, Steven Sterkx & Jan Wouters (2010) The EU as a Regional Actor: Energy Security & Climate Change							1
Sijbren de Jong, Steven Sterkx & Jan Wouters (2010) The EU as a Regional Actor: Terrorism							1
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Sijbren de Jong, Steven Sterkx & Jan Wouters (2010) The EU as a Regional Actor: Human Rights							1
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	Michael Schulz & Mahmoud Miari Palestinian Public Opinion and the EU. 2012						1
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	TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	5				16	102

ICATSEM	Amable B., Demmou L. and Ledezma I. (2009), Product Market Regulation, Innovation and Distance to Frontier, Industrial and Corporate Change.	2	5	10	32		
	Andreosso-O'Callaghan, B., and H. Lenihan Responding to the Crisis: Are policies aimed at a strong indigenous industrial base a necessary condition for sustainable economic growth? (2011) Policy Studies, 32 (4), 325-345, with H. Lenihan.	4	3	3	6		
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	Nicolai T.W. (2013) Investigating the MATSim warm and hot start capability, SustainCity							1
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	(2011) <i>Diasporaengagement für Entwicklung und Frieden. Handlungsspielräume und Kapazitäten der äthiopischen Diaspora in Deutschland</i> . Tatjana Baraulina, Axel Kreienbrink and Andrea Riestler, eds. <i>Potenziale der</i>									1

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SIMPATIC	Takalo, T. Tanayama, T. Toivanen, O. (2013). Market failures and the additional effects of public support to private R&D: Theory and empirical implications. International Journal of Industrial Organization, 31, 634-642.	2	0	2	9		

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Remerge: regression-based record linkage with an application to PATSTAT						1
A scaleable approach to emissions-innovation record linkage						1
A flexible, scaleable approach to the international patent 'name game						1
TOTALS (articles / books or chapters / others)	3				1	4

Annex 5: Webometric Analysis

The term has been used for measuring impact of academic institutions and projects using hyperlink analysis.^{51,52} What has often be compared is the number of in-links to an academic institution to the number of citations publications of researchers from this institution, both indicating some awareness or visibility in the community. What can also be analyzed are the outgoing links. In-links and out-links define the websphere of a unit, organization, person, institution or project having an appearance on the web.

One motivation for our webometric exploration was that visibility on the web is one requirement for EC funding. We all know that proper filling websites during the project is not easy, and that maintaining a project websites after the project is finished is another issue. Still a look at websites reveals another fingerprint of the dissemination activity of projects, which is one important pre-condition for having an impact.

We started with a list of 133 projects both from FP6 and FP7. We complemented the list of websites by a manual search (involving Google and trial-and-error) for missing, additional and moved project websites. Eventually, we build a list of 238 URLs. Those URLs concern 218 projects out of the set of 222 projects, IMPACT-EV originally started with. That means that 98% of all projects have a website. We treated this sample of project as a pilot.

In a next step we run different webometric analysis, using tools of Mike Thelwall's group. Webometric Analyst and Socscibot are two of the analysis tools from the Statistical Cybermetrics Research Group, University of Wolverhampton, UK (<http://webometrics.wlv.ac.uk/index.html>). Roughly speaking Webometric Analyst is used to analyse links to websites (incoming links), while Socscibot analyses links from websites (outgoing links). Both work with the MicroSoft' Bing search engine for gathering data and have build-in analysis functions. Results of webanalysis are output in machine-readable txt-files and human-friendly html pages. At the end we decided not to extend this study for the total population of projects analysed by Impact-EV. The mian reason to freeze the webometric analysis as a pilot only was the fact that we did not find many surprising results, or insights we thought of greater value. But, we still would like to share some of the experiments.

⁵¹ Scharnhorst, A., P. Wouters, and P. van den Besselaar (Eds.) (2006): *What does the Web represent? From virtual ethnography to web indicators*, Special issue of *Cybermetrics* 10(1), Paper 0 (See URL <http://www.cindoc.csic.es/cybermetrics/vol10iss1.html>)

⁵² Thelwall, M. (2009). *Introduction to Webometrics: Quantitative Web Research for the Social Sciences*. San Rafael, CA: Morgan & Claypool.

1.1. Websites alive

Response of ImpactEV project websites. Accessed August 5 2014. FP6 projects (left) and FP7 projects (right).

Total projects: 222	Error Response Codes	26 websites in total were not accessible at the time of testing, out of which 9 were websites of projects with more than one website.
-----	-----	
4 projects with 0 websites	400 Bad request	
197 projects with 1 website	403 Forbidden	
19 projects with 2 websites	404 Not Found	
2 projects with 3 websites	500 Internal Server Error	22 projects had no accessible website at all.
	503 Service Temporarily Unavailable	

Figure 1: Visualization of the responses of websites from FP6 (left) and FP7 (right)

Figure 1 shows the accessibility of websites from FP 6 and FP 7 projects. At the time of the testing (August 2014), 26 websites in total were not accessible. From FP6 projects 92% and from FP7 90% responded back.

Another visualization (Figure 2) shows the responses of those 133 websites which were also recorded in the open CORDIS data.

Response of project websites

Figure 2: Responses for the 133 projects

1.2. Webometric impact

What is meant by impact here is the number of in-links to a website.

Figure 3: Distribution of the inlinks over websites

Figure 3 shows the number of projects (y axe) which have x incoming links. This is actually a snapshot from an html file (wi_histogram.html, uploaded to WP 3). If you start the html file in your browser, you can mouse over the graphics, and see the projects. A large number of in-links can also say something about the web-sphere policy a project did or how well did they promote themselves on the web. Figure 3 displays all projects with more than 70 inlinks from external sites, that means we excluded links from the same site or domain. Not unexpectedly for hyperlink networks, we see a skew distribution. Few projects have a large number (>200) of inlinks.

To also display the projects themselves we choose a bubble graph for all projects with more than 70 in-links (Figure 4). The size of the bubbles is related to the number of in-links. Projects with more in-links are placed in the center.

Figure 4: Bubble graph of projects with more than 70 in-links

Some projects of the success stories with concern to scientific impact (blue line) (MERCURY, INCLUD-ED) and political impact (red-line) (CAP-IRE, FINNOV, INCLUD-ED) are displayed in Figure 4.

Annex 6: Fact sheets of successful projects (social impact)

<h1 style="margin: 0;">AIDA</h1> <h2 style="margin: 0;">(Architectural design in Dialogue with dis-Ability)</h2>	
<p>ERC-2007-StG From: 2008-05-01 to 2013-10-31 EC Contribution: 1.2 million Euros http://architectuur.kuleuven.be/aida/index.php?ref=about</p>	
<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>This research project was based on the notion that, because of their specific interaction with space, people with particular dis-abilities are able to appreciate spatial qualities or detect misfits in the environment that most architects or other designers are not even aware of. This notion holds for sensory dis-abilities such as blindness or visual impairment, but also for mental dis-abilities like autism or Alzheimer's dementia. The experiences and subsequent insights of these disabled people, so it is argued, represent a considerable knowledge resource that would complement and enrich the professional expertise of architects and designers in general. This argument formed the basis for a methodological and theoretical exploration of a multi-sensorial design approach in architecture. On the one hand, a series of retrospective case studies were conducted to identify and describe the motives and elements that trigger or stimulate architects' attention for the multi-sensorial spatial experiences of people with dis-abilities when designing spaces. On the other hand, the research project investigated experimentally in real time to what extent design processes and products in architecture can be enriched by establishing a dialogue between the multi-sensorial knowing-in-action of people with dis-abilities and the expertise of professional architects/designers. In this way, the research project aimed to develop a more profound understanding of how the concept of Design for All can be realised in architectural practice. At least as important, however, was its contribution to innovation in architecture tout court. The research results gave a powerful impulse to quality improvement of the built environment by stimulating and supporting the development of innovative design concepts.</p>

<p>Contribution to Social impact</p>	<p>It contributed to the EU2020 target on Education.</p> <p>It influenced the renovation of university buildings to make them more inclusive in terms of acoustic comfort:</p> <p>This case study explores the notion of acoustic comfort for all in the context of university education. One auditorium, situated in a historic building and subject to renovation in the near future, is studied in detail: acoustic obstacles are identified in collaboration with users/experts and are measured in situ; specific interventions are proposed in consultation with building professionals, technicians and conservation specialists and are tested using dedicated acoustic simulation software.</p>
<p>Contact:</p>	<p>Ann Heylighen, ann.heylighen@asro.kuleuven.be, Tel: 32 16 32 17 41 // 32 16 3 21361, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (Belgium)</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IMPACT-EV Questionnaire - Other Reports - Main Researcher Interview - Other sources (book): Heylighen, A., Rychtáriková, M., Vermeir, G. (2010). Designing spaces for every listener. <i>Universal Access in the Information Society</i>, 9(3), pp. 283-292. - Scientific papers

ALACs

Promotion of Participation and Citizenship in Europe through the Advocacy and Legal Advice Centres (ALACs) of Transparency International

FP7-SSH-2007-1, BSG-CSO - Research for Civil Society Organisations (CSOs)

From 2009-09-01 to 2012-10-31, 225374

Total Cost: EUR 1 191 644 EU Contribution: EUR 999 804

Web: <http://www.soziologie.uni-konstanz.de/alacs/project/>
http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/93362_en.html

<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>The ALAC-project generated better scientific knowledge and a best practice - model of civil society activities in the anti-corruption coalition. With the focus on the Advocacy and Legal Advice Centres (ALACs) of Transparency International (TI), the leading CSO against corruption, the research project aims were enhancing civil society participation raising anti-corruption effectiveness, developing the advocacy for legal change at the national and EU level.</p> <p>Based on the insight that citizens participation and the values of integrity, accountability and transparency were crucial components of fighting corruption, the project was designed to promote the ALACs both as a management tool of a bottom-up anti-corruption work and citizens participation mechanism.</p> <p>The goal of developing an advanced ALAC-methodology as a new model for co-operation between citizens, CSOs and researchers was to meet the challenge of devising policies that raise the level of citizens' participation and empowerment. Combining action-research and practical implementation the project itself designed as a process of organizational learning intended to have direct impact on the work of Transparency International and its partner organizations in Europe and all over the world.</p>
<p>Contribution to</p>	<p>It contributed to the EU2020 target on Employment: Creation of employment due to new services promoted in ALAC's offices.</p> <p>It also contributed to other societal objectives (EU's Justice and Home Affairs</p>

Social impact	Agenda 2020): Providing a new service in ALAC's offices (free legal advice and support to victims, whistle-blowers and witnesses of corruption), which resulted in the increase of complaints, meaning the improvement of citizen participation in the fight against corruption.
Contact	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Prof. Dr. Dirk Tänzler, Dirk.Taenzler@uni-konstanz.de University of Konstanz</p>
Sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC Scientific Officer Interview - ALAC's Final Report (including workforce data) - Other Reports - Main researcher Interview - Interview with collaborator from Transparency International - Other sources: <p>Published in the web "capacity4". Retrieved from: http://capacity4dev.ec.europa.eu/article/citizens-become-actors-fight-against-corruption</p> <p>EU Justice Agenda 2020: COM (2014) 154 final. <i>Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions. An open and secure Europe: making it happen.</i> Retrieved from: http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/home-affairs/e-library/documents/basic-documents/docs/an-open-and-secure-europe-making-it-happen-en.pdf</p> <p>NC's – National Chapters of Transparency International. NC's= Transparency International consists of more than 100 chapters – locally established, independent organizations – that fight corruption in their respective countries</p>

ASPA

Activating Senior Potential in Ageing Europe

FP7-SSH-2007-1, CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project

From 2008-02-01 **to** 2011-06-30, 216289

Total Cost: EUR 1 977 003,3 **EU Contribution:** EUR 1 489 803

Web: <http://www.aspa-eu.com/>

http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/88423_en.html

Aim & General information

The dejuvenation and ageing of Europe's population puts society for some major challenges. The development towards a knowledge-based society requires continued investment in new knowledge and skills. Given the ageing of the population and low fertility rates it also requires high(er) participation rates of females and people over fifty. So far, employers' and governments' policies had focused on human capital investments for the younger age categories and have stimulated older workers to retire at a relatively early age, instead of investing in sustainable workers throughout the life course. This project examined the forces and mechanisms behind employers' and governments' behaviour and the resulting societal arrangements. To that aim it was used large-scale surveys for the analyses of employers' behaviour and desk research and interviews to map government behaviour. Statistical and focus group analyses were also used to get insight in the participation and activity rates of people between 50 to 70. The project also identified good practices at the company level and at the level of government policies that contribute to continuous investment in knowledge and skills throughout the life course, resulting in high activity rates for people between 50 and 70.

The aim of the project was threefold: (1) The first aim was to get insight on the influence of organisational behaviour, organisational and public policies on the use of senior potential (men and women) over fifty; (2) The second aim was to get insight into activity rates of people between 50 and 70, both in paid labour and unpaid activities (in particular care and volunteer work), related to policies with respect to human capital investments over the life course; and, (3) To identify policy strategies for organisations (firms and civil society organisations) and governments to stimulate the participation of older adults and secure human capital investments over the life course based on a comparison of different national strategies and good practices at the organisational level.

<p>Contributions to Social impact</p>	<p>It contributed to the EU2020 target on Employment.</p> <p>Thanks to the development of the project, the employers' behaviours towards the target group (older people) may have changed. Employers went to the final conference and asked for part of the report because they were very interested. Also, researchers gave training to Union employers and suggested them to discuss how to extend their careers. In the Netherlands, they spoke with Beneficial and Reintegration organizations and advise them how to consider social media to reintegrate workers.</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Prof. Dr Joop J. Schippers, Utrecht University School of Economics</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Main Researcher Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents) <p>Final Report Summary – ASPA: Activating Senior Potential in Ageing Europe</p> <p>http://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/56032_en.pdf</p> <p>European Policy brief: Age and Stereotypes http://www.aspa-eu.com/FP7%20Policy%20Brief%203%20April%202011.pdf</p>

<h2 style="margin: 0;">CSEYHP</h2> <h3 style="margin: 0;">Combating social exclusion among young homeless populations: a comparative investigation of homeless paths and reinsertion programmes for young men and women of different ethnic and migrant statuses</h3>	
<p>FP7-SSH-2007-1, CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project From 2008-05-01 to 2011-04-30, 217223 Total Cost: EUR 1 010 016 EU Contribution: EUR 770 173 Web: https://www.movisie.com/combating-youth-homelessness http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/88909_en.html</p>	
<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>The aim of the CSEYHP project was to combat social exclusion and poverty among young homeless people and those at risk of homelessness by gaining in-depth knowledge of the life trajectories of different young homeless populations in four countries – Netherlands, Portugal, Czech Republic and the United Kingdom - and to explore the effectiveness of early intervention and reinsertion programmes. Methodologies used include literature reviews, secondary data analysis, interviews with NGOs, and engaging homeless and ex-homeless young people as co-researchers, interviewing young homeless people, and observing and testing methodologies of intervention and case management in national contexts.</p>

<p>Contributions to Social impact</p>	<p>Contributions to poverty and social exclusion reduction target:</p> <p>Provision of housing opportunities and family mediation for youth who ran away from home, preventing youth homelessness:</p> <p>Currently there are pilots in three regions in Netherlands (The Hague, Groningen and Zeeland) of Nightstop, an effective approach that was presented during the CSEYHP project. It offers a safe time-out to young people who have run away from home, staying with host families instead of in shelters which often have a negative impact on them. In the meantime family mediation is implemented aimed at preventing youth homelessness or facilitating the return of young homeless people to their families, or, at least, promoting a more amiable departure in case the young person cannot stay home any longer. This mediation approach is from UK, and is being piloted and adapted to Netherlands.</p> <p>The Christian Union group in Amersfoort hands have set up together a program called <i>Tussenstation</i> (transit station), an initiative inspired on the results from CSEYHP research. The idea is that residents of Amersfoort offer a room for (homeless) people. These are young people who leave the social care but have no accommodation. It is a temporary solution whereby the landlords have no risk that these young people go off the rails or do not want to leave. Many institutions that provide social care and sheltered housing cannot handle the influx. The waiting time for social housing is 3 to 5 years. If they have income or benefits, they will pay rent. The social care institution remains responsible for the risks and the guidance of these lodgers, until they are assigned a social housing. If, within six months no social housing available, then the lodgers will move to another room in the network. It was only possible to pay one young woman directly because she was a student on a grant but this payment was very important – it allowed her to pay all her rent arrears and prevented her becoming evicted and homeless again and allowed her to remain in college. The other young people were rewarded with computers and payments for internet access that would help their studies in the next three years.</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Thea Meinema, t.meinema@movisie.nl MOVISIE- NL</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Main Researcher Interview - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents)

DESAFIO

Democratization of Water and Sanitation Governance by Means of Socio-Technical Innovation

FP7-SSH-2012-2 / CP-FP-SICA - Small/medium-scale focused research project for specific cooperation actions dedicated to international cooperation partner countries (SICA)

From 2013-02-01 **to** 2015-07-31, 320303

Total Cost: EUR 1 326 374,72 **EU Contribution:** EUR 999 972,8

Web: <http://desafioglobal.org/es/>
http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/106722_en.html

Aim & General information	<p>The main aim of the project is to make a contribution towards tackling what is arguably one of the major challenges facing Brazil -and Latin American and Caribbean countries more generally- in the twenty-first century: eradicating structural social inequality in the access to essential water and sanitation services (WSS).</p>
Contribution to Social impact	<p>Contributions to poverty and social exclusion reduction target:</p> <p>Improving the quality of water management and generating involvement of local communities in water management and systems.</p> <p>The project is successful in achieving the involvement of the communities in the management of water. In Colombia, local women and men have been taught to maintain and run wastewater and water supply systems themselves. In Argentina, a school-based science project is teaching children how to measure levels of arsenic contamination in water. The enthusiastic children are passing on their knowledge to parents and neighbours, helping to raise awareness on how to detect and deal with health-threatening water contamination¹.The project works with the communities while they are implementing the systems for accessing water. The project is making visible the situation and helping communities to improve their access to clean water.</p>

<p>Contact</p>	<p>José Esteban Castro, esteban.castro@ncl.ac.uk Newcastle University</p>
<p>Sources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Main Researcher Interview - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents) - Webpage documents. Posters, Flyers. Extracted from: <p>http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/news/sanitation-gets-social</p>

DIASPEACE

Diasporas for Peace: Patterns, Trends and Potential of Long-distance Diaspora Involvement in Conflict Settings. Case studies from the Horn of Africa.

FP7-SSH-2007-1, CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project

From 2008-03-01 to 2011-02-28, 225408

Total Cost: EUR 1 829 480 EU Contribution: EUR 1 331 530

Web: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/89503_en.html

Aim & General information	<p>DIASPEACE involved case studies from the Horn of Africa (which includes the countries of Somalia, Ethiopia, Eritrea and Djibouti) in order to shed light on the role that Diaspora plays on both conflict and peace in the home country.</p> <p>The project endeavoured to generate policy-relevant, evidence-based knowledge on how exiled populations from conflict regions play into the dynamics of conflict and peace in their countries of origin. DIASPEACE had an empirical focus on diaspora networks operating in Europe, which extend their transnational activities to the Horn of Africa. This is a region where decades of violent conflict have resulted in state collapse and the dispersal of more than two million people. The project involved six partners from Europe and two from the Horn of Africa, and conducted field research in both Europe and Africa.</p>
Contributions to Social impact	<p>Contributions to poverty and social exclusion reduction target:</p> <p>Increase of the Public development aid and its evaluation. The major impact of DIASPEACE was the change in the discourse of the concept of the role of the diaspora in the European societies, for northern countries and Germany. Public development aid, channelled through diaspora organizations has increased and its evaluation is better, as a major consequence of this project. DIASPEACE also contributed to make more visible the involvement of diasporas in peace and development, especially in the case of individuals from the second generation.</p>

<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Liisa Laakso, liisa.laakso@helsinki.fi University of Helsinki</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Main Researcher Interview - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents (webpages official documents) <p>http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/89503_en.html http://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/45861_en.html</p> <p>Other sources: http://www.prio.org/Projects/Project/?x=840</p> <p>¹More information: Sinatti, Giulia & Cindy Horst (2014) Migrants as agents of development: Diaspora engagement discourse and practice in Europe, <i>Ethnicities</i> 14(2). DOI: 10.1177/1468796814530120 Horst, Cindy (2013) The depoliticization of diasporas from the Horn of Africa: From refugees to transnational aid workers. <i>African Studies</i> 72(2), 228–245.</p>

EURESCL

Slave Trade Slavery Abolitions and their Legacies in European Histories and Identities

FP7-SSH-2007-1, CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project
From 2008-03-01 to 2012-08-31, 217624
Total Cost: EUR 2 676 044,4 **EU Contribution:** EUR 1 490 171
Web: <http://www.eurescl.eu/>
http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/89509_en.html

Aim & General information	<p>This project aimed to analyse trafficking and slavery in the history of Europe from a critic point of view. EURESCL has put trafficking and slavery in the Mediterranean and Atlantic in the European identity construction process (both from the political aspect, economic, social, cultural, intellectual, memorial and educational), and studied the update of social relations constructed from the experiences and representations from trafficking and slavery in the Atlantic. EURESCL provided a study about the multiple genealogy of <i>the question "noire"</i> and <i>"afro-descendants"</i> among historians, geographers, sociologists, anthropologists, political scientists, lawyers and educators.</p>
Contributions to Social impact	<p>Contributions to poverty and social exclusion reduction target:</p> <p>Increase awareness on slavery. The main contribution of this project has been making visible for the European society that Europe was also part of slave trade, as other World regions, such America. EURESCL has disseminate and promoted the study of trafficking and slavery in the scientific community, both in Europe and in the countries where the investigation took place, by setting up research networks, workshops, festivals, expositions, and by promoting the creation of research institutes in Senegal and Haiti. The project has connected different historiographies relating to slavery and the slave trade through project seminars. EURESCL developed the first multilingual and multidisciplinary online educational tool related to the slave and slavery, including resources to teach the subject of slavery and the slave trade in the French, Haitian and Senegalese education systems. They also promoted film festivals to disseminate their findings to a wide audience.</p>

<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Myriam Cottias, myriam.cottias@ehess.fr CNRS</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents) <p>¹More information: Shoman, A. (2010). Reflections on Ethnicity and Nation in Belize. <i>Cuaderno de Trabajo Afrodesc</i>, (9). Retrieved from: http://www.ird.fr/afrodesc/IMG/pdf/Cuaderno9-SHOMAN-FINAL.pdf</p> <p>Poiret, C., Hoffmann, O., & Audebert, C. (2011). Éditorial: Contextualiser pour mieux conceptualiser la racialisation. <i>Revue Européenne des migrations internationales</i>, 27(1), 7-16.</p>

INCLUD-ED

Strategies for inclusion and social cohesion in Europe from education

From 02-nov-2006 to 01-nov-2011
 FP6-SSH Priority 7, CP-IP – Integrated project
From 2006-11-02 to 2011-11-01
Website: <http://creaub.info/included/>
http://cordis.europa.eu/news/rcn/35703_en.html

Aim & General information

The five-year project INCLUD-ED ('Strategies for Inclusion and Social Cohesion in Europe from Education') has made significant progress in educational results, having first addressed the various characteristics of the school systems. While also accessing the educational reforms, which are generating high and low rates of educational and social exclusion. They also analysed the mechanism from educational practices, which were believed to decrease the rates of school failure and the practices that are increasing them.

The project was supported by researchers from 14 Member States. As part of it an in-depth analyses was conducted on education and socio-economic background of children. Their research found that a child's background did not stand in the way of their educational achievement.

Armed with this information, the INCLUD-ED project team could then provide valuable recommendations, guidelines and tools. Their detailed analysis led to the identification of 'Successful Educational Actions' (SEAs) and 'Integrative Successful Actions' (ISAs), which were then implemented in various schools across Europe with noteworthy results.

Contribution to Social impact

Contributions to education target: Increased academic attainment in schools implementing the successful actions accomplished in the project: High increase in the score in La Paz Primary School (highly deprived area, Albacete): Increase of the scores in all subjects in standardised tests in one academic year (9 year old pupils). -Increase the scores in mathematics from 1 to 3 (out of 5) in the standardised tests. -Increase the scores in cultural and artistic skills, social and

	<p>citizenship skills, learning to learn, autonomy, and emotional skills from 2 to 3 (out of 5) in the standardised tests.</p> <p>Contributions to employment target: Creation of employment in locations of extreme poverty. Cooperative Miguel Fenollera in La Milagrosa neighbourhood, based on successful actions identified by the INCLUD-ED project: 586 jobs in one of the poorest neighbourhoods in southern Europe. Miguel Fenollera cooperative: 10 permanent positions in the cooperative, 570 contracts in the agricultural sector and 6 in the educational sector.</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Dr Ramón Flecha García ramon.flecha@ub.edu University of Barcelona</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -IMPACT-EV Questionnaire - Final Report - Other Reports - Other documents (EC Documents) <p style="text-align: center;">Success Stories – European Commission (the only project from SSH): http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-11-520_en.htm</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Other documents: Books and scientific papers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flecha, R. (Ed.). (2015). Successful Educational Actions for Inclusion and Social Cohesion in Europe. Netherlands: Springer. - Flecha, R., & Soler. M. (2013). Cambridge Journal of Education, 3(44). - Other Documents (Official documents and reports. Public bodies, private organizations).

LOCALISE

Local Worlds of Social Cohesion. The Local Dimension of Integrated Social and Employment Policies

FP7-SSH-2010-2, CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project

From 2011-07-01 to 2014-06-30, 99622

Total Cost: EUR 1 780 896.32 **EU Contribution:** EUR 1 415 059

Web: <http://www.localise-research.eu/>

http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/99622_en.html

Aim & General information

Radical changes in the local governance of social cohesion in many Member States of the European Union were the focus of LOCALISE's research on the organisational challenges of an integrated social and employment policy. The multiple needs of the most vulnerable groups in society have required the integration of formerly separate policy fields. This has created positive dynamics for reducing social inequalities, fostering social cohesion and enhancing labour market participation – the crucial objectives of the new Europe 2020 Strategy. LOCALISE addressed questions like how do different institutional contexts influence local worlds of social cohesion? How do local actors deal with the conflicts and dilemmas caused by integrated social cohesion policies? What impact do these policies have on social inequality and the conception of social citizenship?

The project used an integrating approach with experienced partners in European and Social Policy research. LOCALISE created a critical mass of research in three key areas: a) analysing how European programmes, national governance patterns and the regional socio-economic context affect the local governance of social cohesion; b) studying how 18 local entities in six European countries (France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Sweden and United Kingdom) cope with the challenges of an integrated social cohesion policy; c) analysing the impact of these policies on social inequalities, citizenship and the most vulnerable social groups.

The main outcomes of the project were the training of young researchers, analysis of the different kinds of social policy impacts, and generation of new knowledge in the field of social cohesion and local governance.

<p>Contributions to Social impact</p>	<p>Contributions to employment target:</p> <p>The project identified examples of best practices that might contribute to the employment target. We could highlight the following practices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Hub Contract in Edinburgh (UK) is a platform for collaboration, networking and information exchange among professionals. It's a legal basis for collaboration among various actors who are involved in the implementation of municipal employment policies with the main objective to give holistic support for unemployed. - Välfärd i Nacka in Nacka (Sweden) is an institutionalised platform for cooperation between organisations with a strong focus on self-entrepreneurship employers and NGOs. Nowadays it is used as a tool to overcome problems at the interfaces between labour market instruments and local social services. - The missions locales pour l'insertion professionnelle des jeunes (France). It is a national law, coordinated at the regional level. It was designed to provide one-stop services to youth with strong implementation in Bordeaux. The main objective is to incorporate low qualified youngsters (16 to 25) to the labour market. <p>These best practices have been disseminated through different actions along the project. For instance, through the European Policy Brief "How the governance of employment systems affects social cohesion: lessons and local best practices from six European Countries" (July 2014) and different presentations in international forums, as for instance: the Policy Conference of the Project in Brussels in June 2014.</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Prof. Dr. Martin Heidenreich, martin.heidenreich@uni-oldenburg.de University of Oldenburg</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IMPACT-EV Questionnaire - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Main Researcher Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents) <p>The European Policy Brief "How the governance of employment systems affects social cohesion: lessons and local best practices from six European Countries" http://ec.europa.eu/research/social-sciences/pdf/policy_briefs/policy-briefs-localise072014.pdf</p> <p>The Policy Conference of LOCALISE in Brussels http://www.localise-research.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/Heidenreich.pdf</p>

<h2 style="margin: 0;">MAXCAP</h2> <h3 style="margin: 0;">Maximizing the integration capacity of the European Union: Lessons and prospects for enlargement and beyond</h3>	
<p>FP7-SSH-2012-2</p> <p>CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project</p> <p>Total cost: 2 994 581,8 EC Contribution: 2 407 522</p> <p>From: 01/04/2013 to 31/03/2016</p> <p>http://www.maxcap-project.eu</p>	
<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>The ‘big bang enlargement’ of the European Union (EU) has nurtured vivid debates among both academics and practitioners about the consequences of ‘an ever larger Union’ for the EU’s integration capacity. The research project MAXCAP started with a critical analysis of the effects of the 2004-2007 enlargements on stability, democracy and prosperity of candidate countries, on the one hand, and the EU’s institutions, on the other. Then it will investigate how the EU can maximize its integration capacity for current and future enlargements. Adopting an inter-disciplinary and mixed methods approach that combines desk research, in-depth interviews and Q-methodology, MAXCAP objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) explain the effects of the EU’s integration modes and strategies on democracy and socio-economic development in the new members, candidates and neighbourhood countries; b) inquire into the relationship between the widening and deepening of the EU by establishing conditions for effective decision-making and implementation in an enlarged EU; c) identify the social limits to the EU’s integration capacity related to citizens’ perceptions of the last and future enlargements; d) study the EU’s current and past negotiation strategies in the context of enlargement and investigate to what extent they need to be adjusted to changing conditions in the EU and the candidate countries; e) examine how the EU employs different modes of integrating countries with highly diverse economic powers, democratic qualities of governance, and institutional capacities and f) Assess whether alternative models, such as the European Neighbourhood Policy, can be successful in bringing countries closer to the EU. <p>MAXCAP features a nine-partner consortium of academic, policy, dissemination and management excellence will create new and strengthen existing links within and between the academic and the policy world on matters relating to the current and future enlargement</p>

	of the EU.
Contribution to Social impact	Contribution to other targets (EU Enlargement): Engagement of civil society in the process of enlargement of the EU. The project allowed citizen and grassroots movements, especially through the Balkan Civil Society Development Network (BCSDN) and several local events, to raise their concerns and make their interests be heard.
Contact	Project Coordinator: Tanja A. Börzel, europe@zedat.fu-berlin.de Free University Berlin
Sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IMPACT-EV Questionnaire - Final Report - Other Reports - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents (official documents)

<h1 style="margin: 0;">MEDPRO</h1> <h2 style="margin: 0;">Prospective Analysis for the Mediterranean Region</h2>	
<p>FP7-SSH-2009-A, CP-FP – Small or medium-scale focused research project</p> <p>From 2010-03-01 to 2013-02-28</p> <p>Total Cost: EUR 3 550 937,2 EU Contribution: EUR 2 647 330</p> <p>Web: http://www.medpro-foresight.eu/ http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/96292_en.html</p>	
<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>The aim of MEDPRO was to contribute to the reform process in the political, economic and social agendas of the countries in the southern and eastern Mediterranean region that participated within the Barcelona process. MEDPRO focused on geopolitics and governance, demography, ageing, migration, economic development, trade and investment, financial services and capital markets and human capital, education and development of skills. MEDPRO delivered the best available scientific underpinning for future policy decisions, both domestically and at EU level within the framework of the Union for the Mediterranean (UfM) – the successor to the Barcelona Process – as well as the EU European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) Programme.</p>
<p>Contributions to Social impact</p>	<p>Contributions to R+D target:</p> <p>The project launched the Euro-Mediterranean Economists' Association (EMEA) with the aim of monitoring and contributing to the reform processes in the political, economic and social agendas, therefore having a high potential social impact.</p> <p>The major social impact of MEDPRO has been building the opportunity to develop a Euro-Mediterranean collaboration to address uncertainty in this local-regional scenario, facing the challenges posed by social events such as the Arab Spring, i.e., the unbalance among countries due to differences in demography, health and ageing trends in terms of population, etc.</p> <p>In the frame of this project a spin-off company was created, posting 3 new job positions. In addition, the Euro-Mediterranean Economists' Association (EMEA) was created to disseminate the outputs of the project. EMEA's creation responds to a revived interest in the Southern and Eastern Mediterranean with the eruption of the "Arab Spring".</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Coordinator: Dr. Rym Ayadi, rym.ayadi@ceps.eu</p>

	Centre for European Policy Studies
Sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IMPACT-EV Questionnaire - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents) <p>Result in brief and report summaries: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/96292_en.html</p>

MEMOLA

MEDITERRANEAN MOUNTANIAN LANDSCAPES

FP7-SSH
From 01/01/2014 to 31/12/2017

<http://www.memolaproject.eu/>

<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>The project is an interdisciplinary approach to cultural landscapes of Mediterranean mountainous areas, taking as a central axis the historical study of two natural resources essential to generate agro-systems: water and soil. The proposal focuses on Sierra Nevada (Spain), Monti di Trapani (Italy), Colli Euganei (Italy) and Vjosa Valley (Albania).</p> <p>Conservation can be achieved through the exploitation of this heritage to generate environmental and cultural conservation strategies for sustainable development in rural areas; with the aim of protecting this cultural heritage and, at the same time, increasing and transmitting knowledge about it in order to benefit the local and wider European society.</p>
<p>Contribution to Social impact</p>	<p>Contributions to employment target:</p> <p>Excavation in Lanteira (Spain) – Increase of number of visitors to the area. Almost all the people from the nearby villages have come to visit the excavation, including all the students from the primary and secondary schools or local cultural, environmental and women associations. Hundreds of people have come to see the results.</p> <p>Fostering Agriculture: Rehabilitation of the traditional irrigation system of Barjas (Granada, Spain) (http://www.memolaproject.eu/sq/node/321)</p>

<p>Contact</p>	<p>Main researcher: José María Martín Civantos Campus Universitario de Cartuja C.P. 18071 (Granada) Granada +34 958249774 civantos@ugr.es</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main Researcher Interview - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents

<h1 style="margin: 0;">MIGROM</h1> <h2 style="margin: 0;">The Immigration of Romanian Roma to Western Europe: Causes, effects, and future engagement strategies.</h2>	
<p>FP7-SSH-2012-2, CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project From 2013-04-01 to 2017-03-3, 2379901</p> <p>Total Cost: EUR 3 278 504 EU Contribution: EUR 2 487 903</p> <p>Web: http://romani.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/migrom/ http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/106714_es.html</p>	
<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>The project investigated the experiences, motivations, and ambitions of Roma migrants from Romania who recently moved to Italy, France, Spain, and the UK, and the effect of migration on their own lives and on the lives of relations left behind in the home communities in Romania. It also investigated popular, media, and official reactions to Roma immigration.</p> <p>By involving assistants from the Roma communities and drawing on the expertise of an interdisciplinary team of leading scholars in Romani studies, the project delivered a much-needed ‘Ethnography of Roma Migration’: an innovative analysis of the causes and effects of Roma migration, an assessment of examples of good practice of integration of Roma migrants and a criteria schema for assessing good practice, a practical contribution to capacity building in Roma migrant communities, policy recommendations, and models for community engagement strategies.</p> <p>The project attempted to illuminate the Roma perspective on migration through a comparative investigation that was based in Roma communities and in Roma homes.</p>
<p>Contribution to Social impact</p>	<p>Contributions to employment target:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -It has promoted the employment of Roma people by the Manchester City Council (MCC). - Weekly drop-in sessions for Roma to assess needs and draft response and engagement strategies (adjustment into a new environment). % increase: In the first year 93 families accessed the drop-in session for advice and support, many of them on a regular basis (topics: tax returns, search for job opportunities, pay utility and Council Tax bills, register children at school, etc.).

Contact	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Yaron Matras, aron.matras@manchester.ac.uk University of Manchester</p>
Sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main Researcher Interview - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents) <p>Project documents: http://romani.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/migrom/docs/MigRom%20briefing%20Oct%202014.pdf Also its impact was mentioned by a EC Officer http://romani.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/migrom/docs/MigRom%20briefing%20Oct%202014.pdf</p>

MYPLACE

Memory, Youth, Political Legacy And Civic Engagement

FP7-SSH-2010-1, CP-IP - Large-scale integrating project
From 2011-06-01 **to** 2015-05-31, **266831**
Total Cost: EUR 9 968 172,4 **EU Contribution:** EUR 7 994 449
Web: <http://www.fp7-myplace.eu/>
http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/99645_en.html

Aim & General information	<p>MYPLACE explored how young people’s social participation is shaped by the shadows (past, present and future) of totalitarianism and populism in Europe. The far-right won substantial support in a number of EU member states - brought into sharp relief the challenge at the heart of the democratic project in Europe. Subsequent acts of right-wing extremist terrorism in Norway and Germany, the electoral success of Golden Dawn in Greece and the emergence of new ‘feet on the street’ movements like the English Defence League (EDL) have intensified scholarly and policy interest in the issue of right-wing extremism. MYPLACE started from the premise that these political trends are evident but neither ‘new’ nor the outcome of discrete national ‘political cultures’; they are rooted in a range of radical and populist political and philosophical traditions that are pan-European in nature and the popularity they currently enjoy is cyclical rather than novel. MYPLACE aimed to provide an honest and critical understanding of the potential of such movements to capture the political imagination of young Europeans today.</p>
Contributions to Social impact	<p>Contributions to poverty and social exclusion reduction target:</p> <p>Through the collaboration with museums, the project developed programmes to reach people from marginalized groups. They used workshops to develop competences like media, communicative and expressive skills, among other things. In this way the project contributed to raise the profile of young people, therefore significantly increasing their potential employability.</p>

<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Hilary Pilkington,</p> <p><u>hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk</u> University of Warwick –UK</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main Researcher Interview - Scientific Officer Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents) - Interview with Main Researcher and Project Manager - Official documents and Reports <p><u>http://www.fp7-myplace.eu/deliverables.php</u></p>

<h1 style="margin: 0;">POINT</h1> <h2 style="margin: 0;">Policy Influence of indicators</h2>	
<p>FP7-SSH-2007-1 CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project</p> <p>From 2008-04-01 to 2011-06-30, 217207</p> <p>Total Cost: EUR 1 916 259,33 EU Contribution: EUR 1 456 724</p> <p>Web: http://www.point-eufp7.info/ http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/89898_en.html</p>	
Aim & General information	<p>There has been an increase of the use of indicators in most areas of public policy. Indicators are employed to monitor policy performance and foster accountability within frameworks such as evidence based policy and New Public Management on the one hand, and to promote policy learning on the other. Attention of researchers and practitioners has so far focused primarily on the technical details of indicator design, while the role of indicators in policymaking has been a relatively little researched topic. Direct, instrumental use of indicators by policymakers seems, however, to be rather an exception than a rule, thus confirming findings concerning the role of research and expert knowledge in policymaking more generally.</p> <p>The overall aim of the project was to help find better ways of using these indicators in all aspects of policy, but with a thematic focus on the role of indicators in fostering and supporting change in areas of policy making towards 'Sustainable Development'.</p>
Contribution to Social impact	<p>Contributions to climate change target:</p> <p>The project influenced the motivation for renewing the Finnish Sustainable Development (SD) indicators, including potential users and actors from various sectors and levels of the society.</p>
Contact	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Pia Frederiksen, pfr@dmu.dk Aarhus University</p>
Sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Main Researcher Interview - Other documents (journal papers, official documents) <p>- Final Reports: http://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/143047_en.html http://cordis.europa.eu/publication/rcn/16830_en.html</p> <p>- Other reports: Review report on Beyond GDP indicators: categorisation, intentions and impacts. Deliverable 1.1 (BRAINPOOL Project).</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Researcher Interview- Other sources:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Jari Lyytimäki, Petri Tapio, Vilja Varho & Tarja Söderman (2013) The use, non-use and misuse of indicators in sustainability assessment and communication. <i>International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology</i>, 20:5, 385-393, DOI: 10.1080/13504509.2013.834524• Revision of Finnish sustainable development indicators. Viewpoints and suggestions from national indicator network. [In Finnish] Available from: http://www.ymparisto.fi/download.asp?contentid=124784&lan=fi• Lyytimäki, Jari (2011). Frameworks for the ex-ante impact assessment of sustainable development. Suggestion for the assessment tool. Reports of the Ministry of the Environment, Helsinki. [In print]• Frederiksen P. (2011) Use and influence of indicators in recent Danish water policy. NESS2011 Stockholm June 14-16 (Conference Presentation)
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<h1 style="margin: 0;">RESPECT</h1> <h2 style="margin: 0;">Towards a Topography of Tolerance and Equal Respect. A comparative study of policies for the distribution of public spaces in culturally diverse societies</h2>	
<p>FP7-SSH-2009-A CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project</p> <p>From 2010-01-01 to 2011-12-31, 244549</p> <p>Total Cost: EUR 1 722 980,4 EU Contribution: EUR 1 262 933</p> <p>Web: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/94003_en.html</p> <p style="text-align: center;">http://www.respect.iusspavia.it/</p>	
<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>Tolerance has been increasingly invoked as the inspiring ideal of a number of social policies in European democracies. The concession of linguistic rights to minorities, the promotion of policies of affirmative action and the distribution of public funds and spaces for building places for worship are just some examples of the many ways in which tolerance may be seen to inspire the political agenda of diverse European countries. To answer this question, the project tested the hypothesis that grounding tolerance on equal respect for persons may contribute to the development of spatial policies capable of resolving the tensions between tolerance and social cohesion in culturally diverse societies. In particular, the project pursued 4 objectives: (1) to develop a conceptual taxonomy to clarify the relations between tolerance, respect and spatial issues; (2) to study the ways in which appeals to tolerance have informed the development of spatial policies; (3) to investigate the influence of cultural diversities on the interpretations of tolerance in different national contexts; (4) to extrapolate from the above studies an overall view of the connections between tolerance and equal respect.</p>
<p>Contribution to Social impact</p>	<p>Contributions to other societal targets (increased cultural tolerance, respect and sensitivity with regards to minority groups):</p> <p>Achievement of proper dialogue in the process of building a mosque in Milan (public meeting with representatives of the City Council, Muslim communities and researchers):</p> <p>Brief Description: Organization a public meeting in Milan inviting a representative of the City Council, representatives of the Muslim communities, and some researchers. This meeting facilitated the dialogue between Milan City Council and representatives of the Muslim communities in the process of building a mosque. The matter concerning the presence of a purpose-built mosque in Milan had been debated for years, but a proper dialogue between the parties was only established through the project.</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Dr Emanuela Ceva, emanuela.ceva@unipv.it Institute for Advanced Study,</p>

	Università di Pavia.
Sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IMPACT-EV Questionnaire - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Main Researcher Interview 1. Other documents (journal papers, official documents)

SAMPLE

Small Area Methods for Poverty and Living Condition Estimates

FP7-SSH-2007-1, CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project

From 2008-03-01 **to** 2011-02-28, 217565

Total Cost: EUR 953 322,4 **EU Contribution:** EUR 774 972

Web: <http://www.sample-project.eu/>

http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/92010_en.html

Aim & General information	<p>The aim of SAMPLE project was to identify and develop new indicators and models for inequality and poverty with attention to social exclusion and deprivation, as well as to develop, implement models, measures and procedures for small area estimation of the traditional and new indicators and models.</p> <p>This goal was achieved using the EU-SILC survey data with the help of the local administrative databases. Local Government Agencies often have huge amount of administrative data to monitor some of the actions which witness situations of social exclusion and deprivation (social security claims for unemployment and eligibility for benefits from any of the programs Social Security administers) of households and citizens. The final goal of the project was to provide a dashboard of reliable indicators of poverty and deprivation defined at NUTS3, NUTS4 level, useful for Local Government Agencies. In the project, the EU-SILC sample was enlarged at NUTS4 or aggregation of NUTS4 level for the Tuscany (Italy) region.</p>
Contributions to Social impact	<p>Contributions to poverty and social exclusion reduction target:</p> <p>Involvement of civil society on the monitoring of poverty and social exclusion through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Within the SAMPLE project the first local Observatory on poverty, vulnerability and social exclusion was created. The focal achievements are: a formal agreement between the Province of Pisa and three local Caritas Agencies for a permanent monitoring of poverty and social exclusion, accessing to the data of Caritas Counselling Centres. Caritas is one of the most important international organizations that implements actions to

	<p>contrast poverty; the involvement of 252 stakeholders (institutions and third sector organizations) to create a local network of qualified “antennas” on the territory. The main instrument for their involvement has been a survey using the Delphi Method (http://www.sampleproject.eu/it/the-project/deliverables-docs.html - see D10 “Final Report task 1.4) and the participation at the development of the project software.</p> <p>- The creation of a mailing list of more than 200 stakeholders that want to share a web space, documents and good practices on actions against poverty. The results of the survey are disseminated by the Province of Pisa web site in an open data system.</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Monica Pratesi,</p> <p>m.pratesi@ec.unipi.it Pisa University</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Other Reports - Employment info Workforce - Official documents and Reports

<h1 style="margin: 0;">SUSTAINCITY</h1> <h2 style="margin: 0;">Micro-simulation for the prospective of sustainable cities in Europe</h2>	
<p>FP7-SSH-2009-A CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project From 2010-01-01 to 2013-06-30, 244557 Total Cost: EUR 3.884.803,8 EU Contribution: EUR 2.695.652 Web: http://www.sustaincity.org/ http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/94314_en.html</p>	
<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>This project proposed to improve urban simulation models and their interaction with transport models. Unified operational models that favour a microscopic approach, such as UrbanSim and ILUTE (Integrated Land Use, Transportation, and Environment Modelling System), in their current forms these models required further development to support a comprehensive analysis of the main environmental and socio-economic questions of the sustainability of urban growth and the relevant public policies.</p> <p>The goal of this project was to address the modelling and computational issues of integrating modern mobility simulations with the latest micro-simulation land use models.</p>
<p>Contribution to Social impact</p>	<p>Contributions to climate change target:</p> <p>This case study has proved that it is possible to develop and run a European version of UrbanSim which is consistent with all the specificities of the European context, and which provides an operational tool for policy evaluation, as illustrated in the Grand Paris project. UrbanSimE simulations provided key inputs for socio-economic analyses which show that the future benefits will largely exceed the initial investment.</p> <p>In response to the project's findings, the federal government of Switzerland has funded a much simpler land use-transport model (FALC) instead of the one that they used to fund.</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project coordinator: <u>Prof. Dr. Kay W. Axhausen.</u> <u>axhausen@collegium.ethz.ch</u> <u>axhausen@ivt.baug.ethz.ch</u> Institute for Transport Planning and Systems (IVT)</p>
<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final Report - Analysis Societal Implications Report - Employment info Workforce - Scientific Officer Interview - Scientific documents) <p>-Paper in a congress:</p>

	<p>Bodenmann, B.R, B.J. Vitins, I. Vecchi, A.J. Zeiler, J.K. Hackney, K.W. Axhausen(2013) FalC: an implementation of a land use transport interaction model for Switzerland, paper presented at 13th Swiss Transport Research Conference, Ascona, April 2013. http://www.strc.ch/conferences/2013/Bodenmann_Vecchi_STR_C13.pdf</p> <p>- European Policy Brief: SustainCity: Case studies in Paris, Zurich and Brussels http://www.sustaincity.org/D7.3_Policy_Brief_SustainCity_Case_Studies.pdf</p>
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TAP

The Assembly Project - Meeting Places in Northern Europe AD 400-1500

FP7 HERA Joint Research Programme 2009 –
 “Cultural Dynamics: Inheritance and Identity” and “Humanities as a Source of Creativity and Innovation”
Call: Cultural Dynamics: Inheritance and Identity.
From June 2010 to 2013.
Websites: <http://www.khm.uio.no/english/research/projects/assembly-project/>
<http://heranet.info/tap/index>

Aim & General information	<p>The TAP team consisted of a number of international scholars from Norway, Austria and the UK, who carried out a large scale study of the role of assemblies in the creation of collective identities and emergent kingdoms in Medieval Northern Europe (AD 400-1500). The project examined how authority was articulated in landscape terms in the medieval North by new and developing kings and kingdoms and how ideas of control and consensus were transferred and established.</p> <p>The team created a cohesive account of the development of administrative systems within early and late medieval Britain and Europe, taking account of the impacts and effects of Norse colonisation in several regions. They assessed how assemblies were valorised in pan-European perceptions in the early modern era, and how certain viewpoints were promoted by Romanticism and then by nationalism in the late 19th and 20th centuries.</p>
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Contribution to Social impact	<p>Contributions to employment target: Development of a Pilgrim Route and promotion of tourism as a result of the discoveries of historical sites, the Frosta' Municipality (Norway). They worked in cooperation with 4 counties and some municipalities in Norway, among them Frosta Municipality, Vestfold County and Vest-Agder County. In total they identified more than 500 sites of this kind only in Norway. Nearly each municipality would have a historical site of this kind.</p> <p>- Generating tourism: The ongoing activities in the sites (which are cheap activities) generate interest of both local people and also tourists. In this sense, in the particular case of the Vestfold County, the TAP project was fundamental for the elaboration of a plan that was delivered to the regional government at the beginning of 2015,</p>
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	which is expected to greatly promote tourism in the County.
Contact	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Frode Iversen, frode.iversen@khm.uio.no University of Oslo</p>
Sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IMPACT-EV Questionnaire - Main Researcher Interview - Other interview (Municipality) - Other documents (journal papers, official documents)

<h1 style="margin: 0;">TENLAW</h1> <h2 style="margin: 0;">Tenancy Law and Housing Policy in Multi-level Europe</h2>	
<p>FP7-SSH-2011-2, CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project</p> <p>From 2012-04-01 to 2015-09-30, 290694</p> <p>Total Cost: EUR 3 467 801,6 EU Contribution: EUR 2 692 526,45</p> <p>Web: http://www.tenlaw.uni-bremen.de/ http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/102183_en.html</p>	
<p>Aim & General information</p>	<p>The project sets out to provide the first large-scale comparative and European law survey of tenancy law. In a first step, it analysed national tenancy laws and their embeddedness in, and effects on, national housing policies and markets. In a second step, the effect of EU legislation on national housing policy in general and national tenancy law in particular were analysed in a comparative perspective. In a third step, a proposal for a better co-ordinating role of the EU in tenancy law and housing policy, in particular through an OMC process developing common principles of good "tenancy regulation", will be designed. This research matches well several priorities of the Stockholm programme given tenancy law's intimate relation to social human rights and a system of law and justice working for the benefit of European citizens, in particular vulnerable groups.</p>
<p>Contributions to Social impact</p>	<p>Contributions to poverty and social exclusion reduction target:</p> <p>Although it is an ongoing project, in the analysis of the Hungarian case, the project results show that the implementation of a Social Rental Agency system, plus a proper regulation of the Private Renting Sector, could be beneficial to the financial and allocative efficiency of the housing sector. Thus, these legal adjustments are showed by the project ongoing results to better manage the problems associated to low income households (e.g. families cannot afford rent and facilities, conflicts arisen, covering fixing expenses).</p>
<p>Contact</p>	<p>Project Co-ordinator: Christoph U. SCHMID, cschmid@zerp.uni-bremen.de Universität Bremen</p>

<p>Sources of information</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- IMPACT-EV Questionnaire- Scientific Officer Interview- Other documents (Scientific documents) <ul style="list-style-type: none">- <u>Hegedüs, J., V. Horváth and N. Tosics. 2014. Economic and legal conflicts between landlords and tenants in the Hungarian private rental sector. <i>International Journal of Housing Policy</i>, 14(2), 141-163.</u>- Project webpage
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Annex 7: Baseline statistics of projects (FP6 and FP7)

1. Motivation of a Baseline Statistics

ImpactEV aims to investigate the impact of SSH projects in FP6 and FP7 along different dimensions: scientific, economically, and societal. Questionnaires were sent out to the Principal investigators will be the main source of information. This will be complemented by a citation analysis of scientific output of these projects.

A right judgment of those specific results requires first to sketch the group of projects we analyze. Information about the number of projects, the main institutions involved, the volume and duration of investments provide the background against which the analysis of output and impact can be made. In other words, this kind of baseline statistics provides an input-side analysis.

Information about the funding programmes of the EC are stored in great detail in the CORDA database. The eCORDA database has been mined by the Barcelona team to explore the SSH funding' alignment with the EU overall objectives. (file EXPOST_SSHFP7)

This text summarizes an exploration into the public available part of the eCORDA database, **for both FP6 and FP7 RTD projects**. In different Linked Open Data projects, information from CORDIS (public) has been expressed as Linked Open Data, and those results are still available on the web and have been reused. They are in the meantime part of the open-data initiative of the EC, and are increasingly data mined by all kind of different projects (for an example see <http://www.ehumanities.nl/call-for-participation-talk-of-europe-creative-camp-2/> Talk of Europe – Travelling CLARIN Campus.

We base our baseline statistics on information collected from public available data sources. Those are:

1. Source: <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp6projects> and <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp7projects>
2. Source: websites of SSH projects

2. Inventory of projects – public available information from the CORDIS database

a. Data collection, description and cleaning

From the CORDIS website⁵³ complete lists of projects for the FP6 and FP7 programmes can be downloaded. The two websites contain the following files.

Please note that their content gets updated now and than. (See below)

⁵³ <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp6projects> and <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp7projects>

Resources		
DOWNLOAD	FP6 CORDIS project participants part 2	EXCEL
DOWNLOAD	FP6 CORDIS projects participants part 1	EXCEL
DOWNLOAD	FP6 Projects (complete with objectives)	CSV
DOWNLOAD	FP6 Projects (without objectives)	EXCEL
DOWNLOAD	FP6 Projects (without objectives)	CSV
DOWNLOAD	FP6 Projects complete (with objectives)	EXCEL

Snapshot from <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp6projects>

Resources		
DOWNLOAD	CORDIS FP7 Programmes	EXCEL
DOWNLOAD	CORDIS FP7 Programmes	CSV
DOWNLOAD	CORDIS SIC codes	CSV
DOWNLOAD	CORDIS SIC codes	EXCEL
DOWNLOAD	CORDIS activity codes	EXCEL
DOWNLOAD	CORDIS activity codes	CSV
DOWNLOAD	CORDIS country codes	EXCEL
DOWNLOAD	CORDIS country codes	CSV

Documentation		
DOWNLOAD	FP7 Projects extract	
DOWNLOAD	FP7 organisations	

Snapshot from <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp7projects>

From the datasets downloaded from the European Union Open Data Portal the following files have been used:

From CORDIS - EU research projects under FP6 (2002-2006)

- cordisfp6complete.csv (Extraction of all FP6 projects from the CORDIS public repository)
- fp6part1contractors.xls (FP6 CORDIS projects participants part 1)
- fp6part2contractors.xls (FP6 project participants part 2)

From CORDIS - EU research projects under FP7 (2007-2013)

- cordisfp7complete.csv (FP7 Projects extract)
- fp7part1contractors.csv (Not available on portal anymore)
- fp7part2contractors.csv (Not available on portal anymore)
- cordisfp7countries.csv (CORDIS country codes)

The downloaded files are in the directory cordis-data/. An index of all files in this directory is

in cordis-data/index.docx. An index of these files is in cordis-data/index.docx.

Re-inspection Oct 2014 Note 1158101419

New CORDIS dataset

In March 2014 we downloaded the CORDIS dataset on FP7-projects from <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data/dataset/cordisfp7projects>

If we now go to this site we find a rather different dataset, one would speak rather of a different edition than a different version. The release date mentioned on the above website is still 2013-11-27, the last modified date is now 2014-10-06.

What are the main differences between these datasets.

Files - overviews of FP7-projects

The version with modified date 2014-10-06 was downloaded Mon Jan 19 10:56:37 2015. The main difference in the set of files that make up the dataset is in the large table that is the overview of all projects under FP7. The list has grown from 22.652 projects to 30.068 projects. The file from March 2014 has 24 fields, a recently downloaded from January 2015 has 25 fields.

Filename	March 2014	Jan 2015
cordisfp7complete.csv	22652, 24	
fp7all12112014.csv		30068, 25

Though some fields in these large tables may have different names, their content remains of the same nature. But there are other fields that are quite different.

colnames(dt.march)	colnames(dt.all)
1 RCN	1 rcn
2 PROJECT_TITLE	2 reference
3 START_DATE	3 acronym
4 END_DATE	4 title
5 DURATION..MONTHS.	5 objective
6 STATUS	6 startDate
7 CONTRACT_NUMBER	7 endDate
8 KEYWORDS	8 totalCost
9 DATE_OF_SIGNATURE	9
10 TOTAL_COST	ecMaxContribution
11 TOTAL_FUNDING	10
12 ENTRY_DATE	programme
13 PROJECT_WEBSITE	11
14 OTHER_INFORMATION	subProgramme1
15 CALL	12
16	subProgramme2
FRAMEWORK_PROGRAMME	13 call
17 PROGRAMME	14 coordinator
18 PROJECT_ACRONYM	15
19 ACHIEVEMENTS	coordinatorCountry
20 ACTIVITY_AREA	16 participant
21 SUBJECTS	17
22 CONTRACT_TYPE	participantCountry
23 GENERAL_INFORMATION	18 report
24 OBJECTIVES	19 reportCount
	20 brief
	21 briefCount
	22 story
	23 storyCount
	24 br
	25 b

Left is column names March 2014 download, right is column names January 2015 download.

In the recent download for instance column 'contract type' is missing, so we can not do filtering for ImpactEV-projects anymore, because the filtering was (also) based on the value of this field. On the other hand we gain information, for instance the 'reportCount', 'briefCount' and 'storyCount' which we would otherwise have to scrape off the website http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/78639_en.html (based on project-rcn).

Of course we can select FP7-ImpactEV projects from the new dataset based on the rcn, the id for projects. Remarkable: in the newly downloaded 2 ImpactEV-projects are missing from the FP7 data: 109198 FLAGSHIP and 110433 MOPACT.

A comparison of the costs and funding values in both versions of the dataset shows small discrepancies on total cost; the funding has not changed. And off course the totals of the budgets differ, because of the two missing projects. See [Dropbox/DANS_ImpactEV/Projectdatabase WP 3/cordis-data-2015-01/data/derived/diff_fund.xlsx](#)

2.1.1 Fields in the Project Lists files

The complete lists of projects from FP6 and FP7 programmes respectively have slightly diverging field names. However, they can easily be matched. Table 1 lists all fields of the

structured information about projects in FP6 and FP7. The fields ‘Contractor Country’ and ‘Coordinator Country’ are missing from the FP7 list; ‘OTHER_INFORMATION’ is not in the FP6 list but lacks data in FP7 as well. In the table below fields from project lists from both programmes are matched.

FP6	FP7	blank	blank in subset
RCN	RCN		
Achievements	ACHIEVEMENTS	FP7	FP6 and FP7
Activity Area	ACTIVITY_AREA		
Project Call	CALL		
Contract Number	CONTRACT_NUMBER		
Contract Type	CONTRACT_TYPE		
Contractor Country	[filled from contractors table]		
Coordinator Country	[filled from contractors table]		
Date of Signature	DATE_OF_SIGNATURE	FP7	FP6 and FP7
Duration	DURATION (MONTHS)		
End Date	END_DATE		
	ENTRY_DATE		
Framework Programme	FRAMEWORK_PROGRAMME		
General Information	GENERAL_INFORMATION		FP6 and FP7
Keywords	KEYWORDS	FP7	FP6 and FP7
Objectives	OBJECTIVES		
	OTHER_INFORMATION	FP7	
PGA	PROGRAMME		
Project Acronym	PROJECT_ACRONYM		
Project Title	PROJECT_TITLE		
Project Website	PROJECT_WEBSITE		
Start Date	START_DATE		
Status	STATUS		
Subject	SUBJECTS		
Total Cost	TOTAL_COST		
Total Funding	TOTAL_FUNDING		

Table 1. Fields in projects complete. Field names matched in cordis-data/cordisfp6projectscomplete.xls and cordis-data/cordisfp7complete.xls

The column ‘blank’ in the above table indicates when all fields from the complete list of projects are blank; the column ‘blank in subset’ indicates when fields are lacking values in the subset of projects to be evaluated by the Impact-EV research effort. (See section 2. List of Projects)

2.1.2 Fields in the Contractor Lists files

The contractor lists that are available in both datasets (FP6 and FP 7) have exact matching fields. Table 2 has an overview.

The column ‘blank’ in the table indicates when all fields from all (part) lists are left empty.

FP6	FP7	Blank	notes
RCN	RCN		
Project Title	Project Title		
Contract Number	Contract Number		
Role	Role		
PJ_UID	PJ_UID		
Organization Name	Organization Name		
Organization Department	Organization Department		
Organization Subdepartment	Organization Subdepartment		
Organization Acronym	Organization Acronym		
Organization Size	Organization Size		0 or NULL for our subset
Organization Type	Organization Type		1 or NULL for our subset
Address	Address		
PO Box	PO Box		
Post Code	Post Code		
City	City		
Country	Country		seem to match ISO 3166: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-2
Organization Website	Organization Website		
PE_UID	PE_UID		
Contact Surname	Contact Surname		
Contact Name	Contact Name		

Contact Position	Contact Position	
Contact Initials	Contact Initials	FP6 and FP7
Contact Title	Contact Title	

Table 2. Fields in contractor lists. Field names matched in *cordis-data/fp6part1contractors.xls*, *cordis-data/fp6part2contractors.xls*, *cordis-data/fp7part1contractors.xls* and *cordis-data/fp7part2contractors.xls*

2.2 List of Core Projects

Due to the orientation of ImpactEV towards impact of *research projects* we have extracted from the list of projects from FP6 and FP7 programmes the RTD⁵⁴ projects. FP6 projects are further restricted by being 'last call'. According to the first selection made for ImpactEV, FP6 projects to be analyzed are 'last call' and 'RTD (i.e. IP and STREP)'.

2.2.1 FP6 Projects

In the CORDIS-dataset the projects EUROCCUPATIONS and ACRE have the wrong information in the fields 'Project Call' and 'PGA' respectively. If we correct this information and then filter the complete set of projects under FP6 according to

PGA: FP6-CITIZENS
 contract type: STREP or IP
 Project Call: FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4 or FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5 or FP6-2004-CITIZENS-6

we end up with a list of 58 projects under FP6.

2.2.2 FP7 Projects

FP7 projects to be analyzed are also RTD.

If we filter *cordis-data/cordisfp7complete.xls* on...

PROGRAMME: FP7-SSH
 CONTRACT_TYPE: CP-FP or CP-IP

we end up with exactly 164 projects.

2.2.3 Project list

Combining the lists gotten from selections described in 2.1 and 2.2 gives a complete list that has a count of 222 projects. Leaving out the fields that contain no data we are left with the following 21 fields:

RCN
 PROJECT_TITLE
 START_DATE
 END_DATE
 DURATION (MONTHS)
 STATUS
 CONTRACT_NUMBER
 TOTAL_COST
 TOTAL_FUNDING
 ENTRY_DATE
 PROJECT_WEBSITE
 CALL
 FRAMEWORK_PROGRAMME
 PROGRAMME
 PROJECT_ACRONYM
 ACTIVITY_AREA
 SUBJECTS
 CONTRACT_TYPE
 OBJECTIVES
 [coordinator country]
 [contractor country]

Mind that [coordinator country] and [contractor country] are blank fields for FP7 projects.

⁵⁴ RTD: Research and Technological Development, source: http://cordis.europa.eu/fp7/capacities/regions-knowledge_en.html

2.3 Institutes

In order to create collaboration networks, we need to uniquely identify the institutes. Only institutes attached to the project-subset are considered (215 of the 222 projects have contractor data). At the moment of creation, 1128 different institutes were identified, within the 2277 contractor-rows.

```
mysql> create table institutes (volgnr int primary key auto_increment, rcn int, country varchar(2), acronym varchar(20), title
varchar(255), role tinyint, id int)
-> ;
Query OK, 0 rows affected (0.00 sec)

mysql> load data local infile '/tmp/institutes_with_ids.csv' into table institutes fields terminated by ',' enclosed by '"' lines terminated
by '\n' (volgnr, rcn, country, acronym, title, role, id);
```

3. Baseline Statistics

In cordis-data-work/project-list-work.xlsx we have corrected the field 'Programme' for the project 'ACRE' from 'FP6-LIFESCIHEALTH' to 'FP6-CITIZENS'. Following baseline statistics are based upon this corrected data.

3.1 Projects per Call

Project call	Count	TOTAL_COST	TOTAL_FUNDING
FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	12	€ 57.313.435	€ 50.336.249
FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	46	€ 62.596.376	€ 53.571.957
FP7-SSH-2007-1	90	€ 162.499.626	€ 123.444.714
FP7-SSH-2009-A	25	€ 77.008.382	€ 59.611.187
FP7-SSH-2010-1	5	€ 50.245.190	€ 39.743.449
FP7-SSH-2010-2	10	€ 29.622.932	€ 23.545.223
FP7-SSH-2011-1	4	€ 40.289.088	€ 30.979.469
FP7-SSH-2011-2	11	€ 36.297.162	€ 28.202.790
FP7-SSH-2012-1	6	€ 48.786.996	€ 38.308.855
FP7-SSH-2012-2	13	€ 39.995.742	€ 31.922.165
Grand Total	222	€ 604.654.929	€ 479.666.058

3.2 Projects per Programme

Programme	Count	TOTAL_COST	TOTAL_FUNDING
FP6-CITIZENS	58	€ 119.909.811	€ 103.908.206
FP7-SSH	164	€ 484.745.118	€ 375.757.852
Grand Total	222	€ 604.654.929	€ 479.666.058

3.3 Projects per Status

Pivot table in project-list_as.xls

Count of Award number	Column Labels		Grand Total
	Completed	Execution (blank)	
Row Labels	Completed	Execution (blank)	Grand Total
FP6-2004-CITIZENS-4	12		12
FP6-2004-CITIZENS-5	46		46
FP7-SSH-2007-1	90		90
FP7-SSH-2009-A	24	1	25
FP7-SSH-2010-1		5	5
FP7-SSH-2010-2		10	10
FP7-SSH-2011-1		4	4
FP7-SSH-2011-2		11	11
FP7-SSH-2012-1		6	6
FP7-SSH-2012-2		13	13
(blank)			
Grand Total	172	50	222

There are still 50 projects ongoing.

3.4 Projects per Duration

Distribution of duration of projects: Between 24 and 66 almost all lengths of months are occupied. But clearly, three years are favored, with almost 50% of the projects falling in the three year period.

3.5 Visualization of Projects – timeline

We visualized 223 projects (both FP6 and FP7) using the Sci2tool (<https://sci2.cns.iu.edu/user/index.php>) and the so-called temporal bar graph visualization. Here each bar represents a project, which full title is used as label. The bars are ordered according to start and end date. The width of the bars is coded by the budget allocated to the projects. By visual inspection one can deduce that in later years the assigned budget per project increases. With an average of 1.7 Mio EUR per project in FP6, and 2.3 EUR per project in FP7, SSH projects are rather small-mid scale.

Temporal Visualization

[Generated from CSV file: /var/olders/zl/rf_lcv964vc1q82plq40140000gs77temp/Preprocessed-project-list_LR-5445770808147689517.csv]
May 13, 2014 | 11:15 AM CEST

Temporal Visualization

(Generated from CSV file: /var/folders/zl/rf_lcv964vc1q82pkq40140000gs/T/temp/Preprocessed-project-list_LR-5445770808147689517.csv)
May 13, 2014 | 11:15 AM CEST

Legend

Area size: size by
Minimum = 217,874
Maximum = 7,999,858
Text label: label

Area

How To Read This Map

This temporal bar graph visualization represents each record as a horizontal bar with a specific start and end date and a text label on its left side. The area of each bar encodes a numerical attribute value, e.g., total amount of funding. Bars may be colored to present categorical attribute values of records.

CNS (cns.lu.edu)

Temporal Visualization

(Generated from CSV file: /var/folders/zl/rf_lcv964vc1q82pkq40140000gs/T/temp/Preprocessed-project-list_LR-5445770808147689517.csv)
May 13, 2014 | 11:15 AM CEST

Legend

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CNS (cns.lu.edu)

Temporal Visualization

(Generated from CSV file: /var/folders/zl/rf_lcv864vc1q82pkq40140000gs/T/temp/Preprocessed-project-list_LR-5445770808147689517.csv)
 May 13, 2014 | 11:15 AM CEST

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CNS (cns.lu.edu)

Temporal Visualization

(Generated from CSV file: /var/folders/zl/rf_lcv864vc1q82pkq40140000gs/T/temp/Preprocessed-project-list_LR-5445770808147689517.csv)
 May 13, 2014 | 11:15 AM CEST

Legend
 Area size: size by
 Minimum = 217,874
 Maximum = 7,999,858
 Text label: label

How To Read This Map

This temporal bar graph visualization represents each record as a horizontal bar with a specific start and end date and a text label on its left side. The area of each bar encodes a numerical attribute value, e.g., total amount of funding. Bars may be colored to present categorical attribute values of records.

CNS (cns.lu.edu)

3.6 Project Titles – textual analysis

Throwing textual data from the project-list at Wordle can give a first impression about what

Mathematics, Statistics	1
Forecasting	1
Reference Materials	1
Biotechnology	1
Telecommunications	2
Standards	2
Climate change & Carbon cycle research	2
Sustainable development	3
Environmental Protection	3
Business aspects	3
Research ethics	4
Employment issues	4
Evaluation	5
Innovation, Technology Transfer	5
Other Technology	6
Information, Media	11
Education, Training	11
Coordination, Cooperation	12
Regional Development	14
Legislation, Regulations	16
Scientific Research	27
Policies	33
Economic Aspects	33
Social Aspects	162
<i>Total</i>	<i>366</i>

If we extend the analysis to all projects we get the following word frequencies.

FP6 subjects	word count	percentage	FP7 subjects	word count	percentage
aspects	48	25%	aspects	150	30%
social	41	21%	social	121	24%
policies	20	10%	research	27	5%
legislation	13	7%	economic	26	5%
regulations	13	7%	scientific	21	4%
coordination	10	5%	development	17	3%
cooperation	7	4%	regional	14	3%
economic	6	3%	policies	13	3%
scientific	6	3%	technology	11	2%
research	6	3%	information	10	2%

Table 5. Word count from FP6 and FP7 SUBJECTs

Fig. 3. Wordle of the values of field SUBJECTS from both FP6 and FP7

3.9 Call Objectives

FP6	word count	percentage	FP7 objectives	word count	percentage
social	115	2%	policy	320	2%
european	105	1%	project	290	2%
project	101	1%	european	248	1%
research	87	1%	research	231	1%
eu	77	1%	social	227	1%
policy	69	1%	eu	153	1%
knowledge	61	1%	policies	153	1%
political	56	1%	economic	144	1%
policies	56	1%	europe	135	1%
national	54	1%	development	124	1%

Table 6. Word count from FP6 and FP7 OBJECTIVES

Fig. 4. Wordle of the values of field OBJECTIVES from both FP6 and FP7

3.10 Projects, Countries, Institutions

Of the 222 projects (FP 6 and FP 7) we list the countries of the coordinator. Please note that there are still data problems (category unknown or empty).

Coordinator Country	Projects
LT	1
TR	1
HU	1
PT	2
PL	2
IE	2
EMPTY	3
DK	4
SE	5
NO	5
CH	5
FI	6
UNKNOWN	7
GR	7
ES	7
BE	11
AT	13
FR	16
NL	23
IT	26
DE	29
GB	46
<i>Total</i>	<i>222</i>

One can also ask, how big are the consortia in terms of number of countries involved. We create a distribution function: y =Number of projects with x countries involved projects and the number of countries involved:

```
create temporary table projects_countries as select p.rcn, count(c.country) as institutes, count(distinct country) as countries from projects p inner join contractors c on p.rcn=c.rcn where impact=1 group by p.rcn;
Query OK, 215 rows affected (11.91 sec)
```

```
select count(rcn), countries into outfile '/tmp/project_countries.csv' from projects_countries group by countries;
```

projects and the number of countries involved

This graph can be read as follows. There are some few projects which have 3 countries – given this is the minimum number of countries for funding we find no smaller consortia. Most of the projects (37) have 6 countries involved. But there is a great range around the *magic number 6*. There is a drop in number of projects with more than 10 countries. There is only one project with 18 and one with 19 projects.

Is size correlated to success and impact? Have smaller consortia a higher chance to succeed, because they are less complex to coordinate? Or is the final success exclusively driven by the quality of the consortium members?

We did the same kind of distribution function on the level of institutes

projects and nr of institutes involved

Not surprisingly there is some similarity to the distribution across countries. In most cases we will have one institution representing a country. The longer tail of the distribution of projects over institutions indicates the cases in which more than one institution from a country is involved.

```
mysql> select c.rcn, country, organization_acronym, organization_name,role into outfile '/tmp/institutes.csv' from contractors c
inner join projects p on p.rcn=c.rcn where impact=1 order by country, organization_name;
Query OK, 2277 rows affected (3.89 sec)
```

There are 1127 institutions involved with our 222 projects, some 300 are involved in more than one project.

These are the 10 institutions with the most collaborating partners, ranging from 89 to 142.

Are those projects we evaluate as successful linked to any of those institutions? How important is experience in finally succeeding with projects?

with these labels;

```
select * from institutes where id in (1395, 1065, 2127, 1840, 819, 774, 126, 1822, 885, 176)
```

	126	BE	K.U.LEUVEN	
	176	BE	ULB	
	774	ES	UAB	
	819	FI	Helsinki	
	885	FR	CNRS	
	1065	GB	LSE	
	1395	HU	CEU	
	1822	NL	UU	
	1840	NL	UVA	
	2127	SE	SCORE	

3.11 Countries and subjects

Using the Sci2 tool we build a bipartite network between the countries (of the coordinator) on the one side and the subjects.

Network Visualization

Subjects (weighted: 1/count subjects per project) per coordinating country
May 14, 2014 | 6:21 PM CEST

Legend

Sorted by
Left side:
Weight
Right side:
Weight

How To Read This Map

This bipartite network shows two record types and their interconnections. Each record is represented by a labeled circle that is size coded by a numerical attribute value. Records of each type are vertically aligned and sorted, e.g., by node size or alphabetically. Links between records of different type may be weighted as represented by line thickness.

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